

Blak Training Center

Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan and Environmental Assessment

Prepared for
Oregon
Military Department
Salem, Oregon

Prepared by
Tetra Tech, Inc.

SAN FRANCISCO, CALIFORNIA

October 2001

**INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN
AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT
Biak Training Center**

Lead Agency: National Guard Bureau, Oregon Military Department

Cooperating Agencies: Bureau of Land Management
US Fish and Wildlife Service
Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife

Title of Proposed Action: Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan and Environmental Assessment for the Biak Training Center, Oregon

Affected Jurisdictions: Crook and Deschutes Counties

Designation: Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan and Environmental Assessment, October 2001

ABSTRACT

The Biak Training Center (BTC) consists of approximately 31,400 acres of federal public lands managed by the Bureau of Land Management (BLM). The Oregon Army National Guard (ORARNG) trains military personnel on these public lands through a special use permit provided by the BLM. The ORARNG is proposing to implement an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) that would enable the ORARNG and BLM to cooperatively manage the natural resources at the BTC and to support the military mission from fiscal years 2002 to 2006. This INRMP has been prepared in accordance with the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, Army Regulation 200-3, applicable Department of Defense directives, and National Guard Bureau guidance. The document addresses the interrelationships among the natural resources managed by the BLM at the BTC (including soils, wildlife, vegetative communities, and outdoor recreation) and the military mission. Without effective and proactive natural resources management, components of the military mission could be jeopardized, especially those related to military training using all-terrain vehicles. This plan provides a flexible program to balance natural resources stewardship and military needs. The INRMP identifies a number of goals and objectives for specific natural resources at the BTC that the ORARNG would implement under cooperative management with the BLM, including controlling invasive species, maintaining and restoring vegetative communities, abating wildfire and dust, managing soils, identifying potentially occurring sensitive species, and minimizing conflict with livestock grazing practices. Specific management strategies are proposed to meet the specific goals and objectives.

The INRMP contains baseline information that supports compliance with regulatory and planning processes. To fulfill the requirements of the National Environmental Policy Act of 1969, an environmental assessment (EA) has been prepared to assess possible impacts from implementing the INRMP and from taking no action. The EA has been integrated into this document, and for this reason this joint document is commonly referred to as the INRMP/EA. No significant adverse environmental impacts have been identified from implementing this INRMP.

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October 2001

**Biak Training Center
Deschutes and Crook Counties, Oregon
Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
Fiscal Years 2002 - 2006**

This Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) meets the requirements for such plans listed in the Sikes Act (16 USC 670a *et seq.*) and Sikes Act Improvement Act, Army Regulation 200-3, applicable Department of Defense directives, and National Guard Bureau guidance and memoranda (specifically the All-States Memorandum of June 15, 2000). The INRMP also complies with all applicable state and federal regulatory requirements. The INRMP sets appropriate and adequate guidelines for conserving and protecting the natural resources to the maximum extent practicable, without unduly limiting or restricting military training activities and opportunities at the Biak Training Center.

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FINDING OF NO SIGNIFICANT IMPACT
for
Implementation of an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
at
Biak Training Center, Deschutes and Crook Counties, Oregon
Oregon Military Department/Oregon Army National Guard

The Oregon Military Department (OMD) prepared a combined Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) and Environmental Assessment (EA) for the Biak Training Center (BTC), a 31,400-acre training site used by Oregon Army National Guard (ORARNG) and located in Deschutes and Crook counties, Oregon. The EA evaluates the potential environmental effects from implementing the INRMP. It was prepared in accordance with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), the Council on Environmental Quality Regulations, and Army Regulation 200-2 Environmental Effects of Army Actions.

A. Description of Proposed Action and Alternatives

Proposed Action.—OMD/ORARNG proposes to adopt and implement an INRMP to provide an integrated and comprehensive method for managing natural resources at BTC. The INRMP is designed to manage natural resources to support high quality training lands in accordance with applicable environmental laws and regulations. Preparation and implementation of the INRMP is required by the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997 (16 U.S.C 670a *et seq.*). The INRMP defines roles and responsibilities for natural resources management at all levels within the ORARNG. It provides a rational, tiered, and uniform basis for addressing all applicable legal requirements and best management practices consistent with achievement of the needs, goals, and objectives of the ORARNG's military and environmental missions.

Alternatives Considered.—In addition to the proposed action, a No Action alternative was analyzed. Current natural resources compliance and management actions would continue under the No Action alternative, but there would be no comprehensive plan to integrate mission needs with natural resources protection. This alternative is not viable because it does not support the mission of the ORARNG and does not meet the Sikes Act requirements. Nevertheless, analysis of the No Action alternative is required by CEQ regulations to serve as a benchmark against which the proposed action could be evaluated.

Other management alternatives were considered and eliminated during the initial evaluation. The eliminated alternatives failed to meet the screening criteria that require satisfying both mission needs and natural resources protection.

B. Environmental Analysis

The analysis of the potential environmental impacts of the proposed action is documented in Section 7 of the INRMP/EA for the following resources: air quality, noise, soils, water resources, biological resources, endangered, threatened, and rare species, cultural resources, land use, socioeconomic resources, and environmental justice. Implementation of the INRMP/EA would result in no adverse effects to the natural or human environment, and in many cases would result in beneficial effects to natural resources from management that improves the existing environmental conditions at BTC.

Although no significant impacts are expected from implementing the No Action alternative, adverse effects may occur over the long-term from not establishing a comprehensive approach for natural resources management and evaluation. Selecting the No Action alternative would also result in not meeting the Sikes Act requirements.

C. Mitigation

No mitigation measures will be required as a result of implementing the INRMP/EA at BTC. Implementation of the INRMP/EA is predominantly a management decision that will not of itself cause any negative impacts to the natural resources at BTC. Adoption of the INRMP/EA will result in better protective measures for BTC's natural resources. Individual projects undertaken at a later date in compliance with the procedures outlined in the INRMP/EA may result in actions that could require mitigation measures. Appropriate mitigation measures will be identified and implemented at that time, as warranted.

D. Regulations

There are no indications that implementation of this action will violate any federal, state, or local environmental laws or regulations, including the National Environmental Policy Act (42 USC § 4321 to 4370e), its regulations as promulgated by the Council on Environmental Quality (40 CFR Parts 1500-1508) and Army Regulation 200-2 "Environmental Effects of Army Actions." The INRMP/EA documents the status of project compliance with applicable federal environmental statutes and executive orders.

E. Public Review and Comment

Scoping letters were sent to Federal, state, and local agencies and Native American tribes requesting input on the proposed action. Responses were incorporated into the draft INRMP/EA. In August 2001, a Notice of Availability and legal advertisement for the draft INRMP/EA were placed in local newspapers. Letters and the draft INRMP/EAs were also mailed to Federal, state, and local agencies and Native American tribes. No issues significant to natural resources management were identified. Comments were received from the state and federal wildlife management agencies, three other government agencies, one organization, and one member of the general public, and were addressed in the final INRMP/EA as appropriate.

The final INRMP/EA is available for review at the following locations: Crook County Public Library in Prineville and the Deschutes County Public Library in Bend and Redmond, OR. Written comments on this Finding of No Significant Impact and the INRMP/EA should be submitted to the Oregon Military Department, ATTN: AGI-ENV (Gerald Elliott), PO Box 14350, Salem, OR 97309-5047. Questions or requests for additional information may be directed to the OMD Environmental Office at (503) 584-3851 during business hours (8:00 A.M.-4:00 P.M.). The deadline for receipt of comments is 30 days from publication of the Notice of Availability.

E. Finding of No Significant Impact

A careful review of the environmental assessment has concluded that the implementation of an INRMP/EA at BTC will not have any significant impact on the quality of the existing natural or human environment. The requirements of the National Environmental Policy Act and the Council on Environmental Quality regulations have been satisfied and an Environmental Impact Statement will not be prepared.

5 Oct 01
Date

RICHARD O. MURPHY
COL, National Guard Bureau
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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Full Phrase
AGI-ENV	Environmental Branch of the Oregon Military Department
Annex	Draft Safety, Fire, and Emergency Services Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures
AR	Army Regulation
AST	Aboveground Storage Tank
AUM	Animal Unit Month
AVLB	Armored Vehicle-Launched Bridge
BEA	Bureau of Economic Analysis
BLM	Bureau of Land Management
BLS	Bureau of Labor Statistics
BTC	Biak Training Center
CAA	Clean Air Act
CEMML	Center for Ecological Management of Military Lands
CEQ	Council on Environmental Quality
CERCLA	Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation, and Liability Act
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
COE	US Army Corps of Engineers
COUTES	Central Oregon Unit Training Equipment Site
CWA	Clean Water Act
DA	Department of the Army
dB	Decibel
dBA	A-weighted Decibel Scale
DOD	Department of Defense
EA	Environmental Assessment
ECAS	Environmental Compliance Assessment System
EO	Executive Order
EPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency
ESA	Endangered Species Act
F	Fahrenheit
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FLPMA	Federal Land Policy and Management Act
FR	Federal Register
HSWA	Hazardous and Solid Waste Amendments
ICRMP	Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan
INRMP	Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
IRP	Installation Restoration Program
ITAM	Integrated Training Area Management
IWM	Integrated Weed Management
LCTA	Land Condition-Trend Analysis
DNL	Day-Night Average Noise Level
LRAM	Land Rehabilitation and Maintenance

LIST OF ACRONYMS *(continued)*

Acronym	Full Phrase
NCES	National Center for Education Statistics
NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
NGB	National Guard Bureau
NHPA	National Historic Preservation Act
NRCS	Natural Resources Conservation Service
NRHP	National Register of Historic Places
NUID	North Unit Irrigation District
OAR	Oregon Administrative Rules
ODA	Oregon Department of Agriculture
ODEQ	Oregon Department of Environmental Quality
ODFW	Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife
OMD	Oregon Military Department
ONHP	Oregon Natural Heritage Program
ORARNG	Oregon Army National Guard
ORS	Oregon Revised Statutes
OSU	Oregon State University
PL	Public Law
PM	Particulate Matter
POL	Petroleum, Oil, and Lubricants
RCRA	Resource Conservation and Recovery Act
SARA	Superfund Amendments and Reauthorization Act
SIP	State Implementation Plan
TRI	Training Requirements Integration
UGB	Urban Growth Boundary
US	United States
USC	United States Code
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
USFWS	United States Fish and Wildlife Service

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

INTRODUCTION

The Biak Training Center (BTC) consists of approximately 31,400 acres of federal public lands managed by the Bureau of Land Management (BLM). The legal land description of the BTC is provided as Appendix A. The Oregon Army National Guard (ORARNG) trains military personnel on these public lands through a special use permit provided by the BLM. The ORARNG is proposing to implement an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) that would enable the ORARNG and BLM to cooperatively manage the natural resources at the BTC and support the military mission from fiscal years 2002 to 2006. To meet the requirements of 16 USC §§ 670a(b)(2), this INRMP will be updated on a regular basis and no less frequently than every five years. This INRMP has been prepared in accordance with the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, National Guard Bureau (NGB) policy, Department of Defense (DOD) policy, specific guidance contained in All-States Memorandum P00-0039 of June 15, 2000, and other military regulations for natural resources management. It addresses the interrelationships among the natural resources managed by the BLM at the BTC (including soils, wildlife, vegetative communities, outdoor recreation) and the military mission. Without effective and proactive natural resources management, components of the military mission could be jeopardized.

The INRMP provides an adaptive management program to balance natural resources stewardship and military needs. It identifies a number of goals and objectives for specific natural resources at the BTC that the ORARNG and BLM would implement, including controlling invasive species, maintaining and restoring vegetative communities, abating wildfire and dust, managing soils, identifying potentially occurring sensitive species, and minimizing conflict with livestock grazing practices. Specific management strategies are proposed to meet the goals and objectives. The INRMP has been prepared in cooperation with the BLM but is considered an ORARNG document and is subordinate to the *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989) for central Oregon.

The INRMP contains baseline information to comply with regulatory and planning processes. To fulfill the requirements of the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) of 1969, PL 91-190 (42 USC §§ 4321 - 4370d), an environmental assessment

(EA) has been prepared to assess possible impacts from implementing the INRMP. This EA has been integrated into this document, and this joint document is referred to as the INRMP/EA.

The BTC is in Deschutes and Crook counties in central Oregon and consists almost entirely of federal public lands located approximately three miles southeast of the city of Redmond and fourteen miles northeast of the city of Bend. With the exception of three small parcels of military-controlled land (approximately 35 acres controlled by the ORARNG, 6.4 acres leased to the ORARNG by the city of Redmond, and 75 acres of federally withdrawn land controlled by the ORARNG), the BTC consists of lands administered and managed under the concept of multiple-use by the BLM. In that regard, the BLM has continually issued a special use permit to the ORARNG since the 1960s to allow for military training to occur at the BTC. As a result, ORARNG actions must be closely coordinated with the BLM to ensure that federal mandates for managing the natural resources are met.

The primary military mission at the BTC is to provide training facilities and terrain for the soldiers of the military. All-terrain vehicles (both tracked and wheeled) are used to train cavalry, engineer, anti-armor, and infantry troops in a natural realistic setting. Most of the federal public lands remain open and easily accessible for public use. The primary nonmilitary uses of the BTC include, but are not limited to, livestock grazing, all-terrain vehicular recreation, target shooting, rockhounding, hiking, biking, and wildlife viewing. The ORARNG controls or manages none of these activities; the INRMP addresses only those natural resources potentially impacted by military training.

PURPOSE OF AND NEED FOR THE PROPOSED ACTION

The purpose of the INRMP is to guide the ORARNG in cooperatively managing, with the BLM, the natural resources on the federal public lands that compose the BTC from fiscal years 2002 to 2006 and to provide a solid foundation for the program beyond 2006. The INRMP is designed to be a programmatic document that would help the BTC ensure the sustainability of the military mission while maintaining the integrity of the ecological process and its ecosystems. In addition, the INRMP would ensure that natural resources conservation measures and military training activities at the BTC are integrated and are consistent with the BLM's *Brother/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989), as well as other federal and military stewardship requirements.

The need for this INRMP is threefold, as follows:

- The INRMP is required by the Natural Resources Management on Military Lands Act of 1960 (commonly known as the Sikes Act), the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, NGB policy, DOD policy, and guidance contained in the All-States Memorandum P00-0039 dated June 15, 2000.
- The INRMP provides an adaptive ecosystem management framework to integrate various management programs. The ORARNG's natural resources management program has surveyed a number of resource-

specific media, including the presence and integrity of vegetative communities at the BTC, special status, threatened, and endangered species that could reside on or migrate through the federal public lands that compose the BTC, and long-term trend monitoring of baseline ecological conditions using the Army's Land Condition-Trend Analysis (LCTA) program. Implementation of the INRMP would resolve potential conflicts among different plans, while maximizing cooperation among different programs. It is Army policy to incorporate ecosystem management as the basis for planning and managing lands used by the Army and Army National Guard by taking a long-term view of human activities, including military uses, and biological resources as part of the same environment. The goals are to enhance ecosystem integrity and to sustain both biological diversity and continued availability of those resources for military and other human uses.

- The INRMP would support the BTC's military mission through the continued training of military personnel in safe land use and management practices.

PUBLIC INVOLVEMENT, AGENCY COORDINATION, AND TRIBAL CONSULTATION

A 30-day public comment period was provided for public review of the draft INRMP. The ORARNG solicited public comment on the draft INRMP through notices in local newspapers and by direct distribution to interested parties. Representatives from federal and state resource management agencies were invited to review the draft INRMP. Copies of the draft INRMP were made available at three area libraries and by request. Four Native American tribes were sent copies of the preliminary draft INRMP/EA in May 2001, were notified of the availability of the draft INRMP/EA in August 2001, and will receive copies of the final INRMP/EA on request. Public agency and tribal representatives have been asked to attend meetings on the INRMP to provide direct input to the plan development. A comprehensive listing of individuals and agencies contacted is provided as Appendix B.

In total, two government agencies, one organization, and one individual commented in writing on the draft INRMP. Copies of these letters are contained in Appendix B, which also outlines how all comments are addressed in this document.

NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT AND THE MILITARY MISSION

Natural resources used by the DOD are to be managed in accordance with numerous laws, regulations, Executive Orders, and DOD instructions. These documents direct the Secretary of the Army to carry out a natural resources management program to balance sustainable military readiness, sustainable environmental stewardship, and sustainable economic development. The BLM's role for the INRMP is as a public agency reviewer for NEPA content and process; it is not a cooperating agency under NEPA. The BLM has reviewed the document and has determined concurrence for the final INRMP. The USFWS and ODFW are cooperating agencies and have been involved in the development and review of the INRMP. As discussed in Sections 1.8.3

and 1.8.5, these agencies serve as primary federal and state authorities on fish and wildlife management. The INRMP reflects mutual agreement of USFWS and ODFW concerning conservation, protection, and management of fish and wildlife resources.

AFFECTED ENVIRONMENT

The affected environment of the federal public lands that compose the BTC includes vegetative communities, land use, facilities, climate, geology, soil resources, water resources, wetlands, wildlife resources, special status species, cultural resources, air quality, noise, public health and safety, socioeconomic resources, and environmental justice. No known encumbrances were identified that would impede the military mission or the use of ecosystem management at the BTC.

MANAGEMENT GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

Management goals and objectives for the affected environment are provided in Section 5. The management goals and objectives have been developed to complement and agree with the BLM's *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989). Section 5 also lists specific management strategies that will be implemented in relation to the goals and objectives.

The goals and objectives provide the backbone of the INRMP. Adaptive management would be used to implement the INRMP. Adaptive management is essentially treating management actions and decisions as experiments that need to be tested to verify their effectiveness in reaching the desired results (Leslie et al. 1996). Monitoring programs are used for testing or verification of these experiments. Monitoring results are then incorporated into the decision-making process to either support current actions and decisions or to revise them into new experiments (actions and decisions). Thus, a feedback loop is established to continually evaluate and update management. Some maintain that this is synonymous with ecosystem management (Leslie et al. 1996).

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROPOSED ACTION AND ALTERNATIVES

To reduce duplication of effort and to streamline the decision-making process, Army guidelines recommend that an INRMP and its associated NEPA analysis and documentation be prepared concurrently. As such, the ORARNG has integrated the INRMP and NEPA compliance requirements into this INRMP/EA document. In accordance with NEPA, the ORARNG has identified a proposed action and alternatives for evaluation. The proposed action is to implement the INRMP for the BTC. This proposal would meet the ORARNG's underlying need to train soldiers in a realistic setting that is in compliance with environmental regulations and policies.

Two alternatives are evaluated in the EA portion of this document: implement the INRMP using an ecosystem paradigm, or take no action and continue with current management measures. Each alternative is discussed below, and Table 7-1 in Section 7 provides an overview of the alternatives' differences.

Alternative 1: Implement Ecosystem-based INRMP

Under this alternative, the ORARNG and BTC would implement the INRMP approach outlined in Section 5, focusing on sustaining military readiness and promoting ecological stewardship and conserving biodiversity, per BLM, DOD, DA, NGB, and ORARNG guidelines, particularly the Sikes Act, as described in Section 2 and Appendix D. Under this alternative, all management issues that are important to the military mission, legal compliance, and ecological health are given a high priority. An adaptive management strategy would be instituted to conduct additional research, to monitor management actions, to reassess the function of management tools, and to revise the management plan accordingly. Alternative 1 would continue to be a subordinate management plan to the *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989) but proposes additional stewardship-based management strategies beyond those related to compliance.

No Action Alternative

The No Action Alternative is continued implementation of the land management recommendations outlined under the BLM's *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989) with no additional stewardship-based conservation measures proposed. The current program focuses on the management concept of multiple-use as a top priority. This alternative broadly supports all natural resources and generally emphasizes specific management areas. In this regard, the level of effort of the No Action Alternative is less than that proposed in Alternative 1. Inclusion of a No Action Alternative is required by the Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) regulations and serves as a benchmark against which proposed federal actions are evaluated.

Alternatives Considered but Eliminated

The ORARNG worked with the ODFW, USFWS, and BLM to identify conservation projects to sustain military readiness, promote environmental stewardship, and conserve biodiversity. Many different concepts and approaches were discussed and considered. These alternatives were eventually dismissed because they would not provide sufficient and/or cost effective protection to natural and cultural resources. In other cases, alternatives were dropped because they eliminated training opportunities or compromised the military mission, were inconsistent with state or federal laws and regulations, or had excessive environmental impacts. Preparation and full implementation of the INRMP is an Army requirement. As such, other alternatives, including partial implementation of the INRMP, were considered but were dismissed as infeasible, impracticable, or precluded by legal insufficiency.

Environmental Consequences

The environmental consequences section (Section 7) evaluates the potential impacts to the affected environment (Section 3) that would result from implementing the various alternatives. For any identified impacts, a determination has been made as to whether they would constitute a significant or less than significant impact. In addition, many of the potential benefits of implementing proposed management strategies are identified. Criteria used to assess each alternative's adverse or beneficial impacts, as well as significance thresholds for adverse impacts, are identified in Section 7.

Overall, implementing the INRMP would result in no significant adverse impacts to environmental resources. Implementation of the INRMP would likely result in beneficial impacts to land use, soils, vegetation, wildlife, special status species, cultural resources, air quality, and public health and safety.

CUMULATIVE EFFECTS

The cumulative effects evaluation analyzes the incremental impacts of the proposed action in conjunction with other public and private projects that are expected to be implemented during the same period as would the proposed action. Nine such projects are considered. Implementing the INRMP with any other proposed management actions at the BTC would not result in any significant adverse impacts to local natural or cultural resources. Public access would continue to be provided at the BTC. Implementing other proposed management actions under the No Action Alternative could result in increased use of public lands at the BTC. Implementation of the INRMP would not result in any additional increase to public land use beyond the increases expected under the No Action Alternative. Implementing the INRMP would not affect the amount of training at the BTC, so issues such as transportation would not be affected by the INRMP. The potential for beneficial impacts is substantially increased by implementing the INRMP. No details for substantially increasing the level of the military mission or training schedule at the BTC have been proposed at this time; therefore, the contribution of such an action to cumulative conditions cannot be assessed.

IMPLEMENTATION OF INRMP AND MILITARY MISSION

Implementation of the INRMP would not result in adverse effects to the military mission.

SECTION 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The Army will be a national leader in environmental and natural resources stewardship for present and future generations as an integral part of our mission.

US Army Environmental Strategy into the 21st Century, 1992

The Biak Training Center (BTC) consists of approximately 31,400 acres of federal public lands managed by the Bureau of Land Management (BLM). The legal land description of the BTC is provided as Appendix A. The Oregon Army National Guard (ORARNG) trains military personnel on these public lands through a special use permit provided by the BLM. The ORARNG is proposing to implement an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) that would enable the ORARNG and BLM to cooperatively manage the natural resources at the BTC and support the military mission from fiscal years 2002 to 2006. The INRMP also provides a solid foundation on which to build the program beyond 2006. To meet the requirements of 16 USC §§ 670a(b)(2), this INRMP will be updated on a regular basis and no less frequently than every five years. This INRMP has been prepared in accordance with the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, National Guard Bureau (NGB) policy, Department of Defense (DOD) policy, specific guidance contained in All-States Memorandum P00-0039 of June 15, 2000, and other military regulations for natural resources management. In addition, this INRMP would ensure that natural resources conservation measures are integrated with ORARNG activities at the BTC and that they are consistent with federal stewardship requirements. The document addresses the interrelationships among the natural resources managed by the BLM at the BTC (including soils, wildlife, vegetative communities, and outdoor recreation) and the military mission. Without effective and proactive natural resources management, components of the military mission could be jeopardized.

This INRMP provides an adaptive management program to balance natural resources stewardship and military needs. It identifies a number of goals and objectives for specific natural resources at the BTC that the ORARNG and the BLM would implement, including controlling invasive species, maintaining and restoring vegetative communities, abating wildfire and dust, managing soils, identifying potentially occurring sensitive species, and minimizing conflict with livestock grazing practices. Specific management strategies are proposed to meet the specific goals and objectives. In recognition of its land and natural resources management responsibilities, the ORARNG has worked closely with the BLM and other natural resources management agencies, notably the US Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife (ODFW), to develop this INRMP. The INRMP has been prepared in cooperation with the BLM, but is considered an ORARNG document and is subordinate to the *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989) for central Oregon.

The INRMP contains baseline information to comply with regulatory and planning processes. To fulfill the requirements of the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) of 1969, PL 91-190 (42 USC §§ 4321 - 4370d), an environmental assessment (EA) has been prepared to assess possible impacts from implementing the INRMP. This EA has been integrated into this document; thus, this joint document is referred to as the INRMP/EA. Section 2.2 discusses the NEPA process in detail.

The federal public lands that compose the BTC are administered and managed by the BLM. Natural resources at the BTC are controlled by the BLM; however, the ORARNG has a natural resource management program to maintain and enhance on-site resources. The program works cooperatively with the BLM, but the BLM does not control the budget or priorities of the ORARNG, nor does the BLM implement any ORARNG-related natural resources management projects at the BTC.

In order to maintain continuity between the BLM and the ORARNG in the management and use of the natural resources of the BTC, the BLM's *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989) is the primary management plan. The ORARNG also is required to meet the regulations and guidelines issued by the DOD, Department of the Army (DA), and the NGB for managing its military training sites. Natural resources used by the DOD are to be managed in accordance with numerous laws, regulations, Executive Orders (EOs), and DOD instructions. These documents direct the Secretary of the Army to carry out a natural resources management program to balance sustainable military readiness while promoting sustainable environmental stewardship. In general, a natural resources management program for a military training site such as the BTC should support the following:

- Consistency with the use of military activities to ensure the preparedness of armed forces;
- No net loss in the capability of lands to support the military mission of ORARNG;

- Conservation and enhancement of natural resources managed by the BLM, where management actions support accomplishment of the military mission;
- Sustainable multiple use of natural resources, subject to resource availability, safety, and military security, including public access to the resources;
- Natural resources management, including protection, enhancement, and conservation of the natural resources;
- Implementation of land management practices that reduce grounds maintenance costs, use environmentally and economically beneficial landscaping practices, conserve soil and water, abate nonpoint pollution, and control noxious weeds;
- Identification of threatened or endangered species, emphasizing mission requirements and interagency cooperation during consultation, species recovery planning, and management activities, in coordination with the BLM;
- Optimum uses of the land and water areas and access thereto;
- Outleased lands that are suitable and available for agricultural uses, consistent with operational requirements and long-term ecosystem management goals; and
- Interaction with the surrounding community to develop positive and productive community involvement and economic opportunities.

All of the above-mentioned elements are to be implemented in cooperation and coordination with the BLM. The INRMP contains baseline information that supports compliance with regulatory and planning processes as well as the directives and guidelines of the BLM.

1.2 OREGON ARMY NATIONAL GUARD

The ORARNG has a unique dual mission that includes both federal and state roles. Although the ORARNG's primary mission is to serve as a federal reserve force in support of the active Army, it has an equally important role in support of the state (NGB 2000b). Until mobilized in support of a federal military mission, the ORARNG units are commanded by the Governor of Oregon. In this capacity, the ORARNG completes required training and is the first military responder within the state during emergencies.

The official mission of the BTC is to support the soldiers serving in the ORARNG by providing training facilities and maneuver areas for cavalry, engineer, anti-armor, and infantry training for troops through battalion-size elements. ORARNG training is focused on ensuring troop readiness across the force in order to mobilize quickly and effectively in times of national or international emergencies.

The ORARNG promotes the following goals as an integral part of its primary mission:

- Instill environmental stewardship in soldiers and employees of the Oregon Military Department (OMD)/ORARNG;
- Comply with all applicable regulatory requirements;
- Minimize environmental impacts of military training and agency operations; and
- Provide guidance to commanders, facility managers, supervisors, and individuals in meeting environmental requirements.

The OMD is the liaison between the Army and state of Oregon public agencies and develops and maintains effective and efficient agency regulations and guidance to incorporate strategies and to implement requirements for compliance, conservation, pollution prevention, restoration, and program management (OMD 2000).

1.3 LOCATION AND LAND USE

The BTC has been unofficially referenced under different names in the past. These names include, but are not limited to, the Central Oregon Training Site, High Desert Training Center, and the Redmond Training Site. For purposes of this document, the military training site is referred to as the Biak Training Center.

The BTC is in Deschutes and Crook counties in central Oregon (Figure 1-1). It consists of approximately 31,400 acres of federal public lands located approximately three miles southeast of the city of Redmond and fourteen miles northeast of the city of Bend. With the exception of three small parcels of military-controlled land (approximately 35 acres controlled by the ORARNG, 6.4 acres leased to the ORARNG by the city of Redmond, and 75 acres of federally withdrawn land controlled by the ORARNG), the BTC consists of lands administered and managed under the concept of multiple-use by the BLM. In that regard, the BLM has continually issued a special use permit to the ORARNG since the 1960s to allow for military training at the BTC. As a result, ORARNG actions must be closely coordinated with the BLM to ensure that federal mandates for managing the natural resources are met.

The primary military mission at the BTC is to provide training facilities and terrain for the soldiers of the ORARNG. All-terrain vehicles (both tracked and wheeled) are used to train cavalry, engineer, anti-armor, and infantry troops in a natural realistic setting. Most of the federal public lands remain open to and easily accessible for public use. The primary nonmilitary uses of the BTC include, but are not limited to, livestock grazing, off-road vehicular recreation, target shooting, rockhounding, hiking, biking, and wildlife viewing. None of these activities are controlled or managed by the ORARNG; the INRMP addresses only those natural resources potentially impacted by military training.

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Legend for Inset

- City
- ★ State Capitol

Legend

- North Unit Main Canal
- Roads
- Training Areas
- Off Limits to Military Training
- OMD - Controlled Property

**Biak Training Center
with Regional View**

Deschutes and Crook Counties, Oregon

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The BLM maintains administrative and managerial control over all of the natural resources located on or associated with the BTC. Wildlife resources might be jointly managed or completely managed by the USFWS or the ODFW. Currently, all natural resources on the federal public lands that compose the BTC are administered according to the requirements and guidelines outlined under a special use permit and the BLM's *Brothers/La Pine Resources Management Plan* (BLM 1989).

A special use permit is issued to the ORARNG by the BLM for military training at the BTC. Each special use permit covers a three-year period; the current special use permit was issued in 2001 and will be reviewed by the BLM for reissue in 2004. The current special use permit (2001 to 2004) includes all the training areas, including the public lands that compose Training Area F.

1.4 CURRENT MILITARY TRAINING

The military mission of the BTC is to provide the training facilities and maneuver area necessary for cavalry, engineer, anti-armor, and infantry training for troop- to battalion-sized units. The BTC is used by military personnel from the ORARNG, with visiting troops from other branches of the military allocated training opportunities as scheduling and special use permit stipulations allow.

Live fire exercises are prohibited at the BTC, except at the small-arms range located in ORARNG-operated, state-owned lands known as the Central Oregon Unit Training Equipment Site (COUTES). Most training exercises involve the use of all-terrain wheeled and tracked vehicles, driven in designated areas. Additionally, infantry training field exercises consisting of land navigation, bivouacking, and temporary construction of fortifications and defensive positions take place throughout the BTC. Currently, the military tracked and wheeled vehicles authorized by the BLM to use the BTC include the following:

- M1A1 Abrams tanks;
- M3A2 cavalry fighting vehicles;
- M113 armored personnel carriers;
- Armored vehicle-launched bridges (AVLB);
- M577 tracked command vehicles;
- M1025 scout vehicles; and
- M966 TOW vehicles.

The BTC is divided into six individual training areas (alphabetically designated A through F), with unique training activities allocated for each area (Figure 1-2). Training areas are the administrative management units used for planning, scheduling, and executing training activities (Jones 2000). Table 1-1 lists the restrictions in each given training area, as designated in the *Environmental Assessment: Fielding the Bradley Fighting Vehicle and Cavalry Fighting Vehicle and Other Proposed Federal Actions at the Central Oregon Training Site* (OMD 1995).

Table 1-1
Current Training Area Designations and Associated Environmental Restrictions

Current Training Area Designation (Figure 1-2)	Use (Figure 1-2)	Environmental Restrictions
A	Primary Use Area for Tracked Vehicles	Open to dismounted soldiers, wheeled and tracked vehicles off-road.
	Tracked Vehicles on Roads Only	Tracked vehicles restricted to designated roads only. Dismounted soldiers and wheeled vehicles permitted off-road.
	Infantry Troops Only	All vehicles restricted to designated roads only. Dismounted soldiers permitted only off-road.
	Infantry Troops Only	All vehicles restricted to designated roads only. Dismounted soldiers permitted only off-road.
B	Primary Use Area for Tracked Vehicles	Open to dismounted soldiers, wheeled and tracked vehicles off-road.
C	Infantry Troops Only	All vehicles restricted to designated roads only. Dismounted soldiers permitted only off-road.
D	Tracked Vehicles on Roads Only	Tracked vehicles restricted to designated roads only. Dismounted soldiers and wheeled vehicles permitted off-road.
	Infantry Troops Only	All vehicles restricted to designated roads only. Dismounted soldiers permitted only off-road.
E	Infantry Troops Only	All vehicles restricted to designated roads only. Dismounted soldiers permitted only off-road.
F	Primary Use Area for Tracked Vehicles	Open to dismounted soldiers, wheeled and tracked vehicles off-road.
Off Limits	Off Limits	Off limits to all training activities.
North Unit Main Canal	Off Limits	The North Unit Main Canal channel is off limits. The North Unit Main Canal service roads on top of the east and west banks are restricted to range control use only with HMMWV vehicles or lighter. Canal crossings are allowed only at the Bailey Bridge or designated AVLB sites.

Sources: OMD 1995; McCaffrey 2001
 * High-mobility multiwheeled vehicle

Only fire, ambulance, range control, or other emergency vehicles are exempted from the restrictions that apply to the training areas, as outlined in Table 1-1. Military training exercises are prohibited within the North Unit Main Canal, private property areas, and identified cultural/historic resource areas.

Training usage is defined as "soldier days" (the number of soldiers that train at the BTC multiplied by the actual number of training days). Military personnel using the BTC for training are not housed at the facility (except those that are permitted to bivouac during actual field exercises). The BTC is allowed to conduct training exercises two to three weekends per month, 24 hours a day. Additionally, a two-week annual training event could be conducted at the facility. Military training exercises are typically not conducted at the BTC during the week nor on at least one weekend a month. Table 1-2 illustrates the historical training usage by year and soldier days.

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Legend

- Dirt or Gravel Road
- Paved Road
- Powerlines
- North Unit Main Canal

- Off Limits to Military Training
- Training Areas
- OMD - Controlled Property
- Primary Use Area for Tracked Vehicles
- Infantry Troops Only
- Tracked Vehicles on Roads Only

Functional Training Areas

Blak Training Center
Deschutes and Crook Counties, Oregon

Figure 1-2

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**Table 1-2
Biak Training Center Training Usage**

Training Year	Soldier Days
1996	4,937
1997	9,692
1998	9,974
1999	22,189*
2000	5,630
2001	6,000 (projected)

Sources: ORARNG 2000b; McCaffrey 2001

*The soldier days for training year 1999 were higher than normal due to a large, two-week training event.

1.4.1 Potential Future Training Activities

The ORARNG does not anticipate major modifications to the military mission or the training schedule/patterns of the BTC in the immediate future. However, some potential modifications to the current military mission and training patterns might be necessary to minimize conflict among user groups, to maintain adequate public access to public lands, and to maintain public health and safety. To this end, the ORARNG could, in the future, coordinate with the BLM to determine the possibility of modifying the following elements:

- Construction of a permanent vehicle wash rack and cover in order to reduce the potential for invasive species propagation and to provide for dust abatement.
- Determination of the feasibility of transferring military training from Training Area A to BLM land at an as yet undetermined location north of Highway 126 or another acceptable location. As stipulated in the BLM's *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan*, some of the acreage used by the military in Training Area A has been identified as public lands that might be transferred to or exchanged with local governments as needed to accommodate community expansion or other purposes.
- Lifting restrictions for training with military vehicles in Training Area D, as deemed appropriate by the BLM.

The expected training frequency and scheduled training events for the BTC would likely remain somewhat constant in the foreseeable future (McCaffrey 2001). None of the proposed training changes would be implemented without prior consultation with and approval by the BLM. Analysis of potential environmental impacts, if determined necessary, also would be conducted prior to the implementation of proposed major changes to the training frequency and schedule.

1.5 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE MILITARY MISSION AND NATURAL RESOURCES

The Army recognizes that a healthy and viable natural resources base is required to support the military mission (US Army 1992). To be effective, the natural conditions of the military training area at the BTC must be maintained to provide realism. Refer to

Section 2 and Appendix D for a description of the pertinent DOD, DA, NGB, and ORARNG regulations that help guide the implementation of an INRMP.

The BTC was created to assist with domestic and international security, as well as with national and state emergencies and to do so in a safe environment; consequently, specific natural resources management actions must be compatible with the military mission and must not jeopardize training schedules or public health and safety. Examples of compatible programs include allowing livestock to graze on the open range, minimizing the potential for invasive weeds to become established, minimizing impacts directly attributable to military training, and minimizing fire risk.

Ongoing military training executed in support of the military mission at the BTC might alter the environmental setting and condition of the natural resources. Pit and foxhole excavating, road grading, and cross-country (or off-road) maneuvering with tracked and wheeled vehicles could result in the disturbance, compaction, and loss of soil resources, along with the associated loss in vegetation. While short-term changes in the environmental setting could still provide for relatively realistic training opportunities, the absence of long-term management measures to properly conserve and rehabilitate natural resources could impede the BTC's ability to continue to adequately train soldiers. In addition to the impacts noted above, environmental damage can place constraints on military training and realism through the following:

- Loss of training acreage;
- Decreased tactical maneuverability;
- Increased land and natural resources maintenance costs; and,
- Increased safety hazards to military personnel.

BTC range control officers and all military personnel using the BTC for training must adhere to the safety policies and procedures outlined in the draft *Safety, Fire, and Emergency Services Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures* document (Annex) (BTC 1999), as well as to pertinent ORARNG regulations. The Annex provides vital information for all troops and commanders in the event of fire, medical, or hazardous materials incidents while they are training at the BTC. The Annex provides incident-specific guidance on how to contact the proper military and supporting civil agencies whose assistance is required to safely effect rescue and medical evacuation, fire suppression, hazardous material spill containment, and law enforcement assistance. A major component of the Annex is focused on risk management, emphasizing that military personnel shall "train as you fight, train to standard, but always provide safety first" (BTC 1999).

While the military mission is paramount, natural resources management can constrain the mission when regulatory issues are identified. For example, activities at the BTC may not kill, harm, or harass species protected under the Endangered Species Act (ESA). If such an action were proposed, the ORARNG would have to enter into

formal consultation with the USFWS and obtain approval from the USFWS prior to implementing the action. Similarly, wetlands and cultural resources are protected by federal law, which could affect the future expansion and use of certain areas within the boundaries of the BTC. Therefore, the INRMP identifies such land use and operational constraints so that they can be considered and planned for in the future.

1.6 PURPOSE OF THE INRMP

The purpose of the INRMP is to guide the ORARNG in cooperatively managing, with the BLM, the natural resources on the federal public lands that compose the BTC from fiscal years 2002 through 2006. The INRMP also provides a solid foundation on which to build the program beyond 2006. It is designed to be a programmatic document that would help the BTC ensure the sustainability of the military mission, while maintaining the integrity of the ecological process and its ecosystems. In addition, the INRMP would ensure that effective natural resources management, BLM public land management guidelines, and ORARNG military training requirements are integrated and are consistent with the BLM's *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989), as well as other federal and military stewardship requirements.

1.7 NEED FOR THE INRMP

The INRMP for the federal public lands that comprise the BTC is an ORARNG document that is required by the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997. NGB policy is to prepare an INRMP and integrated EA for all federally supported military training sites used by the Army National Guard. The need for this INRMP is fourfold, as follows:

- An INRMP must be prepared in accordance with the provisions of the Natural Resources Management on Military Lands Act of 1960 (commonly known as the Sikes Act) and the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, and is required by NGB policy, DOD Policy, and guidance contained in All-States Memorandum P00-0039 of June 15, 2000.
- An INRMP is needed to support the military mission and to sustain the integrity of natural resources, per the BLM's *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989). An essential element of the military mission is to train military personnel as they would be expected to perform under actual combat or emergency conditions. The military mission requires healthy and viable natural resources to provide realistic environmental conditions and to minimize the potential for hazardous situations.
- An INRMP is needed to document previously completed and current natural resources surveys, inventories, and monitoring programs for the federal public lands that compose the BTC. These studies are discussed in Section 4 and include an inventory and evaluation of vertebrate fauna (Reiher et al. 2000), a floristic survey (Sundberg 2000), vegetation monitoring protocols (Jones 2000; Rudd 2000), soil surveys (Myhrum et al. 1999), and archaeological investigations. The vegetation monitoring protocols have led to subsequent field studies that have produced two

years of baseline data on vegetation and disturbance; the INRMP is needed to integrate these existing studies.

- An INRMP is needed to implement an adaptive ecosystem management framework as part of the NGB's policies on natural resources management. This approach takes a long-term view of human activities, including military training needs, human uses, and biological resources as part of the same environment.

1.8 RESPONSIBLE AND INTERESTED PARTIES

Successful natural resources management for the federal public lands that compose the BTC and the implementation of this INRMP require a cooperative effort among the parties directly responsible for using and maintaining the military training site. A brief description of the parties directly responsible for implementing the INRMP and of other interested parties is provided below.

1.8.1 Bureau of Land Management

The land and natural resources that encompass the federal public lands of the BTC are under the direct management of the BLM's Prineville Office. Because the BLM has primary responsibility for the land on which the BTC is located, it is required to manage the land under the concept of "multiple-use," per the Federal Land Policy and Management Act (FLMPA) of 1976, PL 94-579, as amended (43 USC §§ 1701 - 1785). In that regard, the BLM has continually issued a special use permit to the ORARNG since the 1960s to allow for military training at the BTC. As a result, ORARNG actions must be closely coordinated with the BLM to ensure that federal mandates for managing natural resources are met.

The BLM's role for this INRMP is as a public agency reviewer for NEPA content and process rather than as a decision-maker. The BLM has reviewed the draft document at various stages of its development to determine concurrence for the final INRMP. This concurrence is in the form of a signed letter of approval. The USFWS and ODFW are cooperating agencies and have also reviewed the draft document at various stages of its development and have provided letters of concurrence. These letters of concurrence are provided in Appendix C.

1.8.2 ORARNG

The BTC is home to the 1st Squadron, 82nd Cavalry of the ORARNG. Military training site personnel involved with the environmental management of the BTC consist of a Squadron Commander, Training Center Manager, Range Operations Officer, and supporting range operations staff. Military personnel at the BTC that assist the ORARNG in implementing the INRMP are listed below.

Squadron Commander, BTC. The Squadron Commander is responsible for managing and operating the military training site and all associated property. The health and safety of all military personnel training at the BTC is a primary concern, so the Squadron Commander must ensure that the natural resources management program

supports the military mission and does not pose risks to military personnel or the public.

Training Center Manager, BTC. The Training Center Manager is primarily responsible for scheduling, planning, and managing military personnel using the BTC for military training.

Range Operations Officer, BTC. The BTC Range Operations Officer is the primary point of contact and liaison between the BTC and the BLM for issues concerning natural resources. The Range Operations Officer is responsible for maintaining the range in a condition appropriate for military use, reducing negative impacts to the natural resources by restoring degraded sites (in consultation with the BLM), and ensuring the health and safety of training military personnel through adherence to ORARNG, NGB, Army, and DOD regulations and guidance.

1.8.3 Other Federal Agencies

A number of federal agencies other than DOD and the NGB have an interest in the integrity of the natural resources at the BTC. The involvement of these agencies is based on cooperative agreements, regulatory authority, or their designation as cooperating agencies or providers of technical assistance, as required by federal legislation and regulation. These agencies and their roles and responsibilities are described below.

US Department of the Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service. The USFWS is a designated cooperating agency in the development of this INRMP. It is the primary federal agency for issues regarding fish and wildlife management and is the regulatory authority for the Endangered Species Act of 1973, PL 93-205 (codified at 16 USC §§ 1531 - 1534) and the Migratory Bird Treaty Act of 1918, 40 Stat. 755 (codified as amended at 16 USC §§ 703-711). The USFWS has cooperated with the BTC and ORARNG in providing technical assistance on potentially occurring sensitive species and wildlife habitat management issues. A letter of concurrence from the USFWS is reproduced in Appendix C.

US Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS). The NRCS is the primary federal agency with which the BTC cooperates for soils management, including erosion control measures and soils surveys. The NRCS authored the *Soil Survey of Central Oregon Training Site, Oregon* (Myhrum et al. 1999) for the BTC.

1.8.4 Tribal Governments

The Klamath Tribes, Burns Paiute Tribes, the Confederated Tribes of Warm Springs, and the Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation have potential interests in the central Oregon lands and natural and cultural resources, of which the BTC is a part. Tribal councils for those groups have been offered the opportunity to have their representatives participate in the coordinated planning effort on which this INRMP is based. On September 25, 2000, the ORARNG sent letters to tribal governments,

notifying them of the ORARNG's intent to initiate the INRMP process. A copy of this letter is included in Appendix B. Tribal representatives were invited to attend an interagency coordination meeting on October 31, 2000, hosted by the ORARNG at USFWS's Oregon Field Office in Bend, Oregon. The Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation were inadvertently omitted from the September mailing and October meeting. However, they and the other three tribes listed above were invited to a site visit to the BTC (also hosted by the ORARNG) on February 18, 2001. All four tribal governments received a copy of the May 2001 preliminary draft INRMP/EA for review and comment, were notified of the availability of the August 2001 draft INRMP/EA, and will receive a copy of the final INRMP/EA on request. The ORARNG makes internal determinations as to whether a particular federal decision may have the potential to significantly affect protected tribal resources, tribal rights, or Indian Land. If it appears that there may be an effect, the appropriate Native American tribes would be contacted.

1.8.5 State Agencies

The ODFW is the primary state agency responsible for managing fish and wildlife. Cooperation between the ORARNG, BLM and ODFW generally involves compliance issues concerning the ESA, the Migratory Bird Treaty Act, and other federal and state laws and regulations. The ODFW is a designated cooperative agency for the development of this INRMP. A letter of concurrence from the ODFW is reproduced in Appendix C.

1.8.6 Other Interested Parties

A number of other interested organizations and stakeholders to the INRMP have been identified, including the following:

- *Livestock Grazing Permittees.* The BLM has delineated 9 grazing allotments (comprised of 15 pastures) that fall partially or fully within the BTC. Grazing activities, including grazing seasons and allowable animal unit months (the amount of dry forage a cow and calf eat in one month), are regulated by the BLM. The ORARNG consults with the livestock grazing permittees in late winter each year to minimize potential conflict between these land uses during the coming year.
- *Oregon Natural Heritage Program (ONHP).* The mission of the ONHP is to acquire, maintain, and distribute information on the organisms and ecosystems that constitute Oregon's natural heritage and to ensure, through a public planning process and through voluntary public and private efforts, that the full range of Oregon's natural heritage resources is represented within a statewide system of recognized natural areas. It is affiliated with the Oregon State University, which provides administrative support. The ORARNG has contracted with the ONHP to perform ecological monitoring for the BTC. ONHP and The Nature Conservancy reports include *Central Oregon Training Site 1999 Vegetation*

Monitoring Final Report (Kagan 1999) and *1999 Data Summary for Vegetation Monitoring at the Central Oregon Training Site* (Rudd 1999).

- *Center for Ecological Management of Military Lands (CEMML)*. ORARNG contracted with the CEMML to assist in developing and implementing a biological monitoring effort at the BTC. The Land Condition-Trend Analysis (LCTA) program is a vegetation monitoring protocol to collect data and analyze land use impacts using a series of sampling plots, photographs, and other site-specific information. The *Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site* (Jones 2000) is a CEMML publication prepared for the ORARNG.
- *The Nature Conservancy*. ORARNG contracted with the Nature Conservancy to conduct vegetation monitoring at the Central Oregon Training Site. The *1999 Data Summary for Vegetation Monitoring at the Central Oregon Training Site, Oregon Army National Guard* (Rudd 2000) is a Nature Conservancy publication prepared for the ORARNG.

1.9 PUBLIC INVOLVEMENT AND AGENCY COORDINATION

This document has been prepared with input from and coordination with interested agencies, organizations, and individuals within the region. The BLM, USFWS, and the ODFW are cooperating agencies in the preparation of this INRMP; the ORARNG consulted with these and other public agencies. As summarized in Appendix B, on September 25, 2000, the ORARNG sent letters to the cooperating agencies and to other interested agencies, organizations, Native American tribes, and individuals, notifying them that the BTC was beginning its INRMP process. Copies of the September 25, 2000 letters are included in Appendix B. The mailing provided background information and solicited comments from interested parties. Five comments were received (four by letter and one via a telephone message). One comment was from a private individual, one was from the Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project, one was from the Deschutes County Bicycle and Pedestrian Advisory Committee, and two comments were from public agencies: the Oregon Department of Water Resources and the City of Redmond. Copies of these comments are provided in Appendix B.

The ORARNG hosted an interagency coordination meeting on October 31, 2000, in the USFWS's Bend, Oregon, field office. The USFWS and BLM attended to assist the ORARNG and BTC in developing the INRMP. Representatives from three tribal nations and other federal and state agencies were invited to attend. The Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation were inadvertently omitted from the October meeting. However, representatives from all four tribes were invited to a site visit to the BTC (hosted by the ORARNG) on February 18, 2001. Copies of the May 2001 preliminary draft of the INRMP were mailed to four Native American tribes. Copies of the public draft were mailed to pertinent public agencies and were mailed to any public members requesting copies, for review and comment, as noted in Section B.3 of Appendix B.

The ORARNG provided the public with an opportunity to review and comment on the draft INRMP/EA during a 30-day period. Notices of availability for the draft INRMP/EA were printed in local newspapers, and copies were available at local libraries in Bend, Redmond, and Prineville, Oregon, and by request. In total, two government agencies, one organization, and one individual commented in writing on the draft INRMP. These letters are reproduced in Appendix B. Appendix B also summarized how the comments are addressed. This INRMP/EA contains revisions that were made, as necessary, after the review process was complete.

SECTION 2

SIKES ACT AND NEPA COMPLIANCE

Army facilities, including Army National Guard installations, are subject to numerous regulations affecting use and management of natural resources, including federal laws, EOs, and Army regulations. Table 2-1 lists of applicable laws, regulations, and policies, and Appendix D discusses the most important of these.

2.1 SIKES ACT, PL 86-797 (16 USC §§ 670 - 670F)

Under the Natural Resources Management Act of 1960, commonly known as the Sikes Act, PL 86-797, as amended by the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, PL 105-85 (codified at 16 USC § 670 - 670f [1999]), the Secretary of Defense shall carry out a program for conserving and rehabilitating natural resources on military installations. The INRMP is an ORARNG document required by NGB policy and based on the requirements outlined in the Sikes Act. As previously stated, it is NGB policy to prepare an INRMP and EA for all federally supported military training sites used by the Army National Guard. This INRMP has been developed, however, to comply with the intent of the Sikes Act. To this end, the ORARNG shall provide for the following:

- Conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources affected by the military on the military training site;
- Sustainable multipurpose use of the natural resources used by the military in support of the military mission, subject to public and military personnel safety requirements; and
- Public access to the military training site to use natural resources.

The Sikes Act provides a mechanism whereby the DOD, the Department of Interior, and the states can cooperate to manage fish and wildlife on military installations. The ORARNG has coordinated its actions with these agencies and entities in regard to wildlife resources and military training and will continue to do so.

Table 2-1
Natural Resource Laws and Regulations and their Expected Influence on
Natural Resources Management at the BTC

Law or Regulation	Influence		
	Direct	Indirect	Not Applicable
Abandoned Shipwreck Act of 1987, PL 100-298 (43 USC §§ 2101 - 2106)			✓
American Indian Religious Freedom Act of 1978, PL 95-341, as amended (42 USC §§ 1996 - 1996a)	✓		
Anadromous Fish Conservation Act of 1965, as amended (16 USC §§ 757a - 757f)			✓
Antiquities Act of 1906, PL 59-209 (16 USC §§ 431 - 433)		✓	
Archaeological and Historic Resources Management (Department of Defense Directive 4710-1)	✓		
Archaeological and Historic Preservation Act (Moss-Bennett Act) of 1974, PL 86-532 (16 USC §§ 469 - 469c)	✓		
Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979, PL 96-95 (16 USC §§ 470aa - 470mm)	✓		
Bald Eagle Protection Act of 1940, 54 Stat. 251, as amended (16 USC §§ 668 - 668d)		✓	
Clean Air Act of 1955, 69 Stat. 322, as amended (42 USC §§ 7401 - 7671q)	✓		
Clean Water Act (Federal Water Pollution Control Act) of 1972, PL 92-500, as amended (33 USC §§ 1251 - 1387)	✓		
Coastal Zone Management Act of 1972, PL 92-583 (16 USC §§ 1451 - 1465)			✓
Curation of Federally Owned and Administered Archaeological Collections (36 CFR § 79)		✓	
Department of Defense Annotated American Indian and Alaska Native Policy (October 27, 1999)	✓		
Determination of Eligibility for Inclusion in the National Register of Historic Places (36 CFR § 63)		✓	
Emergency Wetlands Resources Act of 1986, PL 99-645, as amended (16 USC §§ 3901 - 3932)			✓
Endangered Species Act of 1973, PL 93-205, (16 USC §§ 1531 - 1534)	✓		
Environmental Protection and Enhancement: Subpart H Historic Preservation (32 CFR § 650)		✓	
Erosion Protection Act, PL 86-645, as amended (33 USC §§ 426 - 426-3)	✓		
Estuary Protection Act of 1968, PL 90-454 (16 USC §§ 1221 - 1226)			✓
Executive Order 13007, Indian Sacred Sites (61 Federal Register 26,771, May 29, 1996)	✓		
Executive Order 11593, Protection and Enhancement of the Cultural Environment, May 13, 1971 (36 Federal Register 8921)		✓	

Table 2-1
 Natural Resource Laws and Regulations and their Expected Influence on
 Natural Resources Management at the BTC (*continued*)

Law or Regulation	Influence		
	Direct	Indirect	Not Applicable
Executive Order 11514, Protection and Enhancement of Environmental Quality, March 7, 1970 (35 Federal Register 4247), as amended by EO 11541 and EO 11991		✓	
Executive Order 11990, Protection of Wetlands, May 24, 1977 (42 Federal Register 26961)	✓		
Executive Order 12962, Recreational Fisheries, June 7, 1995 (60 Federal Register 30769)			✓
Executive Order 12114, Environmental Effects Abroad of Major Federal Actions, January 4, 1979 (44 Federal Register 1957)			✓
Executive Order 13175, Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments, November 6, 2000 (65 Federal Register 67249)	✓		
Executive Order 11988, Floodplain Management, as amended by 12148, May 24, 1977 (42 Federal Register 26951)		✓	
Executive Order 11644, Use of Off-road Vehicles on Public Lands, February 8, 1972 (37 Federal Register 2877), as amended by Executive Order 12608	✓		
Executive Order 13112, Invasive Species, February 3, 1999 (64 Federal Register 6183)	✓		
Executive Order 13186, Responsibilities of Federal Agencies to Protect Migratory Birds, January 10, 2001 (66 Federal Register 3853)	✓		
Farmland Protection Policy Act of 1981, PL 97-98, as amended (7 USC §§ 4201 - 4209)			✓
Federal Cave Resources Protection Act of 1988, PL 100-691, as amended (16 USC §§ 4301 - 4310)	✓		
Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act, PL 92-516, as amended (7 USC §§ 136 - 136y)	✓		
Federal Land Policy and Management Act of 1976, PL 94-579, as amended (43 USC §§ 1701 - 1785)	✓		
Federal Noxious Weed Act of 1974, PL 93-629, as amended (7 USC §§ 2801 - 2814)	✓		
Fish and Wildlife Conservation Act of 1980, PL 96-366 (16 USC §§ 2901 - 2912)		✓	
Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act of 1934, PL 85-624, as amended (16 USC §§ 661 - 666c)		✓	
Food, Agricultural, Conservation, and Trade Act of 1990 (Pesticide Recordkeeping), PL 101-624, as amended (7 USC § 136i-1)	✓		
Forest Rangeland Renewable Resource Planning Act of 1974, PL 93-378 (16 USC §§ 1600 - 1614)		✓	
Historic Preservation Certificates (36 CFR § 67)		✓	

Table 2-1
Natural Resource Laws and Regulations and their Expected Influence on
Natural Resources Management at the BTC (continued)

Law or Regulation	Influence		
	Direct	Indirect	Not Applicable
Historic Sites Act of 1935, as amended by PL 74-292, PL 100-17 (16 USC §§ 461 - 467)		✓	
Historic Preservation (Army Regulation 200-4)	✓		
Hunting and Fishing Permits (32 CFR § 552.19)			✓
Lacey Act of 1900, 31 Stat. 187, as amended (16 USC §§ 667e, 701)			✓
Marine Mammal Protection Act of 1972, PL 92-522 (16 USC §§ 1361 - 1421h)			✓
Migratory Bird Treaty Act of 1918, 40 Stat. 755, as amended (16 USC §§ 703 - 712)		✓	
Multiple-Use Sustained Yield Act of 1960, PL 86-517 (16 USC §§ 528 - 531)	✓		
National Environmental Policy Act of 1969, PL 91-190 (42 USC §§ 4321 - 4370d)	✓		
National Historic Landmarks Program (36 CFR § 65)		✓	
National Historic Preservation Act of 1966, PL 89-665, as amended (16 USC §§ 470 - 470x-6)	✓		
National Register of Historic Places (36 CFR § 60)		✓	
Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act of 1990, PL 101-601 (25 USC §§ 3001 - 3013)		✓	
Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act Regulations (43 CFR § 10)		✓	
North American Wetlands Conservation Act, PL 101-233 (16 USC §§ 4401 - 4414)			✓
Outleasing for Grazing and Agriculture on Military Lands (10 USC § 2667)			✓
Preservation of American Antiquities (Antiquities Act regulations) (43 CFR § 3)		✓	
Protection of Archaeological Resources: Department of Defense Uniform Regulations (32 CFR § 229)	✓		
Protection of Historic and Cultural Properties (36 CFR § 800)	✓		
Rivers and Harbors Appropriations Act of 1899, 30 Stat. 1151, as amended (33 USC §§ 401 - 403)			✓
Safe Drinking Water Act of 1974, PL 93-523, as amended (42 USC §§ 300f-300j-26)		✓	
Salmon and Steelhead Conservation and Enhancement Act of 1980, PL 96-561 (16 USC §§ 3301-3345)		✓	
The Secretary of Interior's Standards for Historic Preservation Projects (36 CFR § 68)		✓	
Sikes Act and Sikes Act Improvement Amendments, PL 86-797, as amended (16 USC §§ 670 - 670f)	✓		

Table 2-1
Natural Resource Laws and Regulations and their Expected Influence on
Natural Resources Management at the BTC (continued)

Law or Regulation	Influence		
	Direct	Indirect	Not Applicable
Soil and Water Resources Conservation Act of 1977, PL 95-192, as amended (16 USC §§ 2001 - 2009)		✓	
Taylor Grazing Act of 1934, PL 73-482 (43 USC §§ 315 - 315o-2)	✓		
Timber Sales on Military Lands (10 USC § 2665)			✓
Waiver of Federal Agency Responsibility under Section 110 of the National Historic Preservation Act (36 CFR § 78)			✓
Water Resources Planning Act, PL 89-80, as amended (42 USC §§ 1962 - 1962d-20)		✓	
Watershed Protection and Flood Prevention Act, PL 92-419 (16 USC §§ 1001 - 1011, 33 USC 701)		✓	
Wild and Scenic Rivers Act of 1968, PL 90-542, as amended (16 USC §§ 1271 - 1287)			✓

Source: Modified from US Army 1997.

2.2 NATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY ACT OF 1969, PL 91-190 (42 USC §§ 4321 - 4370D)

Under NEPA, federal agencies must take into consideration the environmental consequences of proposed major actions. The spirit and intent of NEPA is to protect and enhance the environment through well-informed federal decisions based on sound science. NEPA is premised on the assumption that providing timely information to the decision-maker and the public concerning the potential environmental consequences of proposed actions will improve the quality of federal decisions. Thus, the NEPA process includes the systematic interdisciplinary evaluation of potential environmental consequences expected to result from implementing a proposed action. This document is a joint INRMP/EA and fulfills NEPA requirements.

2.2.1 NEPA/INRMP Integration

Until recently, the Army and other DOD agencies have prepared NEPA analysis and documentation for proposed actions, such as implementing management plans like INRMPs, after such plans have been developed. This approach might comply with the basic tenet of the law, but it often results in inefficient repetition and redundancy, creating multiple documents on similar subjects. This report integrates the requirements of the Sikes Act and NEPA. Table 2-2 lists the required NEPA components, and it references where they are addressed in this report.

Table 2-2
Comparison of NEPA Requirements to INRMP/E A Sections

Required NEPA Analysis	Corresponding INRMP Section
The Executive Summary briefly describes the proposed action, alternatives, environmental consequences, and mitigation measures.	Executive Summary
The Purpose of and Need for the Proposed Action summarizes the proposed action's purpose and need.	Section 1.6—Purpose of the INRMP and, Section 1.7— Need for the INRMP
The Proposed Action summarizes the activity the project proponent would like to implement.	Section 2.2.2— Description of the Proposed Action
The Scope of Analysis describes the extent of the environmental impact analysis process.	Section 2.2.4— Scope of Analysis
The Alternatives describe different means to meet the purpose and need.	Section 2.2.3— Alternatives
The Affected Environment describes the existing environmental setting.	Section 3.0— Existing Environmental Conditions
Environmental Consequences identifies potential environmental effects of implementing any of the alternatives.	Section 7.0— Environmental Consequences
References provide bibliographical information for cited sources.	Section 8.0— References
List of Preparers identifies the persons who prepared the document, as well as their qualifications.	Section 9.0— List of Preparers
Distribution List indicates recipients of the NEPA document.	Appendix B— Distribution List
The Appendices include legal land descriptions, agency consultation letters, public comment letters, federal requirements and other guidelines, and supplemental information used to develop the NEPA analysis.	Appendices A, B, C, D, and E

Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) regulations encourage NEPA and NEPA-related documents to be combined to reduce paperwork and duplication (40 CFR § 1500.4), so that federal agencies can concentrate on the spirit and intent of the law—that of making better informed management decisions (40 CFR § 1506.4). This regulation is supported by the DOD, the DA, and the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA).

2.2.2 Description of the Proposed Action

The proposed action is to develop and implement an INRMP consistent with the military use of the BTC and the goals and objectives established in the Sikes Act (as amended). The goal of the INRMP is to implement an ecosystem-based conservation program that provides for conservation and enhancement of natural resources in a manner that is consistent with the military mission, that integrates and coordinates all natural resources management activities, and that provides for sustainable multipurpose uses of natural resources and for public access for use of natural resources. The management objectives are to integrate management plans as practicable and consistent with the military mission and established land uses.

Implementing the proposed action would comply with federal regulations and military requirements that mandate protection of natural resources managed by the Army. The proposed action focuses on a five-year planning period, which is consistent with the time frame mandated by the Sikes Act and DOD instruction.

2.2.3 Alternatives

In order to capture the full range of possible impacts that could result from implementing the INRMP, two alternative means of implementing a natural resource program at the BTC for the next five years have been identified. These alternatives consist of implementing the full INRMP, as proposed in this document, or implementing only those activities required to comply with existing laws, regulations, and BLM permit conditions. The latter approach is in place at the BTC, in accordance with the BLM's *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* of 1989; hence, it serves as the No Action Alternative.

The preferred alternative is to implement an ecosystem approach to meet multiple objectives, as outlined in Section 5. Land management activities that would be implemented for each alternative have been placed into 14 management categories. Section 7 provides a detailed overview of the specific management activities, along with an assessment of potential impacts resulting from their implementation.

Alternative 1: Implement Ecosystem-based INRMP. Under this alternative, the BTC would implement the INRMP approach outlined in Section 5, focusing on sustaining military readiness, promoting environmental stewardship, and conserving biodiversity. Under this alternative, all management issues that are important to the realization of the military mission, legal compliance, and ecological health are given a high priority; therefore, all management categories are emphasized. An adaptive management strategy would be instituted to conduct additional research, to monitor management actions, to reassess the function of management tools, and to revise the management plan accordingly.

No Action Alternative. The No Action Alternative is the continued implementation of the objectives and strategies under the existing natural resources management program. Ongoing strategies used for managing natural resources at the BTC would continue, and there would be no change to the objectives of the current natural resources management plan. Currently the ORARNG adheres to the regulations and guidance promoted by the BLM in assisting in the management of natural resources at the BTC (BLM 1989). The current program focuses on compliance actions as a top priority but also includes implementation of some stewardship actions pursuant to funding and staffing. This alternative broadly supports all natural resources and generally does not emphasize specific management areas. Inclusion of a No Action Alternative is prescribed by CEQ regulations and serves as a benchmark against which proposed federal actions are evaluated.

Alternatives Considered but Eliminated. The ORARNG worked with the ODFW, USFWS, and BLM to identify conservation projects to sustain military readiness,

promote environmental stewardship, and conserve biodiversity. Many different concepts and approaches were discussed and considered. These alternatives were eventually dismissed because they would not provide sufficient and/or cost effective protection to natural and cultural resources. In other cases, alternatives were dropped because they eliminated training opportunities or compromised the military mission, were inconsistent with state or federal laws and regulations, or had excessive environmental impacts. Preparation and full implementation of the INRMP is an Army requirement. As such, other alternatives, including partial implementation of the INRMP, were considered but were dismissed as infeasible, impracticable, or precluded by legal insufficiency.

2.2.4 Scope of Analysis

The potential environmental impacts associated with the proposed action are required to be assessed in compliance with NEPA and CEQ regulations. This document identifies, documents, and evaluates the effects of implementing the INRMP at the BTC. The scope of the INRMP would guide the facility in achieving the following elements:

- Meeting the training requirements and objectives of the military mission at the BTC;
- Guiding the natural resources management program at the BTC in accordance with BLM regulations and the special use permit; and
- Meeting legal and policy requirements, including those associated with NEPA, that are consistent with currently accepted natural resources management philosophies.

In order to meet this objective, an interdisciplinary team of environmental scientists, biologists, geographers, engineers, archaeologists, historians, planners, and military technicians gathered to develop the INRMP/EA. The team identified the affected environment, analyzed the proposed action against existing conditions, and determined the potential beneficial and adverse effects associated with the proposal.

SECTION 3

EXISTING ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

3.1 BTC LAND USE

Land use at the BTC is segregated into developed and undeveloped areas. Developed areas consist of the 35-acre, state-owned parcel controlled by the ORARNG, approximately 6.4 acres leased to the ORARNG by the city of Redmond, and the 75-acre federal public parcel withdrawn from public domain for restricted use by the ORARNG. These developed areas are used primarily for operations, administration, and range control and are detailed below. Undeveloped areas make up the overwhelming majority of land at the BTC and are used primarily for livestock grazing, military training exercises, outdoor recreation, and natural resources management.

Undeveloped Areas

Military Training

The gently rolling terrain and relatively open vegetative cover provide excellent conditions for a variety of military training exercises at the BTC, from tracked and wheeled vehicle use both on-road and off-road, to light infantry maneuvers on foot (Table 1-1 and Figure 1-2). Most training at the BTC is conducted at the company level, with a typical training exercise consisting of approximately 150 to 300 soldiers training during a three-day weekend, three weekends a month (OMD 1995). Outside of the small-arms firing range, no live fire training is conducted on the military training site.

Unit commanders of visiting units will perform an environmental risk assessment in accordance with the BTC range control procedures before military training exercises. Unit commanders are responsible for excessive damage caused during maneuvers, illegal dumping of trash, damage to sensitive natural or cultural resources, and damage to private property. Unit commanders may be required to repair and rehabilitate maneuver damage caused during training exercises (ORARNG 2000a). Per special use permit stipulations, the BTC is required to reseed training areas negatively affected by military training exercises upon consultation with the BLM. Native seed from sources

approved by the BLM are spread for propagation at adequate rates when and if such rehabilitation efforts are deemed necessary.

Livestock Grazing

All of the undeveloped public lands at the BTC have been parceled into individual livestock grazing pastures by the BLM (Figure 3-1). The BTC has no management or oversight responsibilities for the livestock grazing pastures or the permittees, as the program is managed and regulated by the BLM Prineville District.

The BTC maintains open communication with livestock grazing permittees by hosting an annual meeting between the ORARNG and permittees. During this informal meeting, range control officers from the BTC discuss the upcoming military training schedule in order to reduce potential conflicts among user groups on public lands. Livestock grazing permittees inform the BTC of their grazing season dates and approximate AUMs for the upcoming season (McCaffrey 2000).

Outdoor Recreation

Dispersed outdoor recreational uses of the BTC are promoted and managed by the BLM Prineville District Office. (Dispersed activities are those in which people are spread out over a larger area, such as hiking, while concentrated activities are those in which people assemble at a specific location.) Common dispersed outdoor recreational pursuits by the public include, but are not limited to, off-road vehicle use, trap shooting, rockhounding, wildlife viewing, hunting, mountain biking, hiking/walking, and jogging. The BTC is accessible to the public for outdoor recreation at all times, even during military training exercises.

There are no improved recreational facilities or concentrated recreational activities at the BTC.

Developed Areas

Central Oregon Unit Training and Equipment Site

The COUTES is composed of approximately 35-acres of state-owned, ORARNG-operated property. The COUTES supports the equipment needs of the BTC and includes an administration building, a vehicle maintenance shop, a warehouse, a controlled humidity preservation storage facility, and a motorpool lot for storing and maintaining tracked and wheeled military vehicles. Training grounds on the COUTES consist of a 25/50-meter, fully baffled, small-arms firing range. The range includes earthen and hardened berms that prevent fired rounds from exiting the perimeter of the facility. The small-arms firing range is the only training area where live fire is permitted at the BTC.

Brett Hall Facility Area

The Brett Hall Facility Area consists of approximately 75 acres of federal land withdrawn from public domain until December 9, 2006, for exclusive use by the Army. Brett Hall is the operating facility for the BTC and consists of a 14,350 square foot

Grazing Areas

Biak Training Center
Deschutes and Crook Counties, Oregon

Figure 3-1

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multipurpose building that houses range control, logistical and communications equipment, an equipment hangar, and offices. Other improvements include a helicopter pad.

3.2 FACILITIES

3.2.1 Transportation Systems

Transportation systems at the BTC consist of a network of improved paved and graveled roads and unimproved dirt roads of native soil, roughly bounded by a system of paved highways. Major improved roads that bisect or that are close to the BTC include Highway 126 to the north, Powell Butte Highway to the east and south, and Highway 97 to the west (Figure 3-2). Secondary paved roads at the BTC are limited to two roads that enter the military training site from Highway 126 to the north. These are Phil Sheridan Road into the COUTES facility and John Bufford Road into the Brett Hall facility. Utility companies, railroad companies, the North Unit Irrigation District (NUID), the BLM, owners of private property in-holdings, and the public also may use these roads to access their facilities and for recreation.

A network of unimproved dirt roads provides multiple access points to the undeveloped portions of the military training site. These roadways are principally used by the military during training exercises, by the public for outdoor recreation activities, by the utility companies and NUID, and by livestock grazing permittees during grazing seasons. In addition, some of these roads provide access to the private land in-holdings within the boundaries of the BTC. Per the special use permit issued by the BLM, dirt roads used by the military are graded annually to reduce soil erosion and to minimize vehicle damage.

Two bridges crossing the North Unit Main Canal provide the only permanent irrigation canal crossing sites for the BTC (Figure 3-3). The bridges are owned and maintained by the ORARNG and are open to public use (McCaffrey 2001). The ORARNG has been granted permission to access these bridges during military training exercises using individual wheeled vehicles only (no convoys). The bridges are the only physical means of accessing Training Area A from Training Areas B or D without leaving the BTC boundary. The bridges have a physical capacity of 75 tons.

The NUID permits ORARNG to train using temporary mechanical bridges at specified points along the North Unit Main Canal. AVLBs provide temporary, training event-specific bridges for stream crossings and are removed upon completion of a training exercise.

3.2.2 Utilities and Related Structures

Water Supply Systems

The BTC has few natural water features and is composed of internal, very localized, and ephemeral drainage characteristics, with no natural waterways or surface impoundments. The sole surface water resource at the BTC is the North Unit Main Canal, which runs roughly south to north and flows from April through October

(Figure 3-3). The canal is used exclusively for off-site agricultural purposes; the BTC maintains no water rights for this surface water source. A groundwater aquifer (ranging from 200 to 600 feet deep) beneath the BTC is the principal hydrologic feature of the military training site and is used for potable water needs at the BTC. A domestic well serving the potable water needs of the BTC was drilled into an aquifer at a depth of 420 feet in 1979 near the COUTES facility. The water supply system includes a cistern that holds water pumped from the well at an approximate rate of 30 gallons per minute (OMD 1995). A second well of an undisclosed depth was drilled in 1986 at the Brett Hall facility and supplies two 25,000-gallon buried reservoir tanks with potable water. A buried water pipeline that runs approximately the length of Training Area A is used by private entities.

Wastewater Treatment and Disposal

The BTC maintains standard industrial-sized septic systems and associated drainfields at the COUTES and Brett Hall facilities. These systems collect sanitary wastewater discharged from the facilities; stormwater runoff is not collected using this system.

Stormwater Collection

As the BTC lacks significant cantonment areas or improved roadways, the military training site neither owns, maintains, nor operates a stormwater collection system. Stormwater runoff from the COUTES and Brett Hall developed areas and associated structures is allowed to percolate or evaporate without treatment.

Solid Waste Collection and Disposal

BTC solid waste is removed weekly by a private contractor and is delivered to various facilities, depending on the waste type.

Power Services

BTC electrical power is provided by the Pacific Power and Light Company. Two powerlines bisect the BTC: the Bonneville Power Administration's Redmond-Harney power transmission line and the Pacific Power and Light Company's Pilot Butte-Prineville power transmission line (Figure 3-3). These utility corridors have been developed under a right-of-way grant issued by the BLM to the respective utility operators. The BTC has no management oversight or responsibility for maintaining either utility corridor or related utility structures therein. Military training exercises consisting of vehicular maneuvers are limited within the utility corridors.

Natural Gas Pipeline

The Pacific Gas Transmission Company owns, maintains, and operates two natural gas pipelines within a shared right-of-way at the BTC (Figure 3-3). The subterranean pipelines roughly parallel the North Unit Main Canal. The original pipeline was constructed in 1961 under a right-of-way grant issued by the BLM to the utility operator, and the expansion pipeline was completed in the mid-1990s. The BTC has no management oversight or responsibility for maintaining the natural gas pipelines. Military training exercises consisting of vehicular maneuvers are restricted on terrain overlying the pipelines.

Legend

- North Unit Main Canal
- Dirt or Gravel Road
- Paved Road
- Training Areas
- Off Limits to Military Training
- OMD - Controlled Property

Not all roads are shown.

Regional Transportation Systems

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Legend

- Pipelines
- Bridges
- Powerlines
- North Unit Main Canal
- Training Areas
- Off Limits to Military Training
- OMD - Controlled Property

**Bridges, North Unit Main Canal,
Powerlines, and Natural Gas Pipelines**

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3.3 CLIMATE

The climate of the region is semiarid, with low annual precipitation, dry summers with warm days and cool nights, and cool-to-cold, relatively snow-free winters. Hard frosts are possible in all months except June, July, and August (Jones 2000). Table 3-1 illustrates the maximum, average, and minimum temperature and precipitation data for the BTC, as collected at Roberts Field, the airport for the city of Redmond (BTC 1999).

The average monthly temperature for the region is 47 degrees Fahrenheit (F). The average temperature in June, July, and August is 63 degrees F; the average temperature in December, January, and February is 33 degrees F. The extreme temperatures range from a high of 108 degrees F to a low of -27 degrees F. Total annual precipitation for the region is between 8 and 10 inches (BTC 1999).

Table 3-1
Climatic Data for Roberts Field from 1961 to 1990

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Temperature Data (F)												
E. Max.	67	72	80	89	99	101	105	108	99	95	76	67
M. Max.	41	47	53	59	67	77	85	84	75	64	49	42
Mean	31	36	40	44	51	59	66	65	57	48	38	32
M. Min.	22	25	26	29	35	42	46	46	39	32	27	22
E. Min.	-27	-19	0	10	12	24	28	31	16	4	-10	-28
Precipitation Data (Inches)												
Mean	1.06	0.60	0.69	0.58	0.71	0.73	0.45	0.54	0.41	0.54	1.16	1.09
E. 24-hour	1.57	1.07	0.62	0.95	0.72	1.81	0.86	0.69	0.73	0.57	1.40	1.39
Snowfall (Inches)												
Mean	5.43	2.74	1.91	1.13	0.07	0.08	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.15	3.28	5.02

Source: BTC 1999.

Abbreviations: E. Max. = extreme maximum; M. Max. = mean maximum; M. Min. = mean minimum; E. Min. = extreme minimum; E. 24-hour = extreme 24-hour precipitation.

The mean annual precipitation for Roberts Field, adjacent to the BTC, from 1961 to 1990, was 8.62 inches. Wind data for Roberts Field from 1949 to 1958 shows that sustained hourly winds are strongest from the southeast and south-southeast in January and February, with sustained wind speeds of 39 to 46 mph and averages of approximately 12 mph. Summer winds are predominantly from the west and northwest, with sustained speeds of 25 to 31 mph and average wind speeds of approximately 9 mph in May, June, and July. This data, however, is for sustained hourly winds and does not include wind gust speeds or directions associated with individual thunderstorms (BTC 1999).

3.4 GEOLOGY

3.4.1 Physiography

The topography of the BTC consists of the very gently sloping and undulating terrain that characterizes the High Lava Plains ecoregional province (Bailey 1976) (Figure 3-4). This ecoregional province is composed of moderately dissected mountains and broad flat uplands; debris slides, rock fall, and slow creep are erosional processes that dominate slopes of 20 to 120 percent (about 10 to 60 degrees). A multitude of young eruptive events have left volcanic features, such as basalt outcrops, pressure ridges, and blisters that punctuate the landscape. Middle and late Miocene basalt flows typically underlie a more recent 10- to 100-foot thick veneer of igneous flow that originated from on or near the flanks of the Newberry strato/composite volcano. Elevation typically ranges from 2,000 to 5,000 feet above sea level for the High Lava Plains ecoregional province, though local relief is mostly in the range of 300 to 800 feet.

3.4.2 Geologic Structure

The High Lava Plains ecoregional province is composed of Eocene, Oligocene, and Miocene basalt flows with minor tuffs, sandstone, and siltstone. The region underlying the BTC is predominantly Columbia River basalt group equivalent. Extensive playa valleys are filled in with fluvial sediments and volcanic ash (McNab and Avers 1994). There are no known active faults in the immediate area surrounding the BTC, though the region holds the potential for seismic activity.

3.5 SOIL RESOURCES

The primary goals of soil conservation and management at the BTC are to protect soil resources, to identify areas prone to soil erosion, and to prevent unnecessary soil erosion associated with the military mission. Due to the predominantly flat to gently rolling terrain at the BTC, most undisturbed soils are considered minimally susceptible to erosion. Still, soils disturbed by human- or animal-induced impacts are susceptible to wind erosion and often are found in areas where vegetation has been removed or severely degraded, such as graded roads and livestock holding areas (Myhrum et al. 1999).

Soil types found at the BTC are strongly influenced by Mazama pumice, with windblown sands originating in Pleistocene lakebeds, and Mount Mazama and Newberry craters pumice. Soils between basalt outcrops, pressure ridges, and blisters are typically moderately deep sandy loams or loamy sands that are formed in alluvium from volcanic ash and other materials weathered from lava rock (Jones 2000). The most extensive soil types are those associated with the Deschutes, Stukel, and Gosney soil series. All soils in a series have major horizons that are similar in composition, thickness, and arrangement. A soil complex is composed of two or more soil series. Listed below and illustrated on Figure 3-5 are the dominant soil complexes identified at the BTC. All soils information was extracted from soil surveys conducted by the Natural Resources Conservation Service for Deschutes and Crook counties, Oregon (Myhrum et al. 1999).

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Legend

- North Unit Main Canal
 - Off Limits to Military Training
 - Training Area
 - OMD - Controlled Property
- Contour Interval 20 Feet

Geographic Relief

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Deschutes and Crook Counties, Oregon

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Legend

- North Unit Main Canal
- Off Limits to Military Training
- Area F - No Data Available
- Training Area
- OMD - Controlled Property

Soil Types

- Deschutes-Houstake Complex
- Deschutes-Stukel Complex
- Gosney-Rock outcrop-Deskamp Complex
- Redmond sandy loam
- Stukel-Deschutes complex
- Stukel-Rock outcrop-Deschutes

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Soils

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Deschutes-Houstake Complex—The Deschutes-Houstake complex contains 50 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Deschutes soil series, 35 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Houstake soil series, and 15 percent contrasting inclusions. These soils were formed in volcanic ash and typically are located at elevations of 2,500 to 4,000 feet, on slopes of zero to eight percent. The typical depth to bedrock underlying the Deschutes-Houstake soil complex is 20 to 60 inches. These well-drained, moderately deep to very deep sandy loam soils have moderately rapid permeability and an available water capacity of four to seven inches.

Deschutes-Stukel Complex—The Deschutes-Stukel soil complex contains 50 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Deschutes soil series, 35 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Stukel series, and 15 percent contrasting inclusions. These soils were formed in volcanic ash and typically are located at elevations of 2,500 to 4,000 feet, on slopes of zero to eight percent. The typical depth to bedrock underlying the Deschutes-Stukel soil complex is 10 to 40 inches. These well-drained, shallow to moderately deep sandy loam soils have moderately rapid permeability and an available water capacity of two to four inches.

Gosney-Rock Outcrop-Deskamp Complex—The Gosney-Rock Outcrop-Deskamp soil complex contains 50 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Gosney soil series, 25 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Rock Outcrop series, 20 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Deskamp soil series, and 5 percent contrasting inclusions. These soils were formed in volcanic ash and typically are located at elevations of 3,000 to 4,000 feet, on slopes of zero to 15 percent. The typical depth to bedrock underlying the Gosney-Rock Outcrop-Deskamp soil complex is 10 to 40 inches. These somewhat excessively drained, shallow to moderately deep, sandy loam soils have rapid permeability and an available water capacity of one to three inches.

Redmond Sandy Loam Complex—The Redmond Sandy Loam soil complex contains 85 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Redmond soil series and 15 percent contrasting inclusions. These soils were formed in volcanic ash and typically are located at elevations of 3,000 to 4,000 feet, on slopes of zero to three percent. The typical depth to bedrock underlying the Redmond Sandy Loam soil complex is 20 to 40 inches. These well-drained, moderately deep, sandy loam soils have moderate permeability and an available water capacity of four inches.

Stukel-Deschutes Complex—The Stukel-Deschutes soil complex contains 50 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Stukel soil series, 35 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Deschutes series, and 15 percent contrasting inclusions. These soils were formed in volcanic ash and typically are located at elevations of 2,500 to 4,000 feet, on slopes of zero to eight percent. The typical depth to bedrock underlying the Stukel-Deschutes soil complex is 10 to 40 inches. These well-drained, shallow to moderately deep, sandy loam soils have moderately rapid permeability and an available water capacity of two to four inches.

Stukel-Rock Outcrop-Deschutes Complex—The Stukel-Rock Outcrop-Deschutes soil complex contains 35 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Stukel soil series, 30 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Rock Outcrop series, 20 percent soil and similar inclusions from the Deschutes soil series, and 15 percent contrasting inclusions. These soils were formed in volcanic ash and typically are located at elevations of 2,500 to 3,500 feet, on slopes of zero to 15 percent. The typical depth to bedrock underlying the Stukel-Rock Outcrop-Deschutes soil complex is 10 to 40 inches. These well-drained, shallow to moderately deep, sandy loam soils have moderately rapid permeability and an available water capacity of two to four inches.

3.6 WATER RESOURCES

The BTC is hydrologically undeveloped, owing to the geological recency of the terrain and the region's low annual precipitation. As a result the BTC has few natural water features and is composed of internal, very localized, and ephemeral drainage characteristics, with no natural waterways or surface impoundments. The sole surface water resource at the BTC is the North Unit Main Canal, which runs roughly south to north and flows from April through October (Figure 3-3). A groundwater aquifer (ranging from 200 to 600 feet deep) beneath the BTC is the principal geohydrologic feature of the military training site (OMD 1995, ORARNG 1999d).

There are several water guzzlers throughout the BTC. The guzzlers were installed by either the BLM or the ODFW and are used by wildlife; fencing prohibits livestock from using the guzzlers. Most of the guzzlers appear to suffer from signs of deferred maintenance and are filled only with precipitation. Unless determined otherwise, the water guzzlers are the property and sole responsibility of the BLM. Numerous private livestock-only watering troughs, installed by the livestock grazing permittees, also are found throughout the BTC. The BTC prohibits the military from using, altering, or damaging the water guzzlers or livestock watering troughs during training exercises.

The principal federal laws protecting water quality are the Clean Water Act (33 USC §§ 1251 - 1387) and the Safe Drinking Water Act (42 USC §§ 300f - 300j-26). Both laws are enforced by the EPA. The CWA protects surface water quality and preserves wetlands, and the Safe Drinking Water Act protects drinking water supplies.

At the state level, several regulations pertaining to water quality have been adopted into Chapter 340 of the Oregon Administrative Rules (OAR) and Chapter 468b of the Oregon Revised Statutes (ORS). A complete listing of these rules is available electronically at <http://waterquality.deq.state.or.us/wq/wqrules/wqrules.htm>.

Also at the state level, Oregon water law allows the exempt use of groundwater for up to 15,000 gallons per day for domestic uses and the irrigation of up to 0.5 acre of non-commercial lawn and garden. The law also allows 5,000 gallons per day for commercial use (Gorman 2000).

The Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), in support of local flood management agencies, identifies flood zones under the National Flood Insurance

Program. A product of these studies is flood insurance rate maps, which delineate the regions that would be inundated by floods with average recurrence intervals of 100 and 500 years. FEMA flood insurance programs do not apply to federal lands, such as those managed by the BLM or used by the BTC.

The potential for localized flooding at the BTC is considered minimal due to the relatively flat to undulating terrain of the military training site, the lack of surface water drainages, and the mostly permeable soils that are moderately to well drained.

3.7 VEGETATION

This section describes the vegetation at the BTC and includes a discussion on specific vegetative communities and invasive or noxious weeds.

3.7.1 Vegetative Communities

The western juniper (*Juniperus occidentalis*) woodland community is the dominant vegetative mosaic of the BTC and generally is characterized by an open juniper canopy of less than 10 percent cover, sparse to moderate cover of shrubs, tussock grasses, and a very sparse perennial forb component (Miller and Rose 2000). Vegetative data collected at the BTC during the 1998 and 1999 field seasons indicate that western juniper cover averaged four percent, with a mean density of 17 trees per acre. Approximately half of those trees are considered post-settlement (established in the past 120 years), with the other half considered presettlement (established more than 120 years ago); specifically, the juniper overstory is mixed age with presettlement trees composing 22 to 63 percent of the stand (Jones 2000). The understory vegetative community consists of ninety species that were detected using understory sampling plots. The understory community consists of shrubs, perennial grasses, perennial forbs, and annual forbs and grasses (Miller and Rose 2000).

Oregon State University (OSU) has classified seven major vegetative communities at the BTC using the US National Vegetation Classification System. Vegetative communities are classified at the alliance level (minus the microphyllous evergreen shrubland, classified at the formation level), with this hierarchy based on existing qualitative and quantitative data. The OSU information is summarized below and is illustrated in Figure 3-6.

Big Sagebrush Shrubland Alliance

The big sagebrush (*Artemisia tridentata*) alliance is the most dominant vegetative community at the BTC. Associated understory vegetation consists of gray rabbitbrush (*Chrysothamnus nauseosus*) and green rabbitbrush (*C. viscidiflorus*) as codominant taxa. The percent cover of the herbaceous grass understory is variable, with the most common species being cheatgrass (*Bromus tectorum*), squirreltail (*Elymus elymoides*), crested wheatgrass (*Agropyron cristatum*), Idaho fescue (*Festuca idahoensis*), and bluebunch wheatgrass (*Pseudoroegneria spicata*). The percent cover of the herbaceous forb understory is almost always less than five percent. The big sagebrush shrubland alliance is a member of the microphyllous evergreen shrubland formation.

Bitterbrush Shrubland Alliance

This alliance is defined as having bitterbrush (*Purshia tridentata*) as a dominant taxon and is a member of the microphyllous evergreen shrubland formation. The alliance also consists of gray rabbitbrush, green rabbitbrush, and big sagebrush as other codominant taxa. Western juniper, if present, totals less than 25 percent canopy cover. The percent cover of the herbaceous grass understory is variable. The most common species include cheatgrass, squirreltail, Idaho fescue, and bluebunch wheatgrass. The percent cover of the herbaceous forb understory is almost always less than five percent.

Western Juniper Woodland Alliance

The western juniper shrubland alliance is defined as being equal to or greater than 25 percent western juniper canopy cover. This can be less than 25 percent where it exceeds that of the shrub or herbaceous grass cover. In such areas, tree canopy cover is typically 15 to 25 percent, while shrub or grass cover is less than 15 percent. The percent cover of the herbaceous grass understory is variable. The most common species include cheatgrass, Idaho fescue, and bluebunch wheatgrass. The percent cover of the herbaceous forb understory is almost always less than five percent. The western juniper woodland alliance is a member of the rounded-crown temperate or subpolar needle-leaved evergreen woodland formation.

Western Juniper Wooded Herbaceous Alliance

The western juniper wooded herbaceous alliance is dominated either by Idaho fescue or bluebunch wheatgrass. This alliance also can consist of cheatgrass or bluegrass (*Poa secunda*) as codominant taxa. Western juniper, if present, totals less than 25 percent canopy cover. The shrub layer, big sagebrush, bitterbrush, gray rabbitbrush, or green rabbitbrush, composes less than 15 percent cover. The percent cover of the herbaceous grass understory is variable. The most common species include cheatgrass, squirreltail, Idaho fescue, and bluebunch wheatgrass. The percent cover of the herbaceous forb understory is almost always less than five percent. The western juniper wooded herbaceous alliance is a member of the medium-tall temperate grassland, with sparse needle-leaved evergreen or mixed tree layer formation.

Green Rabbitbrush Shrub Herbaceous Alliance

This alliance is dominated by cheatgrass, crested wheatgrass, or a mixture of native perennial grasses. At the BTC, this alliance represents an early seral community that could be undergoing chronic intense disturbance that prohibits late seral shrub species from colonizing. Western juniper, if present, likely totals less than five percent canopy cover. Green rabbitbrush dominates the shrub layer, with big sagebrush and gray rabbitbrush making up five to ten percent of the total shrub layer. The percent cover of the herbaceous forb understory is almost always less than five percent. The green rabbitbrush shrub herbaceous alliance is a member of the medium-tall temperate grassland with a sparse needle-leaved evergreen or mixed tree layer formation.

Legend

- North Unit Main Canal
- Training Areas
- Off Limits to Military Training
- Area F - No Data Available
- OMD - Controlled Property
- Big Sagebrush shrubland alliance
- Bitterbrush shrubland alliance
- Green Rabbitbrush shrub herbaceous alliance
- Western Juniper wooded herbaceous alliance
- Western Juniper woodland alliance
- Managed Big Sagebrush shrubland
- Microphyllous evergreen shrubland formation
- Developed

Vegetative Communities

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Figure 3-6

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Managed Big Sagebrush Shrubland Alliance

This alliance, similar to the big sagebrush shrubland alliance in both composition and cover, is only within close proximity of the North Unit Main Canal. The vegetation is indistinguishable from the true big sagebrush shrubland alliance, except that junipers are removed from near or on the canal roadway for irrigation canal management. Similar circumstances occur near and adjacent to the natural gas pipeline and utility powerlines. (The natural gas pipeline is dominated by gray rabbitbrush.) Some inclusions within this managed alliance could have big sagebrush or green rabbitbrush as codominant taxa.

Microphyllous Evergreen Shrubland Formation

Areas within the BTC classified as this shrubland formation appear to be an amalgamation of the big sagebrush shrubland alliance and the bitterbrush shrubland alliance. The composition and cover of the species within this formation are the same as those listed under big sagebrush shrubland alliance and the bitterbrush shrubland alliance.

3.7.2 Special Natural Areas Protection and Management

DOD Instruction 4715.3 specifies that "areas on DOD installations that contain natural resources that warrant special conservation efforts ... may be designated as special natural areas." It further states that "the natural resources management plan for the installation shall address special management provisions necessary for the protection of each area." These special natural areas can include botanical areas, ecological reserve areas, geological areas, natural resource areas, riparian areas, scenic areas, or zoological areas, "watchable wildlife" areas, and traditional cultural places having officially recognized special qualities or attributes (DOD 1996).

There are three vegetative communities within the boundaries of the BTC that have been identified and warrant special management because of their ecological importance. These communities are the bitterbrush shrubland alliance, western juniper wooded herbaceous alliance, and western juniper woodland alliance, which are depicted on Figure 3-6. These areas are generally not of exceptional importance on a national or state basis but are unique at the BTC and/or in the region. There are no existing management plans for these communities. No other special natural areas have been identified at the BTC.

3.7.3 Land Condition-Trend Analysis

The BTC has implemented the Army's LCTA as a component of the ITAM program. LCTA provides for collecting, inventorying, monitoring, managing, and analyzing tabular and spatial data concerning land conditions on military training lands over time. LCTA provides the baseline and trend data needed to evaluate the capability of training lands to meet and sustain multiple use demands. The final product of the LCTA is a relational database and a geographical information system that can be used to support land use planning and training area management. The LCTA program was implemented at the BTC during the summer of 1999 to inventory baseline flora conditions and disturbance on the military training site. A total of 172 vegetative

monitoring plots were randomly established and marked for present and future sampling. Data collected from LCTA plots provide critical information on changes and trends in the makeup of BTC vegetation and could be useful in identifying cause and effect relationships for these changes over time. These changes can be percent of ground cover, percent of bare ground, percent of non-native species, proportions of annual versus perennial vegetation, and species composition. (Note that LCTA data may not be able to differentiate between impacts caused by individual user groups. For instance, it might not be possible to determine if soil in a given area was disturbed by military vehicles or public off-road recreationists.)

According to the baseline 1999 and 2000 LCTA data, the following general vegetative information is known. Basal cover (combined woody and herbaceous cover) over the entire BTC is considered very low for all plant species. The perennial forb component accounts for one percent or less of the plant cover and composition on the pumice soils of the BTC (Jones 2000). Bare ground and litter dominate the ground cover for all training areas on the military training site. Microphyte cover (plants of microscopic size) is most prevalent in Training Areas B and C and in off-limits areas. Aerial cover is also low for most plant species and is dominated by litter, cheatgrass, and western juniper (Jones 2000).

3.7.4 Invasive or Noxious Weeds

The BTC pest management program supports the integrated weed management (IWM) program developed by the BLM Prineville District. Noxious weed eradication or control is a vital tool for ecosystem management because it protects biodiversity through the maintenance of native vegetative diversity and improvement of native rangelands (BLM 1994). The IWM program and ORARNG Regulation 210-5 promote four primary control strategies for noxious weeds—mechanical and physical control (physically removing or excluding weeds), cultural control (altering the environment to make it less suitable or attractive to the weed), biological control (using other organisms to control the weed), and chemical control (using herbicides).

Noxious weed eradication or control is a vital tool for ecosystem management because it protects biodiversity by maintaining native vegetation. Lists of noxious or invasive weeds are maintained by both federal and state agencies. The US Department of Agriculture (USDA) noxious weed program and the Oregon Department of Agriculture (ODA) noxious weed control program define weeds that are injurious to public health, agriculture, recreation, wildlife, or any public or private property. Additionally, the BLM Prineville District has developed a noxious weed control program to reduce populations of identified noxious weeds.

The ODA maintains a statewide quarantine against noxious weeds under ORS 570.505. Table 3-2 lists noxious weeds that could occur at the BTC. Noxious weeds are classified under a rating system based on possible eradication or containment, occurrence, and regional distribution. Noxious weeds rated as “A” are of known economic importance and occur in the state in small enough infestations to make

Table 3-2
List of Potentially Occurring Noxious Weeds at the BTC

Common Name	Scientific Name	BLM Weed Priority Number	ODA Noxious Weed Rating System
African rue*	<i>Pegonium harmala</i>	22	A
Austrian peaweed (Swainsonpea)	<i>Sphaerophysa salsula</i>	--	B
Barbed goatgrass	<i>Aegilops triuncialis</i>	--	A
Bearded creeper (common crupia)	<i>Crupina vulgaris</i>	15	A
Biddy-biddy	<i>Acacia novae-zelandiae</i>	--	B
Big-headed knapweed	<i>Centaurea macrocephala</i>	--	A
Buffaloburr	<i>Solanum rostratum</i>	--	B
Bulbed goatgrass	<i>Aegilops ventricosa</i>	--	A
Bull thistle*	<i>Cirsium vulgare</i>	35	B
Camelthorn	<i>Alhagi pseudalhagi</i>	50	A
Canada thistle*	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	14	B
Coltsfoot	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	--	A
Creeping yellow cress	<i>Rorippa sylestris</i>	--	B
Dalmation toadflax*	<i>Linaria dalmatica</i>	4	B
Diffuse knapweed*	<i>Centaurea diffusa</i>	8	B
Dodder	<i>Cuscuta</i> spp.	20	B
Dyers woad	<i>Isatis tinctoria</i>	42	B
Eurasian watermilfoil	<i>Myriophyllum spicatum</i>	48	B
Feather-headed knapweed	<i>Centaurea trichocephala</i>	--	A
Field bindweed	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	31	B
French broom	<i>Cytisus monspessulanus</i>	--	B
Giant hogweed	<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>	--	A
Giant horsetail	<i>Equisetum telmateia</i>	--	B
Giant knotweed	<i>Polygonum sachalinense</i>	--	B
Globe-podded thistle	<i>Cardaria pubescens</i>	--	B
Gorse	<i>Ulex europaeus</i>	--	B
Halogeton	<i>Halogeton glomeratus</i>	29	B
Himalayan knotweed	<i>Polygonum polystachyum</i>	--	B
Houndstongue	<i>Cynoglossum officinale</i>	--	B
Hydrilla	<i>Hydrilla verticillata</i>	--	A
Iberian starthistle	<i>Centaurea iberica</i>	47	A
Italian thistle	<i>Cardus pycnocephalus</i>	41	B
Japanese knotweed (fleece flower)	<i>Polygonum cuspidatum</i>	--	B
Johnsongrass	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	25	B
Jointed goatgrass	<i>Aegilops cylindrical</i>	30	B
Kochia	<i>Kochia scoparia</i>	21	B
Kudzu	<i>Pueraria lobata</i>	--	A
Leafy spurge*	<i>Euphorbia esula</i>	2	B
Lens-podded thistle	<i>Cardaria dhalapensis</i>	--	B
Lepyroclis	<i>Lepyroclis holosteoides</i>	--	A

Table 3-2
List of Potentially Occurring Noxious Weeds at the BTC (continued)

Common Name	Scientific Name	BLM Weed Priority Number	ODA Noxious Weed Rating System
Matgrass	<i>Nardus stricta</i>	18	A
Meadow knapweed*	<i>Centaurea pratensis</i>	--	B
Mediterranean sage*	<i>Salvia aethiops</i>	3	B
Medusahead rye	<i>Taeniatherum caput-medusae</i>	16	B
Musk thistle*	<i>Carduus nutans</i>	17	B
Ovate goatgrass	<i>Aegilops ovata</i>	--	A
Perennial pepperweed*	<i>Lepidium latifolium</i>	34	B
Plumeless thistle	<i>Carduus alantoides</i>	--	A
Poison hemlock	<i>Conium maculatum</i>	27	B
Portugese broom	<i>Cytisus striatus</i>	--	B
Puncture vine	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	13	B
Purple loosestrife	<i>Lythrum salicaria</i>	23	B
Purple nutsedge	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	--	A
Purple starthistle	<i>Centaurea nigrescens</i>	46	A
Quackgrass	<i>Aegypyon repens</i>	--	B
Ragweed	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	--	B
Rush skeletonweed	<i>Chondrilla juncea</i>	6	B
Russian knapweed*	<i>Centaurea repens</i>	10	B
Scotch broom*	<i>Cytisus scoparius</i>	24	B
Scotch thistle	<i>Onopordum acanthium</i>	7	B
Short-fringed knapweed	<i>Centaurea nigrescens</i>	--	A
Silverleaf nightshade	<i>Solanum elaeagnifolium</i>	--	A
Skeletonleaf bursage	<i>Ambrosia tomentosa</i>	--	A
Slender-flowered thistle	<i>Carduus tenuiflorus</i>	--	B
Smooth cordgrass	<i>Spartina alterniflora</i>	--	A
Smooth distaff thistle	<i>Carthamus balticus</i>	--	A
South American waterweed (elodea)	<i>Elodea densa</i>	--	B
Spanish broom	<i>Spartium junceum</i>	--	B
Spartina	<i>Spartina anglica</i>	--	A
Spartina	<i>S. densiflora</i>	--	A
Spartina	<i>S. patens</i>	--	B
Spikeweed	<i>Hemizonia purgens</i>	38	B
Spiny cocklebur	<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	39	B
Spotted knapweed*	<i>Centaurea maculosa</i>	9	B
Squarrose knapweed	<i>C. virgata</i>	19	A
Sulfur cinquefoil	<i>Potentilla recta</i>	--	B
Syrian bean-caper	<i>Zygophyllum fabago</i>	--	A
Tamarisk	<i>Tamarix ramosissima</i>	--	B
Tansy ragwort	<i>Senecio jacobaea</i>	5	B
Tausch's goatgrass	<i>Aegilops tauschii</i>	--	A

Table 3-2
List of Potentially Occurring Noxious Weeds at the BTC (continued)

Common Name	Scientific Name	BLM Weed Priority Number	ODA Noxious Weed Rating System
Texas blueweed	<i>Helianthus ciliaris</i>	--	A
Velvetleaf*	<i>Abitilon theophrasti</i>	--	B
White top (Hoary cress)*	<i>Cardaria</i> spp.	12	B
Whitestem distaff thistle	<i>Carthamus leucocaulos</i>	--	A
Wild proso millet	<i>Panicum miliaceum</i>	40	B
Wild safflower	<i>Carthamus oxycanthus</i>	--	A
Wooly distaff thistle	<i>C. lanatus</i>	49	A
Yellow nutsedge	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	45	B
Yellow starthistle	<i>Centaurea solstitialis</i>	1	B
Yellow toadflax	<i>Linaria vulgaris</i>	33	B

Source: BLM 1994; ODA 2000.

ODA Noxious Weed Rating System:

A - Noxious weeds of known economic importance that occur in the state in small enough infestations to make eradication/containment possible or that are not known to occur but their presence in neighboring states makes future occurrence in Oregon imminent.

B - Noxious weeds of economic importance that are regionally abundant but that could have limited distribution in some counties.

* - Noxious weeds that are known to occur in Crook and Deschutes counties, Oregon.

eradication and containment possible or that are not known to occur but their presence in neighboring states makes future occurrence in Oregon imminent. Noxious weeds designated with a "B" rating are of economic importance and are regionally abundant but could have limited distribution in some counties. Those species that have been assigned an eradication/control number by the BLM also have been identified. In Table 3-2, noxious species known to occur in Crook and Deschutes counties have been identified with an asterisk. Two species of noxious weeds, Scotch thistle (*Onopordium acanthium*) and spotted knapweed (*Centaurea maculosa*), have been identified at the BTC and are nonnative plants of the ORARNG's noxious weed control program (McCaffrey 2001). Most of the noxious or invasive species listed are uncommon, are confined to specific often highly disturbed habitats or are widespread, but they generally present a relatively low density at the BTC. The following noxious weed species are listed on the federal noxious weed list as maintained by the USDA but have not been detected in either Crook or Deschutes counties or the BTC: bearded creeper (*Cripina vulgaris*), giant hogweed (*Heracleum mantegazzianum*), hydrilla (*Hydrilla verticillata*), and wild safflower (*Carthamus oxycanthus*).

3.8 WETLANDS

Wetlands are of critical importance to the protection and maintenance of biological resources because they provide essential breeding, spawning, nesting, and wintering grounds for numerous wildlife species. Wetlands also enhance the quality of surface waters by impeding erosive forces of moving water and trapping waterborne sediment and associated pollutants, providing a gradual release of stored flood waters and

groundwater and a natural means of flood control and storm damage protection by absorbing and storing water during periods of high runoff.

DOD natural resources policy states that wetlands will be protected. All activities that affect wetlands require an environmental analysis, in accordance with AR 200-1, AR 200-2, and applicable federal and state laws and regulations. EO 11990 requires that federal agencies minimize any significant action that contributes to the loss or degradation of wetlands and that action should be initiated to enhance their natural value. COE permits are required under Section 404 of the CWA for discharging dredge or fill material into waters of the US, including wetlands.

The Army maintains a goal of no net loss of values and functions to existing wetlands and permits no overall net loss of wetlands on Army-managed lands (US Army 1995). At the BTC, a wetlands management policy with the objective of maintaining no net loss of wetlands habitat will be continued. Activities occurring both in and adjacent to wetlands that would result in negative impacts on the habitats will be avoided, when possible, in a manner consistent with mission objectives.

Biological surveys conducted by the ONHP (Kagan 1993) and the ORARNG at the BTC identified the streambed and banks of the North Unit Main Canal as an intermittent riverine, semipermanently flooded wetland. Several ephemeral wetlands associated with seepage from the canal also were noted. Approximately five to fifteen of these are palustrine emergent wetlands located immediately adjacent to the canal and north of the Township 15 South/16 South line. A palustrine scrub-shrub wetland, located south of the canal and Bonneville Power Administration's Redmond-Hamey powerline crossing, and a palustrine unconsolidated bottom/diked wetland, located north of the Township South/16 South line, are other seasonally wet wetlands located at the BTC. The silt pond also associated with the canal is the only wetland identified as permanently flooded. Currently, no wetlands at the BTC have been designated as jurisdictional. An ONHP wetlands survey of 1993 did not identify any significant wetland habitats at the BTC (OMD 1995).

The NUID is responsible for managing, maintaining, and regulating waters associated with the North Unit Main Canal. In fall 2000, the NUID began lining with concrete those segments of the canal within the boundaries of the BTC. This work will include the reconstruction of the levee in the vicinity of the perennial silt pond. As a result, the perennial silt pond will be drained and the wetlands/seeps will likely diminish considerably in size and capacity. As this is a NUID action, the BTC has no control or authority over the lining of the canal or its potential impacts on wetland resources associated with the canal. The action is scheduled to be complete by spring 2002 (McCaffrey 2000).

3.9 WILDLIFE

The BTC has worked closely with the USFWS and ODFW to develop a game and nongame wildlife management program. The management of game wildlife resources focuses on maintaining and controlling populations compatible with the range they

occupy, land management objectives, and the military mission and provides for quality recreational opportunities for all public land users. Hunting any game species on or migrating through the BTC is regulated by the ODFW. These game species include mule deer, pronghorn antelope, American elk, upland game birds, and waterfowl. Nongame species management focuses on maintaining population levels compatible with land use objectives and the military mission, while promoting biodiversity. The basis of managing a rich assemblage of nongame wildlife is to provide a mosaic of habitats that are structurally and biologically diverse. These habitat types at the BTC include shrub steppe and upland environs. Wildlife found at the BTC consists of both resident and migrant species common to central Oregon.

Surveys conducted to assess the presence and diversity of wildlife species at the BTC include the *Inventory and Evaluation of Vertebrate Fauna at the BTC* (Reiher et al. 2000) and the *Inventory for Rare, Threatened, and Endangered Species and Significant Habitats* (Kagan 1993). A summary of the wildlife species either observed during these studies or expected to occur is presented in Table 3-3.

Native Species

Reiher et al. (2000) noted that approximately 70 species of bird were observed either on or migrating through the BTC between March 1999 and March 2000. The overwhelming majority of these species were native, with the most frequent sightings being the American robin (*Turdus migratorius*), Townsend's solitaire (*Myadestes townsendii*), western meadowlark (*Sturnella neglecta*), and the northern flicker (*Colaptes auratus*). Overall species richness appeared to be higher in the spring than the winter (Reiher et al. 2000).

Also during the 1999-2000 survey, approximately 22 species of mammal were witnessed, with the deer mouse (*Peromyscus maniculatus*) the most frequently observed species. Other common mammalian species include the yellow-pine chipmunk (*Tamias amoenus*), bushy-tailed wood rat (*Neotoma cinerea*), black-tailed jackrabbit (*Lepus californicus*), and Nuttall's cottontail (*Sylvilagus nuttalli*). Five reptile species and two amphibian species were observed, with the most common reptiles being the sagebrush lizard (*Sceloporus graciosus*), western fence lizard (*Sceloporus occidentalis*), and western skink (*Eumeces skiltonianus*), and the most common amphibians being the Pacific chorus frog (*Pseudacris regilla*) and the Great Basin spadefoot toad (*Scaphiopus intermontanus*) (Reiher et al. 2000).

Table 3-3
Wildlife Species Observed or Potentially Occurring at the BTC

Common Name	Scientific Name
Mammals	
American badger	<i>Taxidea taxus</i>
American elk	<i>Cervus elaphus</i>
Belding's ground squirrel	<i>Spermophilus beldingi</i>
Big brown bat*	<i>Eptesicus fuscus</i>
Black-tailed jackrabbit	<i>Lepus californicus</i>
Bobcat	<i>Lynx rufus</i>
Bushy-tailed wood rat	<i>Neotoma cinerea</i>
California myotis*	<i>Myotis californicus</i>
Coyote	<i>Canis latrans</i>
Deer mouse	<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>
Feral horse (I)	<i>Equus caballus</i>
Fringed myotis*	<i>Myotis thysanodes</i>
Golden-mantled ground squirrel*	<i>Spermophilus lateralis</i>
Great Basin pocket mouse	<i>Perognathus parvus</i>
Hoary bat*	<i>Lasiurus cinereus</i>
Least chipmunk	<i>Tamias minimus</i>
Long-eared myotis*	<i>Myotis evotis</i>
Long-legged myotis*	<i>M. velans</i>
Long-tailed vole*	<i>Microtus longicaudus</i>
Merriam shrew*	<i>Sorex merriami</i>
Montane vole	<i>Microtus montanus</i>
Mountain lion*	<i>Felis concolor</i>
Mule deer	<i>Odocoileus hemionus</i>
Northern grasshopper mouse	<i>Onychomys leucogaster</i>
Nuttall's cottontail	<i>Sylvilagus nuttalli</i>
Ord kangaroo rat	<i>Dipodomys ordi</i>
Pinyon mouse	<i>Peromyscus truei</i>
Porcupine	<i>Erethizon dorsatum</i>
Pronghorn antelope	<i>Antilocapra americana</i>
Pygmy rabbit*	<i>Brachylagus idahoensis</i>
Raccoon	<i>Procyon lotor</i>
Sagebrush vole	<i>Lemmyscus oregonus</i>
Silver-haired bat*	<i>Lasiurus noctivagus</i>
Small-footed myotis*	<i>Myotis californicus</i>
Striped skunk*	<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>
Townsend big-eared bat*	<i>Corynorhinus townsendii</i>
Townsend ground squirrel	<i>Spermophilus townsendii</i>
Western harvest mouse*	<i>Reithrodontomys megalotis</i>
Western spotted skunk*	<i>Spilogale gracilis</i>
White-tailed jackrabbit*	<i>Lepus townsendii</i>
Yellow-pine chipmunk	<i>Tamias amoenus</i>
Yuma myotis*	<i>Myotis yumanensis</i>
Amphibians	
Great Basin spadefoot toad	<i>Scaphiopus intermontanus</i>
Long-toed salamander*	<i>Ambystoma macrodactylum</i>
Oregon spotted frog*	<i>Rana pretiosa</i>
Pacific chorus frog	<i>Pseudacris regilla</i>
Western toad*	<i>Bufo boreas</i>

Table 3-3
Wildlife Species Observed or Potentially Occurring at the BTC (continued)

Common Name	Scientific Name
Reptiles	
Common garter snake	<i>Thamnophis sirtalis</i>
Desert short-horned lizard*	<i>Phrynosoma douglassii</i>
Gopher snake	<i>Pituophis catenifer</i>
Night snake*	<i>Hypsiglena torquata</i>
Northern sagebrush lizard*	<i>Sceloporus graciosus graciosus</i>
Racer snake*	<i>Coluber constrictor</i>
Rubber boa*	<i>Charina bottae</i>
Sagebrush lizard	<i>Sceloporus graciosus</i>
Side-blotched lizard*	<i>Uta stansburiana</i>
Southern alligator lizard*	<i>Elgaria multicarinata</i>
Striped whipsnake*	<i>Masticophis lateralis</i>
Western fence lizard	<i>Sceloporus occidentalis</i>
Western rattlesnake*	<i>Crotalus viridis</i>
Western skink	<i>Eumeces skiltonianus</i>
Western terrestrial garter snake*	<i>Thamnophis elegans</i>
Birds	
American coot	<i>Fulica americana</i>
American crow	<i>Corvus brachyrhynchos</i>
American kestrel	<i>Falco sparverius</i>
American robin	<i>Turdus migratorius</i>
American widgeon	<i>Anas americana</i>
Ash-throated flycatcher	<i>Myiarchus cinerascens</i>
Bald eagle*	<i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>
Barn swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>
Belted kingfisher	<i>Ceryle alcyon</i>
Black-billed magpie	<i>Pica pica</i>
Black-capped chickadee	<i>Parus atricapillus</i>
Black-throated gray warbler*	<i>Dendroica nigrescens</i>
Blue-winged teal	<i>Anas discors</i>
Bohemian waxwing*	<i>Bombycilla garrulus</i>
Brewer's blackbird	<i>Euphagus cyanocephalus</i>
Brewer's sparrow	<i>Spizella breweri</i>
Brown creeper*	<i>Certhia americana</i>
Brown-headed cowbird	<i>Molothrus ater</i>
Bufflehead	<i>Bucephala albeola</i>
Burrowing owl*	<i>Athene cunicularia</i>
California quail (I)	<i>Callipepla californica</i>
Canada goose	<i>Branta canadensis</i>
Cassin's finch*	<i>Carpodacus cassinii</i>
Cedar waxwing*	<i>Bombycilla cedrorum</i>
Chipping sparrow	<i>Spizella passerina</i>
Cinnamon teal	<i>Anas cyanoptera</i>
Clark's nutcracker*	<i>Nucifraga columbiana</i>
Cliff swallow*	<i>Hirundo pyrrhonota</i>
Common barn owl*	<i>Tyto alba</i>
Common bushtit	<i>Psaltriparus minimus</i>
Common merganser	<i>Mergus merganser</i>
Common nighthawk	<i>Chordeiles minor</i>

Table 3-3
Wildlife Species Observed or Potentially Occurring at the BTC (continued)

Common Name	Scientific Name
Common poorwill*	<i>Phalaenoptilus nuttallii</i>
Common raven	<i>Corvus corax</i>
Cooper's hawk*	<i>Accipiter cooperii</i>
Dark-eyed junco	<i>Junco hyemalis</i>
Dusky flycatcher	<i>Empidonax oberholseri</i>
European starling (I)	<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>
Evening grosbeak*	<i>Coccothraustes vespertina</i>
Fox sparrow	<i>Passerella iliaca</i>
Ferruginous hawk*	<i>Buteo regalis</i>
Gadwall	<i>Anas strepera</i>
Golden eagle	<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>
Golden-crowned sparrow	<i>Zonotrichia atricapilla</i>
Gray flycatcher	<i>Empidonax griseus</i>
Great blue heron	<i>Ardea herodias</i>
Great horned owl	<i>Bubo virginianus</i>
Green-tailed towhee*	<i>Pipilo chlorurus</i>
Hermit thrush*	<i>Catharus guttatus</i>
Horned lark*	<i>Eremophila alpestris</i>
House finch	<i>Carpodacus mexicanus</i>
House sparrow* (I)	<i>Passer domesticus</i>
House wren	<i>Troglodytes aedon</i>
Killdeer	<i>Charadrius vociferans</i>
Lark sparrow	<i>Chondestes grammacus</i>
Lazuli bunting*	<i>Passerina amoena</i>
Lesser scaup	<i>Aythya affinis</i>
Lincoln's sparrow*	<i>Melospiza lincolni</i>
Loggerhead shrike	<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>
Mallard	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>
Mountain bluebird	<i>Sialia sialis</i>
Mountain chickadee	<i>Parus gambeli</i>
Mourning dove	<i>Zenaidura macroura</i>
Northern flicker	<i>Colaptes auratus</i>
Northern harrier*	<i>Circus cyaneus</i>
Northern shrike	<i>Lanius excubitor</i>
Olive-sided flycatcher	<i>Contopus cooperi</i>
Osprey	<i>Pandion haliaetus</i>
Pine siskin*	<i>Carduelis pinus</i>
Pinyon jay	<i>Gymnorhinus cyanocephalus</i>
Plain titmouse*	<i>Parus inornatus</i>
Prairie falcon	<i>Falco mexicanus</i>
Purple finch	<i>Carpodacus purpureus</i>
Red crossbill*	<i>Loxia curvirostra</i>
Red-breasted nuthatch*	<i>Sitta canadensis</i>
Red-tailed hawk	<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>
Red-winged blackbird	<i>Agelaius phoeniceus</i>
Ring-necked duck	<i>Aythya collaris</i>
Rough-legged hawk*	<i>Buteo lagopus</i>
Rufous-sided towhee	<i>Pipilo erythrophthalmus</i>
Sage grouse*	<i>Centrocercus urophasianus</i>

Table 3-3
Wildlife Species Observed or Potentially Occurring at the BTC (continued)

Common Name	Scientific Name
Sage sparrow	<i>Amphispiza belli</i>
Sage thrasher	<i>Oreoscoptes montanus</i>
Say's phoebe	<i>Sayornis saya</i>
Sharp-shinned hawk*	<i>Accipiter striatus</i>
Song sparrow	<i>Melospiza melodia</i>
Spotted sandpiper	<i>Actitis macularia</i>
Swainson's hawk	<i>Buteo swainsoni</i>
Townsend's solitaire	<i>Myadestes townsendi</i>
Townsend's warbler*	<i>Dendroica townsendii</i>
Turkey vulture	<i>Cathartes aura</i>
Western bluebird	<i>Sialia mexicana</i>
Western burrowing owl*	<i>Atene curicularia hypuga</i>
Western kingbird	<i>Tyrannus verticalis</i>
Western meadowlark	<i>Sturnella neglecta</i>
Western scrub jay	<i>Apelocoma californica</i>
Western tanager	<i>Piranga ludoviciana</i>
Western wood-pewee*	<i>Contopus sordidulus</i>
White-crowned sparrow	<i>Zonotrichia leucophrys</i>
Willow flycatcher*	<i>Empidonax traillii</i>
Wilson's warbler*	<i>Wilsonia pusilla</i>
Yellow rail	<i>Coturnicops noveboracensis</i>
Yellow-rumped warbler	<i>Dendroica coronata</i>

Source: Kagan 1993; Reiher et al. 2000

Abbreviations: (I) = Introduced species; * = Species not observed but potentially occurs in the region.

Nonnative Species

Two bird species observed at the BTC during the 1999-2000 survey have been introduced to central Oregon from stocks. The California quail (*Callipepla californica*) was introduced in the 1940s and thrives only where natural or artificial water sources are available. This species is a primary food source for red-tailed hawk (*Buteo jamaicensis*) and other carnivores. The European starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*) was not introduced directly into Oregon but expanded into the state from introductions in the eastern US in the late 1800s. The starling competes with native species at the BTC, especially those avian species that depend on cavities for nest sites (Reiher et al. 2000). Thus, the starling is considered a pest species and could be considered a detriment to maintaining native species diversity and integrity at the BTC.

3.9.1 Wildlife Habitats

AR 200-3 requires Army habitat management efforts to be conducted in a manner that conserves and enhances biological diversity, while being consistent with Army goals to accomplish the military mission. AR 200-3 also requires that primary consideration be given to managing environmentally sensitive areas (US Army 1995). As it is Army and ORARNG policy to incorporate ecosystem management as the basis for managing habitats at the BTC, this INRMP uses a long-term view of human activities, including military uses, and biological resources as part of the same environment. To this end,

meeting the goals and objectives outlined in the wildlife management discussion (Section 5) would sustain the biological integrity of the BTC's habitats while maintaining the primary military mission.

As discussed in Section 3.7.1, vegetative communities typical of the High Lava Plains ecoregional province are found at the BTC, including such native species as western juniper, big sagebrush, bitterbrush, gray and green rabbitbrush, Idaho fescue, and bluebunch wheatgrass. Cheatgrass, introduced from Europe in the late 1800s, is also present. Ground cover and tree density vary from open grassland without trees to dense stands of western juniper. Juniper provide structure, shade, and browse for species such as pronghorn antelope, mule deer, and various birds. Sagebrush is important browse for mule deer, jackrabbits, ground squirrels and other rodents, and many species of birds. Bitterbrush and native grasses provide excellent forage for most of these species as well, especially pronghorn antelope. However, gray and green rabbitbrush are only lightly browsed by mule deer, and cheatgrass is considered fair forage only early in the growing season, having a low value for wildlife either as cover or forage by the middle of the growing season. In areas that have experienced heavy grazing or disturbance from off-road vehicles, plants less desirable as forage tend to proliferate. Thus, dense stands of gray and green rabbitbrush and cheatgrass could indicate the presence of these activities. In general, the BTC is coarsely defined as a homogeneous upland juniper shrub-steppe habitat with minor vegetative variations (Reiher et al. 2000).

The BTC maintains suitable habitat for a variety of native and nonnative wildlife species. The BTC is most likely part of a corridor used by a herd of 50 to 120 pronghorn antelope to migrate to and from breeding, fawning, and forage grounds throughout the year. The North Unit Main Canal is dry during winter, allowing antelope to travel and forage freely throughout the area.

A few (less than 10) feral horses use much of the same habitat as the antelope, although they are more likely to be encountered south of the BTC boundary. The feral horses escaped from private land and are of unknown ownership. They are not in the wild horse herd management area that BLM manages and, since they are not wild horses per the definition and guidelines of the Wild Free-Roaming Horse and Burro Act of 1971, they are not protected under the Act (Chaudet 2001, Pieratt 2001). Therefore, the feral horses are considered to be trespassing and will be removed from the public lands by the BLM to deter negative impacts to the environment or native species (BLM 2000). As a BLM action, the removal of the horses is beyond the authority of the ORARNG and, as such, outside the scope of this INRMP/EA.

Several species of myotis (i.e., bat) are likely to occur in the area of the BTC, but the 1999-2000 survey failed to detect any such species. No other surveys have been completed, and there are no known species of importance within the BTC. These mammalian species would likely use the North Unit Main Canal corridor for habitat, watering, and forage. Several lava blisters and lava caves within the confines of Training Area A have the greatest potential for use by myotis (i.e., bat) species.

3.10 SPECIAL STATUS SPECIES

The BTC has conducted species surveys as necessary to document threatened and endangered species and to identify potential habitat for such species (Kagan 1993; OMD 1995; Reiher et al. 2000; Sundberg 2000). The ESA is the primary federal law that protects special status species. The federal government categorizes species as listed (endangered or threatened), proposed, or candidate. USFWS previously maintained a list of federal species of concern. This category is no longer formally recognized; however, to evaluate potential future encumbrances, species of concern are included in this analysis.

No federal- or state-listed threatened or endangered plants, mammals, amphibians, reptiles, and fish or their associated habitats are known to exist at the BTC. No proposed or designated critical habitat exists at BTC (USFWS 2001). Several species of concern have the potential to be located within the region of the BTC and are described below.

Two species of plant are considered federal species of concern and threatened under state classification. Additionally, the ONHP ranks Peck's milk vetch (*Astragalus peckii*) and the pumice grape fern (*Botrychium pumicola*) as critically imperiled. Neither species is known to occur on or near the BTC.

Several mammalian species of concern could reside on or migrate through the BTC, most of which are myotis (i.e., bats). Should these species use the BTC for habitat and forage, they would likely be near the lava blisters and lava caves within Training Area A. Fauna surveys conducted during the 1999-2000 field season failed to identify actual species of myotis (i.e., bat), but several incidental sightings were noted (Reiher et al. 2000). The following species of myotis (i.e., bat) are considered federal species of concern: long-eared myotis (*Myotis evotis*), long-legged myotis (*Myotis volans*), small-footed myotis (*Myotis aliolabrum*), Townsend's big-eared bat (*Corynorhinus townsendii*), and the Yuma myotis (*Myotis yumanensis*). All of the above species have undetermined status by the state, except for Townsend's big-eared bat (state critical species) and the Yuma myotis (not classified as a species of concern by the state). Most of these species are considered rare but not imperiled under the ONHP classification. The fringed myotis (*Myotis thysanodes*) is not a federal species of concern but is considered vulnerable under state criteria. The silver-haired bat (*Lasiorycteris noctivagans*) is also not a federal species of concern but is listed by the state as undetermined due to lack of biological information. Both of these species are considered rare but not imperiled by the ONHP.

The pygmy rabbit (*Brachylagus idahoensis*) is a federal species of concern, considered vulnerable by the state, and classified as imperiled by the ONHP. The white-tailed jackrabbit (*Lepus townsendii*) is not a federal species of concern but is classified as undetermined by the state and as rare but not imperiled by the ONHP. These species have not been documented as residing on or migrating through the BTC during past wildlife surveys.

The only federal candidate species that could reside at the BTC is the Oregon spotted frog (*Rana pretiosa*). This amphibian is also a state species of concern and is listed as critically imperiled by the ONHP. Should this species be federally listed as either threatened or endangered and should its presence be detected at the BTC, specific management actions would need to be developed and implemented for its protection. Due to the lack of wetland resources at the BTC, it is not likely that this species inhabits the military training site.

Several sensitive avian species have been identified as either residing on or migrating through the BTC in past wildlife surveys. The bufflehead (*Bucephala albeola*), loggerhead shrike (*Lanius ludovicianus*), olive-sided flycatcher (*Cortopus borealis*), Swainson's hawk (*Buteo swainsonii*), and the yellow rail (*Coturnicops noveboracensis*) have been sighted at the BTC during breeding season. None of these species, except for the olive-sided flycatcher, is a federal species of concern. The only known state protected species that could be found at or near the BTC are the bald eagle (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*) and the yellow rail. The bald eagle has not been detected as using the BTC for forage, roost, or breeding habitat in past surveys. The yellow rail is listed as critically sensitive under state criteria and has been observed. Several federal species of concern could reside on or migrate through the BTC, but they have not been detected in previous wildlife surveys. They include the ferruginous hawk (*Buteo regalis*), western burrowing owl (*Athene cunicularia hypugae*), western sage grouse (*Centrocercus urophasianus phaeus*), and the willow flycatcher (*Empidonax traillii*).

Table 3-4 illustrates the status and presence at the BTC for threatened and endangered species and species of special concern that were identified by the USFWS, ODFW, and the ONHP.

3.11 CULTURAL RESOURCES

An Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan (ICRMP) is being developed by ORARNG concurrently with this INRMP (ORARNG 2001). The ICRMP covers all ORARNG facilities, including BTC. Approximately 43 percent of BTC has been surveyed for cultural resources. Prior to any soil disturbance or structure modification, these documents are consulted to determine the probability of disturbing any archaeological sites or historic properties that have traditional cultural or religious significance. The BTC's cultural resources management program complies with all federal and state statutes, EOs, DOD instructions and policies, and Army regulations.

3.11.1 Definition of Resource

Cultural resources include prehistoric resources, traditional cultural properties, and historic resources. Prehistoric resources are physical properties resulting from human activities that predate written records and are generally identified as isolated finds or sites. Prehistoric resources can include village sites, temporary camps, lithic scatters, roasting pits and hearths, milling features, petroglyphs, rock features, and burials.

Table 3-4
Special Status Species Inhabiting or Potentially Inhabiting the BTC

Common Name	Scientific Name	Federal/State/ ONHP Status	Presence on BTC
Plants			
Peck's milk vetch	<i>Astragalus peckii</i>	SOC/T/1	P
Pumice grape-fern	<i>Botrychium pumicola</i>	SOC/T/1	P
Mammals			
Fringed myotis	<i>Myotis thysanodes</i>	--/SV/3	P
Long-eared myotis	<i>M. evotis</i>	SOC/SU/4	P
Long-legged myotis	<i>M. volans</i>	SOC/SU/3	P
Pygmy rabbit	<i>Brachylagus idahoensis</i>	SOC/SV/2	P
Silver-haired bat	<i>Lasiorycteris noctivagans</i>	--/SU/3	P
Small-footed myotis	<i>Myotis californicus</i>	SOC/SU/3	P
Townsend's big-eared bat	<i>Corynorhinus townsendii</i>	SOC/SC/3	P
White-tailed jackrabbit	<i>Lepus townsendii</i>	--/SU/3	P
Yuma myotis	<i>Myotis yumanensis</i>	SOC/--/4	P
Amphibians			
Oregon spotted frog	<i>Rana pretiosa</i>	C/SOC/1	U
Western toad	<i>Bufo boreas</i>	--/SV/3	P
Reptiles			
Northern sagebrush lizard	<i>Sceloporus graciosus graciosus</i>	SOC/SV/4	P
Birds			
Bald eagle	<i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>	--/T/1	P
Bufflehead	<i>Bucephala albeola</i>	--/SU/2	C
Ferruginous hawk	<i>Buteo regalis</i>	SOC/SOC/3	P
Loggerhead shrike	<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>	--/SV/4	C
Olive-sided flycatcher	<i>Contopus borealis</i>	SOC/SV/3	C
Swainson's hawk	<i>Buteo swainsoni</i>	--/SV/3	C
Western burrowing owl	<i>Athene cunicularia hypugae</i>	SOC/SOC/3	P
Western sage grouse	<i>Centrocercus urophasianus phaios</i>	SOC/SV/3	P
Willow flycatcher	<i>Empidonax traillii</i>	--/SU/4	P
Yellow rail	<i>Coturnicops noveboracensis</i>	--/SC/2	C

Source: ONHP 2000

Notes:**Federal Status**

E = Endangered
T = Threatened
C = Candidate
SOC = Species of concern

State/ODFW Status

E = Endangered
T = Threatened
SOC = Species of concern
SC = Critical
SV = Vulnerable
SU = Undetermined

ONHP Status

1 = Critically imperiled
2 = Imperiled
3 = Rare
4 = Not rare

Presence on BTC

C = Confirmed
P = Possible
U = Unlikely

Traditional cultural properties are sites, locations, or features that are eligible for inclusion in the National Register of Historic Places (NRHP) because of their association with cultural practices or beliefs of a living community that are rooted in that community's history and that are important in maintaining the cultural identity of the community (Parker and King 1990). Examples include the following:

- A location associated with the traditional beliefs of a Native American group about its origins, its cultural history, or the nature of the world;

- A neighborhood that is the traditional home of a particular cultural group and that reflects its beliefs and practices;
- A location where Native American religious practitioners have historically gone and are known or thought to go today to perform ceremonial activities in accordance with traditional cultural rules of practice; and
- A location where a community has traditionally carried out economic, artistic, or other cultural practices important in maintaining its historical identity.

The ORARNG makes internal determinations as to whether a particular federal decision may have the potential to significantly affect protected tribal resources, tribal rights, or Indian Land. If it appears that there may be an effect, the appropriate Native American tribes would be contacted.

Historic resources consist of physical properties, structures, or built items resulting from human activities that post-date written record. Historic resources can include archaeological remains and architectural structures. Historic archaeological site types include townsites, homesteads, agricultural or ranching features, mining-related features, refuse concentrations, and features or artifacts associated with early pioneer and military use of the land. Historic architectural resources can include houses, cabins, barns, lighthouses, local structures, such as churches, post offices, and meeting halls, and early military structures, such as hangars, administration buildings, barracks, officers quarters, warehouses, and guardhouses.

Additional cultural resources include properties that are less than 50 years old that could be listed on the NRHP if they are of exceptional importance in our nation's history or if they are integral parts of districts that are eligible for the NRHP. On DOD facilities, these resources typically include properties associated with World War II or the Cold War. No resources of this nature occur at the BTC.

3.11.2 Regulatory Considerations

Cultural resources are protected primarily through the NHPA of 1966 and its implementing regulations (36 CFR 800), the Archaeological and Historic Preservation Act of 1974 (16 USC 469 - 469c), and the Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979 (16 USC 470aa - 470mm). Other regulatory considerations include EO 13007 (Indian Sacred Sites), the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act, the American Indian Religious Freedom Act of 1978, DOD Annotated American Indian and Alaska Native Policy, and others listed in Table 2-1.

Section 106 of the NHPA requires federal agencies to consider the effects of their actions on properties listed on or eligible for listing on the NRHP. Criteria for inclusion in the NRHP are provided in 36 CFR 60.4 and are summarized as follows:

- Association with events that have made a significant contribution to the broad patterns of our history;

- Association with the lives of persons significant in our past;
- Resources that embody the distinctive characteristics of a type, period, or method of construction or that represent the work of a master or that possess high artistic values or that represent a significant and distinguishable entity whose components could lack individual distinction; or
- Resources that have yielded or that could be likely to yield information important in prehistory or history.

In addition to historic significance, a property must have integrity to be eligible for the NRHP. Integrity is the property's ability to convey its demonstrated historical significance. Seven individual elements compose integrity—location, design, setting, materials, workmanship, feeling, and association.

3.11.3 Summary of Known Resources

Archaeological Resources

Eleven cultural resource surveys have been conducted at the BTC since 1983 and have examined a total of about 13,200 acres or 43 percent of the facility. The surveys documented 486 cultural resources: archaeological sites and isolates, rock features, and historic dumps, road alignments, and a historic canal. Five resources have been recommended as eligible for listing in the NRHP and 22 resources would require additional research to determine if they are NRHP-eligible properties. No inventories have been conducted to identify historic architectural properties, historic landscapes, or historic objects and monuments at the BTC. There are no agreement documents with State Historic Preservation Office (SHPO) or other parties regarding cultural resources at the BTC. However, the ICRMP being developed covers all ORARNG facilities, including BTC (ORARNG 2001).

Approximately 18,300 acres of the BTC remain to be surveyed. There are no locations that would need to be excluded from survey due to prior disturbance or safety hazards (ORARNG 2001).

The surveys documented 89 archaeological sites (both Native American and Euroamerican), 264 archaeological isolates (both Native American and Euroamerican), 78 rock features, 47 historic dumps, six historic road alignments, one historic monument, and one historic canal. The Oregon SHPO policy is that archaeological isolates are usually not eligible for listing on the NRHP, and none of the isolates at the BTC warrants exemption from that policy. The historic dumps and rock features have also been recommended as not eligible for listing on the NRHP. All of the recorded Native American archaeological sites appear to consist of lithic scatters. Testing at a small sample of these sites has indicated that the site deposits are shallow or limited to the surface. As a result, 64 of these sites (73 percent) have been determined not eligible for the NRHP. Of the remaining 25, one has been recommended as potentially eligible, three have been recommended as eligible, and 21 have not been evaluated. Of the six

identified wagon roads, portions of five have been recommended as not eligible and one (the Horner Road) is recommended as eligible (Table 3-5). The North Unit Main Canal was determined to not be eligible for the NRHP in 1991 as it was not 50 years old at that time. Table 3-5 lists the historic resources at the BTC that are either eligible or potentially eligible for the NRHP (ORARNG 2001).

Traditional Cultural Properties

Preliminary consultations with the appropriate tribes (as described in Section 1.8.4) have not identified any Native American issues specific to the BTC.

Historic Archaeological Sites

Surface and subsurface archaeological sites of historic significance have not been observed at the BTC, and the potential for intact subsurface historic deposits is considered low.

Historic Architectural Resources

No historic structures that would qualify for listing on the NHRP have been identified at the BTC. The military training site lacks structural improvements predating the Cold War era (post-1945); therefore, there are no standing structures at the BTC that are 50 years old or older. Evidence of the World War II training base at Roberts Field is on city of Redmond airport property, just west of the COUTES facility. Additionally, the BTC does not appear to have made an exceptional contribution to the national Cold War program but rather functioned as part of the vast support complex. The mission and accomplishments at BTC during the Cold War era were routine rather than exceptional. "Exceptional importance" is a measure of a property's importance within the appropriate historic context, whether the scale of that context is local, state, or national (NPS 1991). The ICRMP did not identify any properties or issues of "exceptional contribution" under criteria G, "Properties That Have Achieved Significance within the Last Fifty Years," for ORARNG facilities, which include the BTC.

3.12 AIR QUALITY

3.12.1 Existing Sources of Air Emissions

The federal Clean Air Act (CAA), as amended, authorizes the EPA to establish national ambient air quality standards to protect public health and welfare. Federal ambient air quality standards have been adopted for the following six criteria pollutants: ozone, carbon monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide, inhalable and fine particulate matter (PM_{10} and $PM_{2.5}$), and lead. States are required to adopt standards that are at least as stringent as the national standards; Oregon has adopted the national ambient air quality standards, with the exception of sulfur dioxide, for which stricter standards have been adopted.

Areas that violate a federal air quality standard are designated as nonattainment. Nonattainment designations for ozone, carbon monoxide, and PM_{10} include

**Table 3-5
Biak Training Center Historic Resources that are Eligible for the NRHP**

Resource Name	Historic Context	NRHP Status
Horner Road (1908)	historic	eligible
35DS174	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS175	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS176	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS179	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS180	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS181	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS182	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS183	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS184	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS185	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS186	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS187	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS188	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS189	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS190	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS191	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS192	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS559	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS982	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS983	prehistoric	potentially eligible
35DS984	prehistoric	eligible
OR-05-511 (H)	historic	potentially eligible
OR-05-516 (H)	historic	potentially eligible
OR-05-865 (H)	historic	potentially eligible
OR-05-866 (H)	historic	potentially eligible
06-009 (Temp. No.)	historic	eligible
06-022 (Temp. No.)	historic	eligible

Source: ORARNG 2001.

subcategories indicating the severity of the air quality problem. Areas that comply with federal air quality standards are designated as attainment areas. Areas that have been reclassified from nonattainment to attainment are designated as attainment/maintenance areas. Areas that lack monitoring data to demonstrate attainment or nonattainment status are designated as unclassified areas and are treated as attainment areas for various regulatory purposes. Deschutes and Crook counties are attainment/unclassified for all of the federal ambient air quality standards. Vehicles and fugitive dust are the primary sources of air emissions at the BTC.

3.12.2 Regulatory Considerations

The federal CAA requires each state to develop, adopt, and implement a State Implementation Plan (SIP) to achieve, maintain, and enforce federal air quality standards throughout the state. SIP documents are developed on a pollutant-by-pollutant basis whenever one or more air quality standards are being violated.

Section 176(c) of the CAA, USC § 7506(c), requires federal agencies to ensure that actions undertaken in nonattainment or maintenance areas are consistent with the CAA

Section 176(c) of the CAA, USC § 7506(c), requires federal agencies to ensure that actions undertaken in nonattainment or maintenance areas are consistent with the CAA and with federally enforceable air quality management plans. The EPA has promulgated separate rules that establish conformity analysis procedures for transportation-related actions and for other (general) federal agency actions. The EPA general conformity rule applies to federal actions occurring in nonattainment or maintenance areas when the total direct and indirect emissions of nonattainment pollutants (or their precursors) exceed specified thresholds. The emission thresholds that trigger requirements of the conformity rule are called de minimis levels. The CAA conformity guidelines do not apply to the BTC because it is within an attainment/unclassified area.

3.13 NOISE

3.13.1 Noise Level Criteria and Standards

Noise Management

Sound travels through the air in waves of minute air pressure fluctuations caused by some type of vibration. Sound level meters are designed to detect these sound waves and to register different sound frequency ranges on a logarithmic decibel (dB) scale. Because the human ear is not equally sensitive to all frequencies, an "A-weighted" decibel scale (dBA) is commonly used to represent the response of the human ear.

Average noise exposure over a 24-hour period often is presented as a day-night average noise level (DNL). DNL values are calculated from 24-hour averages in which nighttime values (10 PM to 7 AM) are increased by 10 dB to account for the greater disturbance potential from nighttime noises.

Federal Agency Guidelines

The federal Noise Control Act of 1972 (42 USC §§ 4901 - 4918 [1999]) established a requirement that all federal agencies must comply with applicable federal, state, interstate, and local noise control regulations. Local and state agencies have no applicable authority over military aircraft operations. Federal agencies also were directed to administer their programs in a manner that promotes an environment free from noise that jeopardizes public health or welfare. EO 13045 (62 Federal Register 19885) establishes a requirement that federal agencies identify, assess, and address the extent to which agency programs and activities create disproportionate environmental health and safety risks for children.

State Agency Guidelines

State noise standards and guidelines include airport noise standards, guidelines for noise elements of general plans, and noise insulation standards for hotels, motels, and new multiple unit residential developments. The Oregon Department of Environmental Quality (ODEQ) regulates noise control under ORS Chapter 467.

Local Guidelines and Criteria

Crook County does not maintain any county noise control ordinances. Deschutes County maintains a county noise control ordinance under Ordinance 203.11 §§ 1, 1980, (also codified as Chapter 8.08) as pursuant to the provisions outlined under ORS 467. Chapter 8.08 identifies and defines unreasonably loud or raucous noises that could adversely affect the public peace, health, safety, and general welfare of county residents. As noise at the BTC results from the military activity to protect the citizens of Oregon from hostile forces and to maintain public order and safety during emergency situations, the training activities are exempt from regulations outlined in Chapter 8.08.

3.13.2 Existing Noise Conditions**Sensitive Noise Receptors**

Sensitive noise receptors include residences, schools, libraries, hospitals, and other similar land uses where people generally expect and need a quiet environment. On-site sensitive noise receptors include the private property in-holdings within the BLM's boundaries for the BTC. Off-site sensitive receptors include residential areas immediately west and south of the BTC.

Area Noise Sources

There are no permanent noise sources at the BTC, and all-terrain military vehicles and the baffled small-arms firing range are the only intermittent sources of concern. Sound levels in the vicinity of the military training site are generally low, and aircraft operations from Roberts Field, intermittent all-terrain vehicle use, highway traffic, and reports from the baffled small-arms firing range are the major contributors to noise in the vicinity of the BTC.

3.14 PUBLIC HEALTH AND SAFETY

Specific elements concerning the public health and safety management program at the BTC include wildfire control, dust abatement, and potential accidents involving military all-terrain vehicles, public all-terrain vehicles, and livestock. The Annex outlines specific procedures that military personnel follow in the event of a public health and safety concern (BTC 1999). Using the concept of risk management, the BTC ensures not only the physical safety of military personnel and public land users, but the integrity of natural resources and personal property as well. The risk management concept used by the BTC is integrated into the decision-making process by identifying and assessing potential hazards, developing means of control to such hazards, determining residual risks, and implementing mitigation controls.

3.14.1 Hazardous Materials and Hazardous Waste

As defined by the Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation, and Liability Act (CERCLA) of 1980, PL 96-510, as amended (42 USC §§ 9601 - 9675), and the Superfund Amendments and Reauthorization Act (SARA) of 1986, a hazardous material is a substance, pollutant, or contaminant that, due to its quantity, concentration, or physical or chemical characteristics, poses a potential hazard to

human health and safety or to the environment if released into the workplace or the environment.

The Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA) of 1976, PL 94-580 (42 USC §§ 6901 - 6992k), as amended by the Hazardous and Solid Waste Amendments (HSWA) of 1984, PL 98-616, defines a hazardous waste as a solid waste or combination of wastes that, due to its quantity, concentration, or physical, chemical, or infectious characteristics, could cause or significantly contribute to an increase in mortality or an increase in serious irreversible or incapacitating reversible illness or could pose a substantial present or future hazard to human health or the environment when improperly treated, stored, disposed of, or otherwise managed. A solid waste is a hazardous waste if it is not excluded from regulation as a hazardous waste, if it exhibits any ignitable, corrosive, reactive, or toxic characteristic, or if it is listed in Subpart D of RCRA.

RCRA requires that hazardous wastes be managed through a recordkeeping system that requires manifesting properly labeled hazardous shipments from point of generation to ultimate disposal. Also required by federal law are proper labeling, storage, containerization, training, and emergency procedures for hazardous waste.

ORARNG Regulation 210-6 describes responsibilities of military personnel in planning for and responding to spills of regulated substances to the environment. Additionally, ORARNG Regulation 420-47 outlines guidance for managing hazardous materials and disposing of hazardous waste generated on ORARNG facilities in accordance with federal and state regulations. Hazardous materials are used for military activities involving vehicular maneuvers at the BTC in support of the military mission and are handled, stored, and transported in accordance with EPA, Occupational Safety and Health Administration, US Department of Transportation, state, and Army requirements. Hazardous materials used on-site can include petroleum, oils, and lubricants (POL), antifreeze, brake, hydraulic, and transmission fluids, acids, caustic materials, and pesticides. These materials are used at the locations detailed below.

Storage Tanks and Fuel

Aboveground storage tanks (AST) are used to store hazardous substances and petroleum products at the BTC, specifically diesel fuel and JP-8 fuel for military vehicles. There are no known underground storage tanks at the BTC.

Ordnance and Explosives

No ordnance or explosives are stored at the BTC. Training units are responsible for supplying and transporting blank or live ammunition from off-site locations for use at the COUTES small-arms baffled firing range. Ammunition is removed from the BTC when the training exercise is completed.

3.14.2 Wildfire Control

Military training exercises performed on public lands managed by the BLM are considered equivalent to an industrial use and, as such, are subject to the provisions

outlined under the BLM's Timber Sale Contract 5450-3, Sections 15 and 41, and stipulations in the current Industrial Fire Precautions Level (Wortman 1999). In order to receive a waiver from these provisions, the BTC keeps a fire-fighting vehicle able to perform to BLM-approved standards during all military training exercises. In addition, the BTC adheres to the stipulations outlined in AR 420-90, *Fire and Emergency Services*.

Unlike active military installations that have intensive ground training and live-fire components, there are few activities at the BTC that generate fire hazards (e.g., live ammunition and flares). However, there are activities at the BTC that generate fire hazards from spark emissions (e.g., firing blank ammunition and using pyrotechnics, such as smoke grenades, artillery simulators, and aerial flares). According to BLM guidelines, the BTC maintains a crew of seasonally trained and equipped wildfire-fighting personnel during military training exercises; however, the crew is not trained or available to fight structural fires. The fire crews are not maintained during the low fire season (all months other than June, July, August, and September).

Fire is a natural part of the western juniper/big sagebrush vegetative community that composes most of the BTC ecosystem and is one of the primary processes driving compositional and structural changes in this ecosystem (Jones 2000). Without disturbance such as fire, shrub abundance could decline and junipers could gain dominance. This scenario could result in the overall decline in herbaceous production, especially understory grasses and shrubs that provide forage for wildlife and livestock. The BLM estimates that the natural fire interval for the BTC is 16 years (BLM 1989).

The BTC lacks a program to implement prescribed burns. Although using prescribed burns could benefit wildlife habitat and forage, invasive weeds, such as cheatgrass, respond well to fire, potentially resulting in a negative impact on native perennial species (Reiher et al. 2000). Furthermore, the BLM has evaluated BTC public lands for potential damage to resource values by fire. The BLM has categorized these public lands as the lowest value at risk (BLM 1989). Values at risk are the basis for determining fire suppression action. The fire management goals and objectives of the BTC, therefore, are focused on providing for the safety of military personnel and the public in the event of fire.

3.14.3 Dust Abatement

In addition to being a nuisance, dust is a public health and safety hazard because it reduces visibility and increases the risk to nearby aircraft operations. Dust also can negatively affect the military mission by clogging equipment and hampering training exercises.

Blowing dust is frequent at the BTC due to the semiarid climate, pumice soil conditions, and local wind patterns. Vegetative cover aids in preventing wind erosion and dust. As with all safety issues, minimizing this risk is a primary objective under the risk-management plan implemented by the BTC and outlined in the Annex (BTC 1999).

3.15 SOCIOECONOMIC RESOURCES

3.15.1 Definition of Resource

Socioeconomics includes data on population, employment, income, housing, earnings, and schools. Population includes the number of residents in the area and the recent change in population growth. Employment data includes labor sectors, labor force, and statistics on unemployment. Income information is provided as an annual total by county and as per capita income. Housing includes numbers of multifamily units, single-family homes, and mobile homes and their vacancy rate. Earnings-by-industry provides a measure of the health of local business activity. School enrollment and capacity are important considerations in assessing the effects of potential growth.

3.15.2 Affected Area

The affected socioeconomic area for the BTC includes Crook and Deschutes counties. The affected area was selected based on the assumption that most base personnel commute to work from and spend dollars in one or both of the two counties.

Both Crook and Deschutes counties are in central Oregon. Crook County is surrounded by Jefferson and Wheeler counties to the north, Wheeler County to the east, Harney County to the southeast, and Deschutes County to the west and southwest. Prineville is the only incorporated city in Crook County, and it is the county seat. Deschutes County is surrounded by Jefferson County to the north, Crook County to the east, Harney County to the southeast, Lake and Klamath counties to the south, Lane County to the west, and Linn County to the northwest. The three incorporated cities in Deschutes County are Sisters, Redmond, and Bend. The three unincorporated cities in Deschutes County are Terrebonne, Deschutes River Woods, and Three Rivers. Bend is the Deschutes County seat.

Population

The population in the affected area totaled approximately 134,549 in 2000, representing an increase of over 50 percent from the 1990 population (Table 3-6). Deschutes County has continued to be more populated than Crook County, consistent with its greater number of incorporated cities, and grew by a higher percentage than Crook County between 1990 and 2000. Deschutes County grew by 53.9 percent, while Crook County grew by 35.9 percent. In 1997, the population density was approximately 5.7 persons per square mile in Crook County and 33.6 persons per square mile in Deschutes County, which covers a slightly larger land area.

Employment

Between 1993 and 1997, total employment in Crook and Deschutes counties increased by approximately 20 percent. The greatest increase was in the services sector; however, this was offset by slight decreases in manufacturing, wholesale trade, federal civilian, and military employment. State and local employment in Crook and Deschutes counties also increased by an estimated 20 percent (US Bureau of Economic Analysis 2000a and 2000d).

Table 3-6
Population, Crook and Deschutes Counties

	Crook County	Deschutes County	Total
1990	14,111	74,958	89,069
1992	15,110	84,234	99,344
1997	16,958	101,367	118,325
2000	19,182	115,367	134,549
Change 1990 to 2000 (percent)	35.9	53.9	51.1

Sources: City and County Data Book 1994; US Bureau of Economic Analysis 2000b and 2000e; US Census Bureau 2001a and 2001b.

In 1996, the civilian labor force for Crook County totaled 7,796, and 904 people were unemployed (11.6 percent unemployment rate). The unemployment rate was 7.5 percent for 1994, an increase of 0.4 percent from 1990. In Deschutes County, the civilian labor force equaled 53,534 in 1996, and 4,554 persons were unemployed (8.5 percent unemployment rate). The combined unemployment rate for the affected area in 1996 was 8.9 percent (US Bureau of Labor Statistics 1998a and 1998b).

Income

In 1999, the per capita personal income for the affected area was \$23,623, an increase of 48 percent over the 1989 income. In Crook County, the average per capita income was \$21,168 in 1999; in Deschutes County, the per capita personal income was \$26,077 in 1999 (US Bureau of Economic Analysis 2001a and 2001b).

Housing

The affected area had 58,885 housing units in 1998. There were 7,776 units in Crook County and 51,109 units in Deschutes County. In each county, approximately 70 percent of the housing is single-family units. Mobile homes make up about 25 percent of the Crook County housing stock, whereas they form slightly less than 20 percent of the Deschutes County housing stock. Apartments, condominiums, duplexes, triplexes, and townhouses compose the remaining small percentage of the housing stock in both counties. Slightly more than 80 percent of housing in Crook County is owner-occupied, while about 75 percent of housing in Deschutes County is owner-occupied. Rental vacancy rates in central Oregon are declining, and the volume of sales has been growing in Deschutes and Crook counties. The growth in sales in 1998 in Deschutes County of 18.8 percent reflects a substantial increase over a relatively large number of transactions from the previous year. The 18.8 percent rate of growth shown for 1999 in Crook County is based on a relatively small volume of sales in 1998 (Reese Consulting, Inc. 2000).

Earnings by Industry

Earnings by persons employed in Crook and Deschutes counties increased from \$921,422,000 in 1989 to \$2,021,313,000 in 1999, an increase of 83.8 percent. The

largest industries in 1999 were service, government, manufacturing, retail trade, and construction (US Bureau of Economic Analysis 2001a and 2001b). Between 1991 and 1997 farm earnings declined for the area by 130.7 percent, but in 1990 and 1991 Deschutes County had positive farm earnings of \$597,000 and \$798,000, respectively (US Bureau of Economic Analysis 2000c and 2000f).

Schools

Crook County has one school district with seven schools serving approximately 2,990 students. Three elementary schools, a middle school, and one high school are in Prineville. The additional two elementary schools are in Paulina and Powell Butte (NCES 2000).

Deschutes County is divided into five school districts: Bend-La Pine School District, Brothers School District, Crook-Deschutes Regional Education Service Agency, Redmond School District, and Sisters School District. The Bend-La Pine School District, the largest in Deschutes County, is composed of 12 elementary schools, four middle schools, and four high schools, serving approximately 12,363 students. The Brothers School District is an independent local rural district and is the smallest in the county, serving only nine students with one elementary school. The Crook-Deschutes Regional Education Service Agency operates the Cascade Child Treatment Center in Redmond, with an enrollment of 14. The Redmond School District has an enrollment of approximately 5,461 students in its six elementary schools, two middle schools, one high school, and the Brown Education Center for Pre-kindergarten students. The Sisters School District contains one elementary school, one middle school, and one high school, to serving approximately 1,136 students (NCES 2000).

3.16 ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

This section addresses specific topics related to environmental justice, as required by NEPA. Specifically, a discussion of issues related to environmental justice are presented in accordance with EO 12898, and issues related to protecting children from environmental health risks are presented in accordance with EO 13045.

3.16.1 Executive Order 12898

On February 11, 1994, President Clinton issued EO 12898, entitled "Federal Actions to Address Environmental Justice in Minority and Low-income Populations." This order requires that "each federal agency make achieving environmental justice part of its mission by identifying and addressing, as appropriate, disproportionately high and adverse human health or environmental effects of its programs, policies, and activities, on minority populations and low-income populations" (EO 12898, 59 FR 7629 [Section 1-101]). On April 21, 1995, the Secretary of Defense submitted a formal environmental justice strategy and implementation plan to the EPA. To comply with the order, the following actions have occurred concurrently with this INRMP:

- Gathered economic, racial, and demographic information generated from the 1990 census to identify areas of low income and high minority populations in and around the BTC;

- Assessed the alternatives for disproportionate impacts resulting from on-site activities associated with the proposed action; and
- Encouraged community participation in and input from public agencies through meetings and public notification of the draft document, as identified in Sections 1.8 and 1.9.

Existing Demographics

Regional trends indicate that the population of Hispanic residents from all races in Crook and Deschutes counties has increased slightly (approximately 1.4 percent) between 1990 and 1999. The racial/ethnic composition of both counties has remained predominantly white (around 98 percent in both 1990 and 1999) (Oregon Office of Economic Analysis 1999).

The statistics on poverty indicate that between 1990 and 1995 poverty in Crook County increased by slightly more than three percent; in Deschutes County the population in poverty decreased by slightly less than three percent. According to the 1998 State of Oregon Population Survey for the region in which these counties are located (which also includes adjacent Jefferson County), 3.7 percent of the respondent population had incomes below the poverty line (Clearwater Research 1999; Oregon State University Extension Service 1999).

3.16.2 Executive Order 13045

EO 13045, entitled "Protection of Children from Environmental Health Risks and Safety Risks" (EO 13045, 62 FR 19885), states that each federal agency shall make it a high priority to identify and assess environmental health risks and safety risks that could disproportionately affect children and ensure that its policies, programs, activities, and standards address disproportionate risks to children that result from environmental health risks or safety risks. Environmental health risks and safety risks mean risks to health or to safety that are attributable to products or substances that the child is likely to come into contact with or to ingest.

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SECTION 4

EXISTING MANAGEMENT PROGRAMS AND INITIATIVES

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This section provides a brief overview of existing management plans and programs in place at the BTC. Applicable components of these plans have been integrated into this INRMP and support the goals, objectives, and management strategies presented in Section 5.

4.2 NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

Natural resources at the BTC are managed by the BLM under the guidelines outlined in the *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989). The BLM plan emphasizes production on a sustained yield basis and use of the renewable resources on most public lands in the planning area and for the multiple use of these lands. There are a number of important natural resource issues being managed by the BLM within the BTC. These include the following:

- Livestock grazing and permitting;
- Public access and recreation;
- Off-road vehicles;
- Wildlife;
- Fire control;
- Vegetation and forestry; and
- Historic properties.

The *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989) meets federal guidance, satisfies the planning criteria of the BLM, is consistent with other federal, state, local,

and tribal management plans, and effectively resolves issues while contributing to the local economy (BLM 1989).

The BTC implements natural resources management, where directed or necessary, under the direction of the BLM and ORARNG in compliance with federal, state, and military laws, regulations, and guidelines. Cooperation with and adherence to policies developed by the BLM is necessary for the sound implementation of the natural resources management strategies outlined in this document.

4.3 LAND USE PLANNING

Land use planning at the BTC is guided by the *Real Property Development Plan: Central Oregon Training Site* (ORARNG 1999d) and Range and Training Land Program Development Plan for the BTC (ORARNG 2000c). The development plan provides a summary of the existing infrastructure, facilities, and improved structures used by the ORARNG at the BTC. The development plan identifies short-term and long-term management techniques for maintaining the physical integrity of these improvements.

4.4 INTEGRATED TRAINING AREA MANAGEMENT

ITAM is a management approach that seeks to match military mission requirements with the long-term ecological integrity of military training sites. The Army and the Army National Guard have embraced this approach and are implementing it on their installations and training areas. The goal of ITAM is to achieve and sustain the optimum use of training lands to support training and mission requirements indefinitely, while ensuring protection of natural resources. ITAM is composed of four components that should be implemented as a whole in order to meet its overall goal. A synopsis of the four components is provided below.

Land Condition-Trend Analysis

As discussed in Section 3.7.3, LCTA is long-term ecological monitoring. It includes natural resource inventories, field data collection, and data analysis. Ecological field methods and modern technological devices/products (e.g., geographic information systems, global positioning systems, remote imagery) are used. The purpose of LCTA is to identify adverse impacts and support decision-making related to training activities and natural resource management projects. It also seeks to define the carrying capacity of land units for military training. The LCTA program was implemented at the BTC during the summer of 1999 to inventory baseline flora conditions and disturbance on the military training site. Section 3.7.3 discusses LCTA in more detail.

Training Requirements Integration

Training Requirements Integration (TRI) uses LCTA information and Army training requirements to select appropriate training sites for units requesting training, and for the placement of training facilities. It applies the carrying capacity concept and seeks to minimize adverse impacts to training lands. TRI mandates a high level of coordination between operations, range control, engineering, and environmental staffs.

Land Rehabilitation and Maintenance

LRAM is the planning, design, and implementation of projects to maintain the environmental condition of training lands. These projects should be based on LCTA information and priorities derived through the ITAM process. Although LRAM often focuses on repairing military damage, the goal is to maintain training areas in an acceptable condition to support realistic training opportunities. Official ITAM-funded LRAM projects were started at the BTC in fiscal year 2000, but land rehabilitation work has been done for approximately the past 15 years.

Environmental Awareness

Environmental awareness involves using educational opportunities and materials to help the land user understand the impacts of their action. This applies to training site staff and units conducting training, although these materials are also valuable to others interested in the site. Examples include awareness briefings and videos, posters, and instructional field cards. The first ITAM-funded environmental awareness project at the BTC was started in fiscal year 2000, but soldiers have been briefed on environmental issues for over 15 years.

4.5 ENVIRONMENTAL COMPLIANCE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

The Environmental Compliance Assessment System (ECAS) program assists all Army commanders in attaining, sustaining, and monitoring compliance with federal, state, and local environmental laws and regulations, as well as DOD and Army requirements. The ECAS external and internal multimedia assessments identify noncompliance and deficiencies, suggest immediate and long-term corrective actions, and indicate resources needed for implementation. Military training site commanders, including those at the BTC, use environmental compliance assessments, in combination with regulatory agency inspections and sound day-to-day environmental management procedures, as a means of attaining, sustaining, and monitoring compliance with applicable environmental regulations.

4.6 CULTURAL RESOURCES

The ORARNG ICRMP (ORARNG 2001) has been developed in accordance with the requirements outlined in AR 200-4 to support the military mission and to meet the legal requirements of federal historic preservation laws and regulations in a manner consistent with the sound principles of cultural resources stewardship (US Army 1998). The ICRMP establishes priorities for identifying and standards for evaluating historic properties on ORARNG facilities and provides a schedule for accomplishing program objectives.

Approximately 43 percent of the BTC has been surveyed for archaeological resources. The ICRMP has determined that one prehistoric archaeological site, one historic roadway, and two historic archaeological sites at the BTC are eligible for listing on the NRHP. The ICRMP requires the ORARNG to develop an agreement document with the BLM to define respective cultural resource responsibilities. Additionally, those portions of the BTC that have not been previously surveyed for cultural resources and

that are areas designated for all-terrain vehicular maneuvers will be surveyed in a timely manner.

4.7 VEGETATION MONITORING

A vegetation monitoring protocol has been prepared for the BTC in accordance with the Army's LCTA program. The monitoring protocol is an important tool that helps natural resource managers organize, design, and evaluate vegetative data collection and analysis efforts. It provides detailed information about natural resources and associated management concerns, management objectives and their corresponding monitoring objectives, monitoring methodologies and data collection procedures, data management, quality control, and storage, and data analysis and interpretation. It also contains site-specific information about sampling locations and plots, photographs, and other remotely sensed data (Jones 2000).

The LCTA monitoring program ensures that monitoring goals are well defined, prioritized, and cost effective and that scientific standards and statistical rigors are appropriate to the natural resources. It also helps to maximize efficiency and to provide continuity for monitoring programs by providing a legacy that will remain in effect regardless of variable program funding or potential staff turnover.

In order for the LCTA program to capture changes in natural resource quality and quantity due to land use activities, the monitoring program is viewed as a long-term undertaking that documents the inherent variability due to natural processes and events, as well as changes caused by different management activities and land uses, including disturbance by military and public all-terrain vehicles and livestock grazing. The vegetative monitoring objectives that would likely be determined in using the *Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site* (Jones 2000) include the following:

- An overview of the status of major ecological communities of interest;
- Management concerns and potential threats;
- Documentation of the sampling design, sampling locations, and methodologies for data collection and analysis; and
- Short-term and long-term schedule for monitoring activities.

4.8 PUBLIC HEALTH AND SAFETY

The Annex provides information pertaining to the policies and procedures to be followed by military personnel in the event of a medical, fire, or hazardous materials incident at the BTC (BTC 1999). The Annex provides safety and risk management information to help train military personnel in mitigating hazards and to improve overall safety during training. In the event of an actual or true emergency, the Annex outlines incident-specific guidance on how to contact the proper military or civilian authorities whose assistance is required to safely effect rescue and medical evacuation, fire suppression, hazardous spill containment, and law enforcement assistance.

The Annex is divided into four distinct sections. The first section provides the user with the BTC Commander's policy statement, along with command information. The second section provides general safety and risk management to the user. Because the BTC operates on public land and in cooperation with several public agencies with overlapping responsibility for emergency incidents, the third section provides a brief overview of the geographic location systems in use in central Oregon and the civilian incident command structure that military personnel might encounter during an emergency. The fourth section establishes the standard operating procedures for all fire and emergency service incidents at the BTC.

4.9 HAZARDOUS MATERIALS AND WASTE MANAGEMENT

Hazardous materials and wastes must be transported, stored, and disposed of according to federal and military standards. To this end, the ORARNG has completed a statewide Hazardous Waste Management Plan (ORARNG 1999b) and Installation Spill Contingency Plan (ORARNG 1998). These military regulations, described in detail in Appendix D (Section D.1.4), are implemented at the BTC in full compliance with federal and military regulations. With the exception of those chemicals used to control identified noxious weeds and pests, all hazardous materials and waste used or created in the management of the BTC are transported to approved receiving facilities for storage or disposal.

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SECTION 5

NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT APPROACH

5.1 ECOSYSTEM MANAGEMENT CONCEPT

This INRMP was developed on the ecosystem approach, in accordance with DOD, DA, NGB, and ORARNG policy. As defined by the DOD, the goal of ecosystem management is to “ensure that military lands support present and future training and testing requirements while preserving, improving, and enhancing ecosystem integrity” (DOD 1996). However, given the fact that the public lands that compose the BTC are managed by the BLM and not the ORARNG, the management provisions of this plan have been modified to ensure that management actions are consistent with the overall land use goals of the BLM and its mandate to provide for multiple use of the natural resources under its supervision. With this in mind, the ecosystem approach will be applied to the management strategies of this plan in an effort to ensure that the public lands of the BTC provide for sustained military training and readiness. This approach also encourages sound environmental stewardship.

The ecosystem management approach focuses on the ecological system instead of a single species or single resource. Thus, a natural resource is not viewed as a thing or an object but as a function that a thing or an object can perform or as an operation in which it can take part within the system (Zimmerman 1951). The art of ecosystem management is managing the system to maximize the functions of resources for predetermined desired conditions. Before one can implement ecosystem management, two inherent rules must be understood. First, natural ecosystems are incredibly complex and our understanding of them is limited (Leslie et al. 1996). Second, unlike tangible objects (e.g., trees), resources (e.g., timber) change in response to ecological, social, and institutional events, including changes in the following:

- Societal tastes and values;
- Knowledge;
- Technology;

- Laws and institutions; and
- The ecosystem (Salazar and Lee 1990).

Thus, the greatest impediment to effective ecosystem management is uncertainty. To mitigate uncertainty, the BTC will implement adaptive management.

Leslie et al. (1996) describe the heart of adaptive management as a willingness to approach all management decisions as experiments to be tested. Instead of prescribing an inflexible management scenario, an adaptive management plan tests possible solutions to problems in a scientifically sound, experimental fashion. Adaptive management recognizes that there is incomplete data when dealing with natural resources and that through continued research and monitoring of the effects of management practices, new information will be developed. This information can be reevaluated and incorporated into the management plan, and practices can be adjusted accordingly (Noss and Cooperider 1994). According to an adaptive management prescription, goals, local knowledge, technologies, and resource inventories make up the adaptive management plan. The plan is implemented and its effectiveness is evaluated using monitoring protocols. Revised goals, new local knowledge, updated inventories, and new technologies could be the result at the end of the evaluation process. These new elements are integrated into the management plan, and the process repeats itself. This adaptive management process is illustrated in Figure 5-1.

Figure 5-1
Adaptive Management Strategy

5.2 GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PROGRAM

The two overall goals of the INRMP are: 1) to provide a means for managing the natural resources at the BTC to sustain military readiness; and 2) to comply with all applicable federal mandates. A number of general objectives to achieve this goal have been developed and have been reviewed by the BLM, USFWS, and ODFW. These objectives are as follows:

- Ensure no net loss in the capability of the land and natural resources at the BTC to support the military mission;
- Ensure compliance with applicable laws and regulations as they pertain to natural resources;
- Enhance the level of biodiversity within the constraints of the military mission;
- Implement adaptive management techniques to provide flexible and responsive management strategies, based on scientific data gathered from monitoring programs, literature, and resource experts;
- Protect and enhance the quality of habitat for threatened and endangered species and species of special interest, should such species be located on or migrate through the BTC;
- Within federal funding limitations and in accordance with NGB guidance, maintain sufficient personnel to implement, manage, and monitor the management strategies of the INRMP; and
- Provide for an institutional memory that can be used as a framework for future natural resources personnel on which to base management decisions.

The ORARNG's management of military activities at the BTC must be in concert with the BLM's management plans and programs, especially the *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989) for the region. The BLM could refer to the INRMP in its own management plans and documents.

Resource-specific management goals and objectives are provided in this section, followed by implementable management tools (termed strategies) for obtaining the desired outcomes. If a management strategy is site specific, the location is provided. There are numerous goals and objectives addressing rehabilitation of resources from military training activities. The ORARNG is not responsible for damage to BTC lands by other users and will coordinate with the BLM to monitor resource damage. Additionally, many of the goals and objectives in this section focus on rehabilitation and enhancement of resources. Rehabilitation work is guided by the Army's ITAM program, while enhancement is for the purpose of the stewardship mission and Sikes Act requirements and is guided by AGI-ENV.

Methods to monitor how the strategies are working after their implementation are also identified, where applicable. Many of the management strategies are administrative (e.g., coordination with other agencies) or for the purposes of baseline data collection (e.g., conducting ecological surveys) and do not require monitoring. The INRMP will be evaluated in five years as to whether or not these administrative or data acquisition strategies have been implemented. The following goals, objectives, and strategies, unless otherwise noted, are expected to be implemented during the five-year tenure of the INRMP. Project timelines are represented in Table 6-2 under the column

“implementation priority.” Because the INRMP has been developed as an adaptive management program, modifications to the management elements are anticipated and encouraged, as additional information becomes available.

This INRMP has been coordinated with the ITAM program and is consistent with the five-year ITAM work plan, which describes the projects that will be undertaken with ITAM funds. Implementation of the plan is discussed in Section 6.

5.3 SOIL MANAGEMENT

5.3.1 Management Measures

Goal: To protect the soil resources of the BTC from erosion, compaction, and contamination resulting from military use, while maintaining the military mission.

Objective 1: Minimize the extent of wind erosion of soils from military training exercises.

- Vegetation on military training areas affected by tracked and wheeled vehicles (other than established trails and roads) will be rehabilitated annually, in part to stabilize soil resources. The BLM and ORARNG will coordinate to identify disturbed areas requiring revegetation. These areas will be seeded in fall or winter or both, at a rate of 12 pounds per acre or per site-specific BLM prescription. Seeds will be broadcast or sowed using a rangeland drill with a native seed mixture approved by the BLM.

Location: This action will be required in Training Areas A and B where wheeled or tracked vehicles are allowed off established roads and trails.

- Funding will be requested to obtain a water truck for use on graded roads prior to and during military training exercises to reduce dust emissions and to protect soil resources. The water truck will be used in conjunction with military training exercises involving wheeled or tracked vehicles and can be retrofitted with emergency fire-fighting equipment during fire season.

Location: The truck will spray all roads planned for training activities involving wheeled or tracked vehicles.

Objective 2: Minimize potential for soil contamination during military training exercises.

- Require military personnel using the BTC for training to adhere strictly to the following military regulations concerning the use, transportation, and disposal of petroleum products, oils, and lubricants in the field:
 - ORARNG Pamphlet 200-1, Chapter 11: Response to Spills and Notification of Reporting Requirements;
 - ORARNG Regulation 210-6: Installation Spill Contingency Plan;

- ORARNG Regulation 420-47: Hazardous Waste Management Plan; and
- Draft Safety, Fire and Emergency Services Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures (Hazardous Materials Response Procedures) (BTC 1999).

5.3.2 Monitoring Methods

- ORARNG will monitor vegetation actions to control soil erosion in accordance with the monitoring management goals and objectives outlined in the *Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site* (Jones 2000) (see Appendix E).
- In coordination with BLM, ORARNG will conduct annual site inspections during the growing season to ensure the success of vegetation rehabilitation on military training areas affected by tracked and wheeled vehicles (other than established trails and roads).

5.4 WATER RESOURCES

5.4.1 Management Measures

Goal: To efficiently use and conserve the water resources available to the BTC in support of the military mission and natural resources management.

Objective: Manage the BTC to reduce impacts of military training on water resources and associated water structures.

- Maintain current water conservation measures to minimize any potential waste of groundwater-produced potable water.
- Maintain the integrity and functionality of the water guzzlers for wildlife. Consider adding additional water guzzlers for wildlife as funding and time constraints allow.

Location: ORARNG will coordinate with the ODFW and BLM to determine the best location for any new guzzlers.

5.4.2 Monitoring Methods

- AGI-ENV staff will inspect and document the integrity and functionality of water guzzlers for wildlife every three years.

5.5 HABITAT MANAGEMENT

5.5.1 Wetlands

Management Measures

Goal: To assist the BLM in identifying wetland resources at the BTC.

Objective 1: Identify wetland resources, in cooperation with the BLM, that could be affected by military training after the NUID completes lining the North Unit Main Canal.

- Conduct a wetland survey for any new or remnant ephemeral or perennial wetland resources that might be located at the BTC.

Location: This action will be required on all lands within the BTC that are adjacent to the canal and used for military training.

Objective 2: Assist the BLM and other appropriate federal agencies in protecting identified wetland resources at the BTC in compliance with federal and state laws.

- Prohibit any alteration or destruction of any identified wetlands by military training activities, except those activities limited to pedestrian use.
- Encourage the BLM to conduct discussions with the NUID to determine if it is feasible to preserve some of the seepage areas that have produced wetland habitat adjacent to the North Unit Main Canal, provided no adverse impacts to military training result from this action.

Location: This action will be required in wetland areas along the canal (that are used for military training) as identified by the ONHP (Kagan 1993) and discussed in Section 3.8.

- Support federal mitigation policy of avoidance, minimization, and compensation for any wetland losses.

Monitoring Methods

- AGI-ENV will survey wetlands in areas used for military training every three years using photo points to document the conditions of and any alterations to wetlands. The survey will document the cause of alterations (e.g., loss of inflow from lining of the canal, destruction of vegetation from public use or military training).

5.5.2 Terrestrial Habitat

Management Measures

Goal: To maintain and enhance upland resources for desired plant communities (e.g., native vegetation), plant species composition, species diversity, and military training realism.

Objective 1: Minimize unnecessary impacts associated with military training exercises on terrestrial natural resources.

- When conducting maneuvers off road or when not using designated assembly areas, unit commanders will follow the guidelines written in the Standard Operating Procedures. The units will be required to provide necessary information to OMD/ORARNG to facilitate preparation of an environmental checklist when requesting the use of the training site. Guidelines will include such things as the following (and could be changed to address unforeseen issues, concerns, or opportunities):

- Disperse vehicles and equipment to avoid areas with heavy shrub and tree cover and to avoid excessive concentrations in small areas.
 - Locate assembly areas near existing roads. Only use existing roads to access all assembly areas.
 - Prohibit convoys or administrative vehicle movements off road.
 - Avoid the use of column formations and all sharp turns with tracked vehicles.
 - Use areas dominated by grasses for intensive maneuvers, column formations, and sharp turns, but only as necessary.
- Fighting positions will be excavated only in designated areas with prior BLM and BTC range control approval.
 - Trash and refuse associated with military training will not be dumped or burned at the BTC and will be removed by troops after a training event.
 - Live vegetation will not be used or cut for troop camouflage.
 - No new roads or trails will be constructed without prior approval of the BLM and the BTC range control.
 - All roads that have been used by tracked military vehicles will be graded annually by pulling the excess road material to the center of the roadway (thereby establishing a crowned running surface), with as much soil moisture as possible.
 - The BTC and ORARNG are responsible for repairing and rehabilitating damage to rangelands from military training. Rehabilitation measures will follow those outlined under Soils Management.

Objective 2: Minimize the establishment and dispersal of undesirable nonnative flora.

- To remove nonnative plant propagules, all military vehicles entering the BTC for training, except those stationed at Brett Hall or COUTES, will be washed before use to remove all dirt, mud, and vegetative material from tracks, wheel wells, tires, and under carriage. In addition, all military vehicles will be washed after use. These activities will not occur until funding is available to construct a facility.
- In cooperation with the BLM, the BTC will survey dirt roads used by the military and public for inclusion in a potential road maintenance plan.

Location: All lands within the BTC.

- Established assembly and vehicle staging areas will be hardened, as deemed necessary and within funding constraints, with gravel to reduce windblown emissions, rehabilitation costs, and potential for invasion by nonnative plants. Other sites may be used for assembly and staging only after approval by the BTC and BLM.
- Areas of disturbed soil will be surveyed for noxious weeds. Noxious weeds will be eradicated by actively removing plants.

Monitoring Methods

- Continue to implement the Army's LCTA program, as funding permits, in order to monitor ecological status, plant species composition, disturbance, and species diversity of the BTC's terrestrial habitat communities.
- Implement the monitoring management goals and objectives outlined in the *Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site* (Jones 2000) for maintaining and improving rangeland health (refer to Appendix E for monitoring management goals and objectives).
- BTC range control will review training activities for compliance with management strategies.

5.6 WILDLIFE MANAGEMENT**5.6.1 Management Measures**

Goal: To protect and enhance the wildlife resources that reside on and migrate through the BTC.

Objective 1: Assist the BLM, USFWS, and ODFW in identifying potentially important wildlife species and habitat.

- Conduct a biodiversity survey before the 2007-2011 INRMP for the BTC in order to analyze and monitor environmental trends derived from the 2002-2006 INRMP.

Location: This action will be required on all lands within the BTC.

- Coordinate with the BLM to conduct a survey on antelope use of the BTC.

Location: This action will be required on all lands within the BTC.

- Coordinate with the BLM to conduct surveys to determine where bat species are residing and whether sage grouse or pygmy rabbits are present.

Location: This action will be required on all lands within the BTC.

- Coordinate with the BLM and ODFW to assess the need for developing a pronghorn antelope management plan for the BTC.

Objective 2: Encourage diversity of terrestrial wildlife habitat at the BTC.

- Coordinate with the BLM to identify potential areas for habitat enhancement projects, such as vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects. Vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects will be conducted in an irregular pattern to create a vegetation mosaic. This will allow for a variety of vegetative successional stages and a corresponding variety of habitats for wildlife. Data from the Army's LCTA program will be used to identify enhancement areas.

Location: Any areas within the BTC could be identified for enhancement; however, emphasis will likely be placed on areas with important vegetation communities, such as old growth western juniper and bitterbrush shrubland (see Figure 3-6).

- Assess the feasibility and effectiveness of using prescribed fire by consulting with the BLM to determine whether or not a prescribed burn management plan is necessary.

5.6.2 Monitoring Methods

- No monitoring will be required for administrative actions and baseline data collection.
- Coordinate with the BLM and ODFW to determine an appropriate wildlife monitoring program, as stated in the *Inventory and Evaluation of Vertebrate Fauna at the BTC 1999-2000* (Reiher et al. 2000).
- AGI-ENV will conduct monitoring of vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects in accordance with the *Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site* (Jones 2000) (see Appendix E).

5.7 SPECIAL NATURAL AREAS MANAGEMENT

5.7.1 Management Measures

Goal: To enhance and rehabilitate western juniper and bitterbrush habitat.

Objective: Implement operating procedures to minimize effects from military training activities.

- AGI-ENV will instruct BTC range control how to identify bitterbrush and will brief them on where bitterbrush-dominated areas are located. All military assembly areas, bivouacs, mess, and latrine sites will be located more than 30 feet from any bitterbrush and in such a way that no new roads or trails are created.
- BTC range control will brief military personnel not to remove or damage old growth western juniper.
- Coordinate with the BLM to identify potential areas for enhancement.

Location: This action will be required in areas mapped in Figure 3-6 as western juniper alliance and bitterbrush shrubland alliance.

5.7.2 Monitoring Methods

- No monitoring will be required for administrative actions.
- AGI-ENV will conduct monitoring of vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects in accordance with the *Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site* (Jones 2000) (see Appendix E).
- Continue to implement the Army's LCTA program, as funding permits, in order to monitor ecological status, plant species composition, disturbance, and species diversity within western juniper and bitterbrush shrubland alliances.

5.8 FISHERIES MANAGEMENT

The BTC lacks aquatic habitat for sustainable fisheries resources. This includes Essential Fish Habitat, as defined by the Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act, and Critical Habitat, as defined under the Endangered Species Act. Therefore, no management measures are proposed. Moreover, military training activities emanating from the BTC have no impact on fisheries habitat outside of military training site boundaries.

5.9 SPECIAL STATUS SPECIES MANAGEMENT

5.9.1 Management Measures

Goal: To protect the potential habitat and populations of threatened, endangered, and special status species that could reside on or migrate through the BTC in the future.

Objective: Determine whether there is a need to manage BTC natural resources for federal or state sensitive species and the role and responsibilities of the ORARNG in this regard.

- Survey the BTC for the federally threatened or endangered species identified in Table 3-4. Surveys will be conducted in three-year intervals.

Location: This action will be required on all lands within the BTC with suitable habitat.

- Develop specific measures to protect habitats within the BTC that are used by federally threatened or endangered species identified during surveys.

5.9.2 Monitoring Methods

- No monitoring will be required for baseline data collection.
- ORARNG will develop a monitoring program for federally threatened or endangered species or their habitat if identified through surveys.

5.10 LIVESTOCK GRAZING MANAGEMENT

5.10.1 Management Measures

Goal: To provide a sustained level of livestock forage to minimize conflict between public land uses in accordance with BLM guidelines, the military mission, and ecological constraints, in balance with other resource values and uses.

Objective: Minimize potential conflict between the use of land for livestock grazing and military training at the BTC.

- Inform military personnel of the presence and potential location of livestock at the BTC before military training exercises begin. Brief military personnel on proper conduct, including maintaining the structural integrity of livestock fences and

keeping gates closed during grazing season. Prohibit training troops from damaging or breaching grazing allotment fencing.

- Continue annual meeting between the BTC and livestock grazing permittees to discuss current and potential future rangeland management issues.
- Maintain metal swing gates (powder-river gates) installed by the BTC for use by the military and livestock grazing permittees.
- Coordinate with the BLM and livestock grazing permittees to install additional powder-river gates to support military training, as determined necessary and appropriate, and as funding and staffing constraints allow.

5.10.2 Monitoring Methods

- BTC range control will review training activities for compliance with management strategies.
- BTC range control will conduct bi-annual surveys of training lands to ensure fencing is in good condition.

5.11 PEST MANAGEMENT

5.11.1 Management Measures

Goal: To aggressively control nonnative noxious and undesirable weeds using integrated pest management methods in accordance with environmental policies as funding allows.

Objective 1: Continue implementation of the BTC's pest management program, including pesticide/herbicide applications.

- Maintain compliance with all federal, military, state, and local environmental standards in regard to pesticide/herbicide use and continue to obtain necessary permits for chemical application.
- Continue requiring annual submission and subsequent review of pest management plans, as well as annual weed surveys and pest control reporting, per ORARNG Regulation 210-5.
- Coordinate with and obtain approval from the USFWS, ODFW, BLM, and other applicable federal or state agencies prior to pest management operations, as deemed appropriate and necessary to comply with applicable law.
- Prohibit applying pesticides or herbicides directly to wetlands, surface waters, or other identified sensitive areas unless use in such sites is specifically approved by the OMD, BLM, and other applicable federal and state agencies. *Location:* Wetland areas that are located adjacent to the canal as discussed in Section 3.8. Other sensitive areas also include habitat for protected species, which will be established under management measures in Section 5.9.

Objective 2: Support the federal and military requirement for reducing reliance on chemical means of pest control, per DOD directive 4150.7.

- Per ORARNG Regulation 210-5, substitute biological, physical/mechanical, cultural, or ecosystem management controls in lieu of chemicals whenever logistically, environmentally, and financially feasible.

5.11.2 Monitoring Methods

- AGI-ENV will review the annual submission of the pest management plan (described in the above strategy) to evaluate its effectiveness.

5.12 CULTURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

5.12.1 Management Measures

Goal: To minimize disturbance of cultural resources.

Objective: Coordinate with Native American tribes and the Oregon SHPO to identify cultural resources on 100 percent of the BTC.

- Planning of all ground-disturbing activities will occur in consultation with Native American tribes and Oregon SHPO.

5.12.2 Monitoring Methods

- No monitoring will be required.

5.13 OUTDOOR RECREATION MANAGEMENT, ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS, AND ENFORCEMENT

5.13.1 Management Measures

Goal 1: To minimize potential conflict between public recreationists using public lands and military training exercises.

Objective 1: Support the BLM policy for multiple use on public lands, including public access and recreation.

- ORARNG will not restrict public access for recreation to the federal lands that compose the BTC.

Objective 2: Assist the BLM in educating users of public lands about the presence and importance of the military mission.

- Develop and install interpretative displays at BTC public access points that explain the presence of the military, the approximate training schedule, and the importance of the military mission.

Location: This action will be required at major public access points, which include the two southern roads off Highway 126 into Training Area B, the northern road

off Highway 126 into Training Area F, and the western road off Powell Butte Highway along the boundary of Training Areas D and E (Figure 3-2).

- Military range patrols will inform public land users of the presence of the military without hindering access to the public lands.

Objective 3: Maintain the integrity of natural resources at the BTC by supporting the BLM's outdoor recreation management program, as defined by the *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989).

- Support the BLM in developing and installing displays that interpret land, water, and wildlife resource values found at the BTC. Signs will explain the destructive potential of invasive species and noxious weeds and how public land users can minimize their potential impacts on natural resources.

Objective 4: Adhere to the stipulations outlined in AR 200-3 in regard to cooperating with the BLM, USFWS, ODFW, and other public agencies in maintaining natural resources law enforcement on public lands.

- BTC will assist the BLM, Oregon State Police, and other law enforcement officials, as requested, by informing proper authorities about illegal hunting and illegal trash disposal on public lands.
- ODFW and the BLM will retain responsibility for any hunting on BTC lands (BTC does not have the authority to administer a hunting program).

Goal 2: To cooperate and assist the BLM, upon interagency agreement, with the promotion and enjoyment of wildlife resources that reside on and migrate through the BTC.

Objective: Inform and educate the public about the importance of maintaining and enhancing biodiversity on public lands.

- In cooperation with the BLM, install educational displays, as funding allows, about wildlife resources at the BTC and emphasize special status or sensitive species and military efforts to conserve such fauna.

5.13.2 Monitoring Methods

- No monitoring will be required.

5.14 FIRE MANAGEMENT

5.14.1 Management Measures

Goal: To minimize the potential for fire at the BTC, as related to military training exercises.

Objective 1: Maintain military training protocols and seasonally trained and equipped fire crews to reduce the potential for incidents of fire outbreak at the BTC.

- Follow emergency services notification and fire evacuation procedures in the event of fire, as outlined under the BTC's draft Annex (BTC 1999) and AR 420-90, Fire and Emergency Services.
- Request funding to buy and maintain a water truck for fighting fires. The water truck will be retrofitted with equipment for dust abatement prior to training maneuvers with tracked and wheeled vehicles.

Objective 2: Determine the appropriateness of implementing a prescribed burn management program or fuel hazard reduction strategy at the BTC by consulting with the BLM.

- Consult with the BLM to determine if a prescribed burn program for the BTC would be financially feasible, politically acceptable, and beneficial to wildlife habitat and forage, biodiversity, and military training.

5.14.2 Monitoring Methods

- No monitoring will be required.

5.15 PUBLIC HEALTH AND SAFETY

5.15.1 Management Measures

Goal: To ensure the health, welfare, and safety of military personnel and the public from unexpected military training incidents at the BTC.

Objective 1: Provide for military personnel safety during military training exercises.

- Adhere strictly to the military training safety procedures, as outlined in the BTC's draft Annex (BTC 1999).

Objective 2: Provide for public safety during military training exercises.

- Inform the public of ongoing military training exercises without denying public access to public lands.
- Design and post signs informing the public of the presence and activity of the military at the BTC. Include basic safety information and an approximate schedule of military training exercises.

Location: This action will be required at major public access points, which include the two southern roads off Highway 126 into Training Area B, the northern road off Highway 126 into Training Area F, and the western road off Powell Butte Highway along the boundary of Training Areas D and E (Figure 3-2).

5.15.2 Monitoring Methods

- No monitoring will be required for administrative actions.

5.16 FOREST MANAGEMENT

5.16.1 Management Measures

Goal: To protect forestry resources and allow public access to forested areas.

Objective 1: To support BLM policy of multiple use, including forestry, and to maintain forest cover for military training.

- Juniper trees will not be removed or damaged for training activities. Any damage will be reported to the BLM and, if applicable, revegetation will take place.
- ORARNG will not restrict public access for any forestry activities authorized by the BLM.

5.16.2 Monitoring Methods

- No monitoring will be required for administrative actions.

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SECTION 6

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INRMP

6.1 ORGANIZATIONS, ROLES, AND RESPONSIBILITIES

6.1.1 Introduction

As detailed below, the mission of the ORARNG is to ensure that its activities and operations comply with applicable federal, state, and local environmental laws and regulations, as well as with DOD, DA, and NGB policy, regulations, and implementing guidance (OMD 2000). Consequently, the ORARNG has the primary role and responsibility for directing the implementation of this INRMP at the BTC from 2002 to 2006. The training center manager and range control personnel at the BTC are responsible for the daily management and oversight of the BTC's natural resources management program. As the administrator of the public lands on which the BTC is located, the BLM is the primary land steward, and the ORARNG complies with regulations and guidance developed by this agency. Under the INRMP, the BLM will retain the right to authorize use by the ORARNG under special use permits and will retain their authority as the primary land manager for BTC lands. No alteration to the existing organizational structure of the ORARNG or BTC is expected or necessary to meet the goals and objectives identified in the INRMP.

6.1.2 National Guard Bureau Responsibilities

The NGB Environmental Programs Division is responsible for reviewing and approving the INRMP/EA. Such approval would be documented by signing both the signature page in the document and a Finding of No Significant Impact. They are also responsible for advising the ORARNG before formal submission to the USFWS, BLM, and ODFW. The NGB Environmental Programs Division ensures operational readiness by promoting environmental quality and an environmental ethic throughout the Army National Guard and is responsible for tracking projects, providing technical assistance, conducting quality assurance of written materials, and providing funding to support the programs.

6.1.3 OMD/ORARNG Responsibilities

The Adjutant General is responsible for the operation and maintenance of the BTC, which includes implementation of this INRMP. The Adjutant General ensures that all facility land users are aware of and comply with procedures, requirements, or applicable laws and regulations that accomplish the goals and objectives of the INRMP. The Adjutant General also ensures coordination of projects and construction between environmental, training, and engineering staffs.

The Deputy Chief of Staff Operations has the primary responsibility for scheduling military training and safety of all personnel while training exercises are being conducted. Secondary to scheduling is maintaining a high-quality training environment.

The AGI-ENV is responsible for characterizing the natural and cultural resources of the training sites, identifying compliance needs, and advising the OMD/ORARNG on the best ways to comply with federal and state environmental laws and regulations. The AGI-ENV provides technical assistance to training site personnel including developing projects, securing permits, conducting field studies, providing Environmental Awareness materials, locating and mapping natural and cultural resources, preparing plans, and revising the INRMP every five years. The AGI-ENV also coordinates the ITAM program and oversees the NEPA process for the OMD/ORARNG.

The training center manager and range control personnel at the BTC are responsible for the daily management and oversight of the BTC's natural resources management program. BTC staff has intimate knowledge of all aspects of the training site, including training scheduling (and conflicts), locations of training facilities, impairments or problems with human-made structures or natural functions, and needs for improvement or maintenance of the training land.

The statewide Construction and Facilities Management Office provides a full range of engineering disciplines for all facilities under the jurisdiction of the OMD, including the BTC. The statewide Construction and Facilities Management Office is responsible for master planning and ensuring that all construction projects comply with environmental regulations by consulting with the AGI-ENV prior to any construction by ORARNG engineers or contractors. The statewide Construction and Facilities Management Office also provides necessary assistance with design of construction projects, such as roads and erosion control projects.

The Public Affairs Office is expected to provide expertise in the development and production of Environmental Awareness materials for distribution to training site managers and unit commanders. The Public Affairs Office also functions as a liaison with the public in public meetings and community educational events.

The Judge Staff Advocate is expected to advise the Adjutant General, Deputy Chief of Staff Operations, statewide Construction and Facilities Management Office, and AGI-ENV on laws and regulations that affect training land use and environmental

compliance. Depending on the issue, this responsibility may be shared with the State Attorney General, as mandated by state law.

The Director of Plans, Operations, and Training will coordinate with commands and assist the AGI-ENV in training of environmental personnel, assist the AGI-ENV in coordinating environmental program projects and budget requirements, and ensure appropriate NEPA documents are being prepared before implementing various plans or programs.

6.2 LABOR RESOURCES

Two ORARNG on-site staff manage the BTC's natural resources program, with oversight and assistance by the BLM Prineville District. The training center manager oversees the risk management program as it pertains to natural resources. The range control office manages military training exercises, including educating military personnel to the natural resources management program before training. In addition, AGI-ENV provides administrative support and technical assistance staff for natural resources programs at the BTC.

6.3 PLAN REVISION AND AMENDMENT PROCESS

This plan covers fiscal years 2002 through 2006 and will be revised for fiscal year 2007. Plan revisions will include consultation with the appropriate state and federal agencies, Native American tribes, and local community. Prior to the scheduled revision, it may be necessary to amend the plan to reflect management changes. Changes are likely because adaptive management is part of the plan and information is constantly being improved. Proposed amendments will be drafted into a letter and mailed to the appropriate state and federal agencies (including the BLM, ODFW, and USFWS), Native American tribes, and interested parties for review and comments. If no comments are received, or no substantial issues raised, the amendment will be adopted into the plan. This INRMP will be reviewed per the Environmental Compliance Assessment System, which is discussed in Section 4.5.

6.4 INRMP FUNDING

6.4.1 Military Funding

Funding for the BTC is provided by the NGB, which receives an annual budget from congressional appropriations. To receive funding for natural resources projects, proposed management actions must be shown to comply with federal laws and mandates before funds are appropriated.

Funding requirements for Army environmental programs (including the natural and cultural resources programs) are identified in the Environmental Program Requirements reporting process. The AGI-ENV handles the Environmental Program Requirements funding for the BTC.

6.4.2 Integrated Training Area Management Funding

The Deputy Chief of Staff Operations and Training oversees the ITAM program. The ITAM program provides funding for baseline data collection, monitoring programs, and rehabilitation activities that are implemented by the military at the BTC. The ITAM funds offered to the BTC are earmarked for projects aimed at maintaining, preserving, and restoring natural resources that could be affected by military training activities. Funding for the ITAM program is appropriated by NGB from training funds, rather than through the environmental program, and consequently, cannot be used for stewardship projects.

Implementing any of the projects described in this INRMP would require assistance from, coordination with, and approval of the BLM. Additionally, some of the projects described could require outside assistance from other federal and state agencies, universities, organizations, and private contractors. Using these resources is often the most efficient and cost-effective method for acquiring short-term or temporary expertise. Some of the parties will be reimbursed for their assistance, as agreed, based on memoranda of understanding and contractual agreements. Other parties could supply their assistance in accordance with cooperative agreements. The Legacy Resource Management Program (Legacy) is one potential outside partner and is summarized below.

6.4.3 Legacy Resource Management Program

Legacy was established by Congress to provide financial assistance to the DOD military branches to conserve and protect natural and cultural resources. Typical Legacy projects involve regional ecosystem management initiatives, habitat preservation efforts, archaeological investigations, invasive species control, and bird and mammal migratory patterns monitoring and predicting.

The three principles of the Legacy program—stewardship, leadership, and partnership—are seen as the foundation from which the program promotes four specific elements, as follows:

1. Incorporate an ecosystem approach that assists DOD in maintaining biological diversity and the sustainable use of the land and water resources for the military mission and other uses.
2. Implement an interdisciplinary approach to resource stewardship that takes advantage of the similarities between DOD's natural and cultural resource plans. The program strives to integrate management methodologies and techniques across natural and cultural resource initiatives.
3. Promote an understanding and appreciation of natural and cultural resources by encouraging greater awareness and involvement by both the military and the public.

4. Apply known and scientifically defensible resource management principles across broad geographic areas. Specific Legacy programs with an ecoregional scope include the Sonoran Ecosystem Management Initiative, the Gulf Coast Plain Ecosystem Partnership, the Chesapeake Bay Program, and Partners in Flight.

For fiscal years 1991 to 1999, the DOD Legacy program funded more than \$200 million in natural and cultural resource projects. Project proposals are typically due in the spring of each fiscal year. Projects are competitively funded; proposal submittal guidelines and format requirements are available through the Internet at <http://www.dodlegacy.org>. Funding for this program has been reduced over the years, and currently only those projects already tied into the Legacy program are receiving funds.

6.5 IMPLEMENTATION AND FUNDING PRIORITY FOR THE INRMP

To facilitate the implementation process of the different management tools of the INRMP, an implementation priority and funding priority rating system has been developed. The purpose of the system is to allow the ORARNG and BTC to forecast funding requests and staffing needs. It is designed to justify why certain management actions are needed to secure funding and to emphasize the importance of certain projects over others.

Due to budgetary limitations, DOD-related funding tends to be allocated for those actions fulfilling legal requirements but is more limited for stewardship (on noncompliance) actions. Thus, funding priorities sometimes differ from the implementation priorities of an ecosystem-based INRMP.

Funding priority is defined by the "Environmental Quality Conservation Compliance Classes," as detailed in DOD Instruction 4715.3, and is summarized in Table 6-1.

Implementation priorities tend to be based on legal, institutional, and ecological principles related to ecosystem-based natural resource management. Implementation priorities are determined by the following criteria:

- High priority— Legally required activities or actions deemed important to the military mission, ecology, or personnel safety. These actions would be ongoing or would be expected to be implemented within the next three years, depending on the availability of funding (fiscal years 2002 – 2005).
- Medium priority— Compliance or stewardship actions that need to be implemented in time to meet the established deadlines defined in the INRMP or within the next six years, depending on the availability of funding (fiscal years 2002 – 2008).

Table 6-1
Definition of DOD-related Funding Priorities

Conservation Compliance Class	Description of Requirement	DOD-related Funding Priority
0	Recurring: Includes activities needed to cover the recurring administrative, personnel, and other costs associated with managing the military training site conservation program that are necessary to meet applicable compliance requirements or that are in direct support of the military mission. Also included are environmental management activities associated with operating facilities and the military training site.	High
I	Current Compliance: Includes projects and activities that are needed because a military training site is out of compliance with current legal requirements or will be out of compliance if the project or activities are not implemented in the current program year, or the projects and activities are immediate and essential to maintain operational integrity or to sustain readiness of the military mission.	High
II	Maintenance: Includes those projects and activities that are not currently out of compliance but that will be out of compliance if projects and activities are not implemented in time to meet an established deadline beyond the current program year.	Medium
III	Enhancement Actions Beyond Compliance: Includes those projects and activities that enhance conservation resources or the integrity of the military training site mission or that are needed to address overall environmental goals and objectives but that are not specifically required by law.	Low

Source: DOD Instruction 4715.3

- Low priority— Activities and projects that enhance natural resources but that are not specifically required by law or military mission needs. These activities or projects are likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

The BTC INRMP management strategies are summarized in Table 6-2, and monitoring methods are summarized in Table 6-3. These tables list each management strategy and monitoring method presented in Section 5 and compares the implementation priority to the funding priority. The tables are based on an initial review of funding needs, and include the likely source of funds and the party responsible for each management strategy. In most cases, AGI-ENV funding is allocated to strategies that are compliance and policy-based, while ITAM funds are for projects relating to maintaining, monitoring, and restoring training lands. Where possible, other funding sources have been identified.

Table 6-2
 Summary of Management Strategies, Priority of Implementation and Funding, and Potential Funding Sources

Conservation Compliance or Stewardship Class	Compliance (C) or Stewardship (S)	Management Strategy	Funding Priority	Implementation Priority	Potential Funding Source	Responsible Party
0	C	<p>Soil Management Annually rehabilitate vegetation on military training areas affected by tracked and wheeled vehicles (other than established trails and roads), in part to stabilize soil resources. The BLM and ORANG will coordinate to identify disturbed areas requiring revegetation. These areas will be seeded in the fall or winter or both at a rate of 12 pounds per acre, or per site-specific BLM prescription. Seeds will be broadcast or sowed using a rangeland drill with a native seed mixture approved by the BLM. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required in Training Areas A and B where wheeled or tracked vehicles are allowed off established roads and trails.</p> <p>Funding will be requested to obtain a water truck for use on graded roads prior to and during military training exercises involving wheeled or tracked vehicles, but can be retrofitted with emergency fire-fighting equipment during fire season. <i>Location:</i> The truck will spray all roads planned for training activities involving wheeled or tracked vehicles.</p> <p>Require military personnel using the BTC for training to adhere strictly to the following military regulations concerning the use, transportation, and disposal of petroleum products, oils, and lubricants in the field:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORANG Pamphlet 200-1, Chapter 11: Response to Spills and Notification of Reporting Requirements • ORANG Regulation 210-6: Installation Spill Contingency Plan; • ORANG Regulation 420-47: Hazardous Waste Management Plan; and • Draft <i>Safety, Fire and Emergency Services Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures</i> (Hazardous Materials Response Procedures). 	High	High	ITAM	BTC/AGI-ENV
III	S	<p>Funding will be requested to obtain a water truck for use on graded roads prior to and during military training exercises involving wheeled or tracked vehicles, but can be retrofitted with emergency fire-fighting equipment during fire season. <i>Location:</i> The truck will spray all roads planned for training activities involving wheeled or tracked vehicles.</p> <p>Require military personnel using the BTC for training to adhere strictly to the following military regulations concerning the use, transportation, and disposal of petroleum products, oils, and lubricants in the field:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORANG Pamphlet 200-1, Chapter 11: Response to Spills and Notification of Reporting Requirements • ORANG Regulation 210-6: Installation Spill Contingency Plan; • ORANG Regulation 420-47: Hazardous Waste Management Plan; and • Draft <i>Safety, Fire and Emergency Services Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures</i> (Hazardous Materials Response Procedures). 	High	Medium	ITAM	AGI-ENV
0	C	<p>Require military personnel using the BTC for training to adhere strictly to the following military regulations concerning the use, transportation, and disposal of petroleum products, oils, and lubricants in the field:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORANG Pamphlet 200-1, Chapter 11: Response to Spills and Notification of Reporting Requirements • ORANG Regulation 210-6: Installation Spill Contingency Plan; • ORANG Regulation 420-47: Hazardous Waste Management Plan; and • Draft <i>Safety, Fire and Emergency Services Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures</i> (Hazardous Materials Response Procedures). 	High	High	ITAM/AGI-ENV	BTC/AGI-ENV
0	C	<p>Water Resources Maintain current water conservation measures to minimize any potential waste of groundwater-produced potable water.</p>	N/A	High	N/A	BTC
III	S	<p>Maintain the integrity and functionality of the water guzzlers for wildlife. Consider adding additional water guzzlers for wildlife as funding and time constraints allow. <i>Location:</i> ORANG will coordinate with the ODFW and BLM to determine the best location for any new guzzlers.</p>	Low	Medium	AGI-ENV/BLM	AGI-ENV/BLM

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents the following timing preference:
 High priority = Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).
 Medium priority = Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).
 Low priority = Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

Funding priority ranking is based on the likelihood of receiving funds for such a project/program as follows:
 High priority = Program likely will be funded due to federal, state, or military requirement.
 Medium priority = Program likely will be funded due to military policy.
 Low priority = Program will be funded only if discretionary funds are available.

N/A = Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.
 Potential funding sources: AGI-ENV, BLM, ODFW, and ITAM

Table 6-2
 Summary of Management Strategies, Priority of Implementation and Funding, and Potential Funding Sources (continued)

Conservation Compliance Class	Compliance (C) or Stewardship (S)	Management Strategy	Funding Priority	Implementation Priority	Potential Funding Source	Responsible Party
		Wetlands				
I	C	Conduct a wetland survey for any new or remnant ephemeral or perennial wetlands resources at the BTC. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required on all lands within the BTC that are adjacent to the canal and used for military training.	Medium	Medium	AGI-ENV	AGI-ENV
I	C	Prohibit any alteration to or destruction of any identified wetlands by military training activities, except those activities limited to pedestrian use.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC
III	S	Encourage the BLM to conduct discussions with the NIJD to determine if it is feasible to preserve some of the seepage areas that have produced wetland habitat adjacent to the North Unit Maun Canal, provided no adverse impacts to military training result from this action. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required in all wetland areas along the canal (that are used for military training) as identified by the ONHP (Kagan 1993) and discussed in Section 3.8.	N/A	Medium	N/A	AGI-ENV/BLM
0	C	Support federal mitigation policy of avoidance, minimization, and compensation for any wetland losses.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC/AGI-ENV
0	C	Terrestrial Habitat When conducting maneuvers off road or when not using designated assembly areas, unit commanders will follow the guidelines written in the Standard Operating Procedures. The units will be required to provide necessary information to OMD/ORANNG to facilitate preparation of an environmental checklist when requesting the use of the training site. Guidelines will include such things as the following (and could be changed to address unforeseen issues, concerns, or opportunities): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disperse vehicles and equipment to avoid areas with heavy shrub and tree cover and to avoid excessive concentrations in small areas. • Locate assembly areas near existing roads. Only use existing roads to access all assembly areas. • Prohibit convoys or administrative vehicle movements off road. • Avoid the use of column formations and all sharp turns with tracked vehicles. • Use areas dominated by grasses for intensive maneuvers, column formations, and sharp turns, but only as necessary. Excavate fighting positions only in designated areas with prior BLM and BTC range control approval.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC
I	C		N/A	High	N/A	BTC

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents the following timing preference:
 High priority - Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).
 Medium priority - Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).
 Low priority - Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

Funding priority ranking is based on the likelihood of receiving funds for such a project/program as follows:
 High priority - Program likely will be funded due to federal, state, or military requirement.
 Medium priority - Program likely will be funded due to military policy.
 Low priority - Program will be funded only if discretionary funds are available.
 N/A - Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Potential funding sources: AGI-ENV, BLM, ODFW, and ITAM

Table 6-2
 Summary of Management Strategies, Priority of Implementation and Funding, and Potential Funding Sources (continued)

Conservation Compliance Class	Compliance or Stewardship (S)	Management Strategy	Funding Priority	Implementation Priority	Potential Funding Source	Responsible Party
II	C	Prohibit trash and refuse associated with military training from being dumped or burned at the BTC and remove it at the end of training.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC
I	C	Prohibit live vegetation from being used or cut for troop camouflage.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC
I	C	Prohibit construction of new roads or trails without prior approval of the BLM and the BTC range control.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC/BLM
I	C	Grade all roads that have been used by tracked military vehicles by pulling the excess road material to the center of the roadway (thereby establishing a crowned running surface) with as much soil moisture as possible.	High	High	ITAM	BTC/AGI-ENV
0	C	The BTC and ORARNG will repair and rehabilitate damage to rangelands from military training. Rehabilitation measures will follow those outlined under Soils Management.	F-high	F-high	ITAM	BTC/AGI-ENV
I	C	To remove nonnative plant propagules, all military vehicles entering the BTC for training, except those stationed at Brett Hall or COUTES, will be washed before use on training lands to remove all dirt, mud, and vegetative material from tracks, wheel wells, tires, and under carriage. These activities will not occur until funding is available to construct a facility.	F-high	F-high	ITAM	AGI-ENV
III	S	In cooperation with the BLM, require the BTC to survey dirt roads used by the military and the public for inclusion in a potential road maintenance plan (as part of the BTC Development Plan). <i>Location:</i> This action will be required on all lands within the BTC.	N/A	Medium	N/A	BTC/AGI-ENV
II	S	Harden established assembly and vehicle staging areas, as deemed necessary and within funding constraints, with gravel to reduce windblown emissions, rehabilitation costs, and potential for invasion by non-native plants. Other sites may be used for assembly and staging only after approval by the BTC and BLM.	Medium	F-high	ITAM	BTC/AGI-ENV
0	C	Survey areas of disturbed soil for noxious weeds. Eradicate noxious weeds by actively removing plants.	High	High	ITAM/AGI-ENV	BTC/AGI-ENV
II	S	Wildlife Management Conduct a biodiversity survey before developing the 2007-2011 INRMP for the BTC in order to analyze and monitor environmental trends derived from the 2002-2006 INRMP. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required on all lands within the BTC.	Medium	Medium	AGI-ENV	AGI-ENV
II	S	Coordinate with the BLM to conduct a survey on antelope use of the BTC. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required on all lands within the BTC.	Medium	Medium	AGI-ENV	BLM/AGI-ENV

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents the following timing preference:
 High priority = Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).
 Medium priority = Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).
 Low priority = Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

Funding priority ranking is based on the likelihood of receiving funds for such a project/program as follows:
 High priority = Program likely will be funded due to federal, state, or military requirement.
 Medium priority = Program likely will be funded due to military policy.
 Low priority = Program will be funded only if discretionary funds are available.

N/A = Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Potential funding sources: AGI-ENV, BLM, ODFW, and ITAM

Table 6-2
 Summary of Management Strategies, Priority of Implementation and Funding, and Potential Funding Sources (continued)

Conservation Compliance Class	Compliance (C) or Stewardship (S)	Management Strategy	Funding Priority	Implementation Priority	Potential Funding Source	Responsible Party
II	S	Coordinate with the BLM to conduct surveys to determine where bat species are residing and whether sage grouse or pygmy rabbits are present. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required on all lands within the BTC.	Medium	Medium	AGI-ENV	BLM/AGI-ENV
III	S	Coordinate with the BLM and ODFW to assess the need for developing a pronghorn antelope management plan for the BTC.	N/A	Medium	N/A	AGI-ENV
II	C	Coordinate with the BLM to identify potential areas for habitat enhancement projects, such as vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects. Conduct vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects in an irregular pattern to create a vegetation mosaic. This will allow for a variety of vegetative successional stages and a corresponding variety of habitats for wildlife. Data from the Army's LCIA program will be used to identify enhancement areas. <i>Location:</i> Any areas within the BTC could be identified for enhancement; however, emphasis will likely be placed on areas with important vegetation communities, such as old growth western juniper and bitterbrush shrubland (see Figure 3-6).	Low	Medium	ITAM	BTC/AGI-ENV
III	S	Assess the feasibility and effectiveness of using prescribed fire by consulting with the BLM to determine whether or not a prescribed burn management plan is necessary.	N/A	Low	AGI-ENV	AGI-ENV
0	C	Special Natural Areas Management AGI-ENV will instruct BTC range control how to identify bitterbrush and will brief them on where bitterbrush-dominated areas are located. All military assembly areas, bivouacs, mess, and latrine sites will be located more than 30 feet from any bitterbrush and in such a way that no new roads or trails are created.	N/A	High	AGI-ENV	AGI-ENV
III	S	BTC range control will brief military personnel not to remove old growth western juniper.	N/A	Medium	N/A	BTC
III	S	Coordinate with the BLM to identify potential areas for enhancement. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required in areas mapped in Figure 3-6 as western juniper alliance and bitterbrush shrubland alliance.	Low	Medium	AGI-ENV	AGI-ENV
I	C	Special Status Species Management Survey the BTC for federally threatened or endangered species identified in Table 3-4. Surveys will be conducted in three-year intervals. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required on all lands within the BTC with suitable habitat.	High	High	AGI-ENV	AGI-ENV
I	C	Develop specific measures to protect habitats within the BTC that are used by federally threatened or endangered species identified during surveys.	High	High	AGI-ENV/BLM	AGI-ENV

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents the following timing preference:
 High priority - Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).
 Medium priority - Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).
 Low priority - Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

Funding priority ranking is based on the likelihood of receiving funds for such a project/program as follows:

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 Medium priority - Program likely will be funded due to military policy.

Low priority - Program will be funded only if discretionary funds are available.

N/A - Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Potential funding sources: AGI-ENV, BLM, ODFW, and ITAM

Table 6-2
 Summary of Management Strategies, Priority of Implementation and Funding, and Potential Funding Sources (continued)

Conservation Compliance Class	Compliance (C) or Stewardship (S)	Management Strategy	Funding Priority	Implementation Priority	Potential Funding Source	Responsible Party
II	C	Livestock Grazing Management Inform military personnel of the presence and potential location of livestock at the BTC before military training exercises begin. Brief military personnel on proper conduct, including maintaining the structural integrity of livestock fences and keeping gates closed during grazing season. Prohibit training troops from damaging or breaching grazing allotment fencing.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC
II	S	Continue annual meetings between the BTC and livestock grazing permittees to discuss current and potential rangeland management issues.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC/BLM
II	S	Maintain powder-river gates installed by the BTC for use by the military and livestock grazing permittees.	Medium	High	ITAM	BTC
III	S	Coordinate with the BLM and livestock grazing permittees to install additional powder-river gates, as determined necessary and appropriate and as funding and staffing constraints allow.	Low	Low	ITAM	BTC/AGI-ENV
I	C	Pest Management Maintain compliance with all federal, military, state, and local environmental standards in regard to pesticide/herbicide use and continue to obtain necessary permits for chemical application.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC/AGI-ENV
I	C	Continue requiring pest management plans, as well as annual weed surveys and pest control reporting, per ORARING Regulation 210-5.	N/A	High	N/A	AGI-ENV
II	C	Coordinate with and obtain approval from the USFWS, ODFW, BLM, and other applicable federal or state agencies prior to pest management operations, as deemed appropriate and necessary to comply with applicable law.	N/A	High	N/A	AGI-ENV
I	C	Prohibit applying pesticides or herbicide directly to wetlands, surface waters, or other identified sensitive areas unless use in such sites is specifically approved by the OMD, BLM, and other applicable federal and state agencies. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required in wetland areas that are located adjacent to the canal as discussed in Section 3.8. Other sensitive areas also include habitat for protected species, which will be established under management measures for threatened, endangered, and special status species.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC/AGI-ENV
I	C	Per ORARING Regulation 210-5, substitute biological, physical/mechanical, cultural, or ecosystem management controls in lieu of chemicals whenever logistically, environmentally, and financially feasible.	N/A	High	N/A	ENV

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents the following timing preference:
 High priority = Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).
 Medium priority = Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).
 Low priority = Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

Funding priority ranking is based on the likelihood of receiving funds for such a project/program as follows:

High priority = Program likely will be funded due to federal, state, or military requirement.

Medium priority = Program likely will be funded due to military policy.

Low priority = Program will be funded only if discretionary funds are available.

N/A = Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Potential funding sources: AGI-ENV, BLM, ODFW, and ITAM

Table 6-2
 Summary of Management Strategies, Priority of Implementation and Funding, and Potential Funding Sources (continued)

Conservation Compliance Class	Compliance (C) or Stewardship (S)	Management Strategy	Funding Priority	Implementation Priority	Potential Funding Source	Responsible Party
I	C	Cultural Resource Management Planning of all ground-disturbing activities will occur in consultation with Native American tribes and Oregon SHPO.	High	High	AGI-ENV	BTC/AGI-ENV
I	C	Outdoor Recreation Management, Environmental Awareness, and Enforcement ORARNG will not restrict public access for recreation on the federal public lands that compose the BTC.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC
III	S	Develop and install interpretive displays at BTC public access points that explain the presence of the military, the approximate training schedule, and the importance of the military mission. Location: This action will be required at major public access points, which include the two southern roads off Highway 126 into Training Area B, the northern road off Highway 126 into Training Area F, and the western road off Powell Butte Highway along the boundary of Training Areas D and E (Figure 3-2).	High	High	ITAM	BTC/AGI-ENV
I	S	Military range patrols will inform public land users of the presence of the military without hindering access to the public lands.	N/A	Medium	N/A	BTC
III	S	Support the BLM in developing and installing displays that interpret land, water, and wildlife resource values found at the BTC. Signs will explain the destructive potential of invasive species and noxious weeds and how public land users can minimize their potential impacts on natural resources.	Medium	Medium	ITAM/BLM	BTC/BLM/AGI-ENV
III	S	BTC will assist the BLM, Oregon State Police, and other law enforcement officials, as requested, by informing proper authorities about illegal hunting and illegal trash disposal on public lands.	N/A	Low	N/A	BTC
III	S	ODFW and the BLM will retain responsibility for any hunting on BTC lands (BTC does not have the authority to administer a hunting program).	N/A	Low	N/A	BLM/ODFW
III	S	In cooperation with the BLM, install educational displays, as funding allows, about wildlife resources at the BTC and emphasize special status or sensitive species and military efforts to conserve such fauna.	Low	Low	ITAM/BLM	BTC/BLM/AGI-ENV
I	C	Fire Management Follow emergency services notification and fire evacuation procedures in the event of fire, as outlined under the BTC's draft <i>Fire Safety and Emergency Service Annex to the Standard Operating Procedures</i> and AR 420-90, <i>Fire and Emergency Services</i> .	N/A	High	N/A	BTC

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents the following timing preference:

High priority - Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).

Medium priority - Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).

Low priority - Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

Funding priority ranking is based on the likelihood of receiving funds for such a project/program as follows:

High priority - Program likely will be funded due to federal, state, or military requirement.

Medium priority - Program likely will be funded due to military policy.

Low priority - Program will be funded only if discretionary funds are available.

N/A - Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Potential funding sources: AGI-ENV, BLM, ODFW, and ITAM

Table 6-2
 Summary of Management Strategies, Priority of Implementation and Funding, and Potential Funding Sources (continued)

Conservation Compliance Class	Compliance (C) or Stewardship (S)	Management Strategy	Funding Priority	Implementation Priority	Potential Funding Source	Responsible Party
II	S	Request funds to buy and maintain a water truck for fighting fires. Retrofit truck with equipment for dust abatement before training maneuvers with tracked and wheeled vehicles begin.	Medium	Medium	ITAM	AGI-ENV
III	S	Consult with the BLM to determine if a prescribed burn program for the BTC would be financially feasible, politically acceptable, and beneficial to wildlife habitat and forage, biodiversity, and military training.	N/A	Low	N/A	AGI-ENV
I	C	Public Health and Safety Management Adhere strictly to the military training safety procedures, as outlined in the BTC's draft <i>Fire Safety, and Emergency Services Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures</i> .	N/A	High	N/A	BTC
II	S	Inform public of ongoing military training exercises without denying public access to public lands.	High	High	ITAM	BTC
III	S	Design and post signs informing the public of military activities at the BTC. Include basic safety information and an approximate schedule of military training exercises. Location: This action will be required at major public access points, which include the two southern roads off Highway 126 into Training Area B, the northern road off Highway 126 into Training Area F, and the western road off Powell Butte Highway along the boundary of Training Areas D and E (Figure 3-2).	High	High	ITAM	ORARNG/BTC
0	S	Forest Management Juniper trees will not be removed or damaged for training activities. Any damage will be reported to the BLM and, if applicable, revegetation will take place.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC
0	C	ORARNG will not restrict public access for any forestry activities authorized by the BLM.	N/A	High	N/A	BTC

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents the following timing preference:
 High priority - Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).
 Medium priority - Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).
 Low priority - Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

Funding priority ranking is based on the likelihood of receiving funds for such a project/program as follows:

High priority - Program likely will be funded due to federal, state, or military requirement.

Medium priority - Program likely will be funded due to military policy.

Low priority - Program will be funded only if discretionary funds are available.

N/A - Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Potential funding sources: AGI-ENV, BLM, ODFW, and ITAM

Table 6-3
 Summary of Monitoring Methods, Priority of Implementation and Funding, and Potential Funding Sources

Monitoring Method	Funding Priority	Implementation Priority	Potential Funding Source	Responsible Party
Soils Monitoring ORARNG will monitor vegetation actions to control soil erosion in accordance with the monitoring management goals and objectives outlined in the <i>Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site</i> (Jones 2000) (see Appendix E). In coordination with BLM, ORARNG will conduct annual site inspections during the growing season to ensure the success of vegetation rehabilitation on military training areas affected by tracked and wheeled vehicles (other than established trails and roads).	High	High	ITAM	AGI-ENV
Water Resources Monitoring AGI-ENV staff will inspect and document the integrity and functionality of water guzzlers for wildlife every three years.	Low	Medium	AGI-ENV	AGI-ENV
Wetlands Monitoring AGI-ENV will survey wetlands in areas used for military training every three years using photo points to document the conditions of and any alterations to wetlands. The survey will document the cause of alterations (e.g., loss of inflow from lining of the canal, destruction of vegetation from public use or military training).	Medium	Medium	AGI-ENV	AGI-ENV
Terrestrial Habitat Monitoring Continue to implement the Army's LCITA program, as funding permits, in order to monitor ecological status, plant species composition, disturbance, and species diversity of the BTC's terrestrial habitat communities. Implement the monitoring management goals and objectives outlined in <i>Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site</i> (Jones 2000) for maintaining and improving rangeland health (refer to Appendix E for monitoring management goals and objectives). BTC range control will review training activities for compliance with management strategies.	High	High	ITAM	AGI-ENV
Wildlife Monitoring AGI-ENV will conduct monitoring of vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects in accordance with the <i>Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site</i> (Jones 2000) (see Appendix E). Coordinate with the BLM and ODFW to determine an appropriate wildlife monitoring program, as stated in the <i>Inventory and Evaluation of Vertebrate Fauna at the BTC 1999-2000</i> (Reiter et al. 2000).	High	High	ITAM	AGI-ENV
Special Natural Areas Monitoring AGI-ENV will conduct monitoring of vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects in accordance with the <i>Inventory and Evaluation of Vertebrate Fauna at the BTC 1999-2000</i> (Reiter et al. 2000).	High	High	ITAM	AGI-ENV

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents the following timing preference:
 High priority - Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).
 Medium priority - Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).
 Low priority - Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

Funding priority ranking is based on the likelihood of receiving funds for such a project/program as follows:
 High priority - Program likely will be funded due to federal, state, or military requirement.
 Medium priority - Program likely will be funded due to military policy.
 Low priority - Program will be funded only if discretionary funds are available.

N/A - Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Potential funding sources: AGI-ENV, BLM, ODFW, and ITAM

Table 6-3
 Summary of Monitoring Methods, Priority of Implementation and Funding, and Potential Funding Sources (*continued*)

Monitoring Method	Funding Priority	Implementation Priority	Potential Funding Source	Responsible Party
Special Status Species Monitoring ORANNG will develop a monitoring program for federally threatened or endangered species or their habitat if identified through surveys.	High	High	ITAM	AGI-ENV
Livestock Grazing Monitoring BTC range control will review training activities for compliance with management strategies. BTC range control will conduct bi-annual surveys of training lands to ensure fencing is in good condition.	N/A N/A	High Medium	N/A N/A	BTC BTC
Pest Monitoring AGI-ENV will review the annual submission of the pest management plan to evaluate its effectiveness.	N/A	Medium	N/A	AGI-ENV

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents the following timing preference:

High priority - Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).

Medium priority - Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).

Low priority - Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

Funding priority ranking is based on the likelihood of receiving funds for such a project/program as follows:

High priority - Program likely will be funded due to federal, state, or military requirement.

Medium priority - Program likely will be funded due to military policy.

Low priority - Program will be funded only if discretionary funds are available.

N/A - Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Potential funding sources: AGI-ENV, BLM, ODFW, and ITAM

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SECTION 7

ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES

This section describes the environmental consequences that would likely occur from implementing either Alternative 1, an ecosystem-based INRMP using adaptive management, or the No Action Alternative. Management strategies included in each alternative are outlined in Table 7-1. Each environmental resource is presented in the same sequence as in Section 3, followed by a discussion of the impacts of either alternative. Both alternatives are compared to existing conditions (Section 3) to determine if direct or indirect impacts would result from implementing them. In addition, potential cumulative effects of both alternatives are disclosed in Section 7.18.

For each resource, impact analyses use different criteria to define adverse or beneficial impacts. Similarly, different criteria are used to define significance thresholds for adverse impacts. Criteria that were used to assess each alternative's adverse or beneficial impacts (if applicable) on resources are identified at the beginning of each resource section below. Significance thresholds for adverse impacts are also identified. If appropriate, impacts are also identified as short-term or long-term. Short-term is defined as the transition period for implementing the high priority actions within the management plan. This term is expected to be about three years.

Implementation priorities for each alternative were determined by the following criteria:

- High priority— Legally required activities or actions deemed important to the military mission, ecology, or personnel safety. This includes actions required by the BLM as part of land use agreements with the ORARNG to continue military training at the BTC. These actions would be ongoing or would be expected to be implemented within the next three years, depending on the availability of funding.
- Medium priority— Compliance or stewardship actions that need to be implemented in time to meet the established deadlines defined in the INRMP or within the next six years, depending on the availability of funding.

- Low priority— Activities and projects that enhance natural resources but that are not specifically required by law or military mission needs. These activities and projects are likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available and with shared resources from other agencies or entities.

The primary difference between Alternative 1 and the No Action Alternative is the management philosophy and priority for implementing specific management tools and strategies. The general management models for both alternatives are discussed in Section 2.2.3; the priorities for implementing specific management tools under the alternatives are summarized in Table 7-1.

7.1 LAND USE

Land uses at the BTC include the developed and undeveloped areas discussed in Section 3.1. Beneficial impacts are those that would result in promotion of the designated purpose of land uses, maintenance of grazing allotment integrity, and insurance of continued compatibility among adjacent land uses and public land users. Adverse impacts on land use include conflicts with established land uses in the area, disruption or division of established land use configurations, substantial changes in existing land uses, or inconsistencies with adopted regional land use plans. Adverse impacts are judged to be significant if they result in noncompliance with regulatory standards, plans, or policies. Otherwise, the significance is based on the degree of harm the impacts could cause to people or the environment. In general, any change in land use that reduces the existing or potential beneficial uses of the land is considered significant.

7.1.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing the management strategies under Alternative 1 would have no significant adverse effects on land use and would be largely beneficial to both developed and undeveloped uses. Management strategies proposed under this alternative, especially those related to the support of military training, livestock grazing, outdoor recreation management, and wildlife resources, would promote the designated purpose of developed and undeveloped land uses at the military training site. Undeveloped lands are used for multiple uses, including military training, livestock grazing, and outdoor recreation. The high priority given to educating military personnel on maintaining the integrity of grazing allotments (e.g., closing gates after entering and exiting an area) would increase the likelihood that grazing would occur only in designated areas and would minimize damage caused by stray livestock. Raising the priority of informing the public of training exercises would better ensure safe public use of undeveloped lands by supplying users with better information. In addition, specific management strategies would ensure continued compatibility among adjacent land uses and public land users, would establish a priority for proposed actions, and would identify responsible agencies or entities at the BTC.

Table 7-1
Summary of Management Strategies and Priority of Implementation by Alternative

Management Strategy/Recommendation	PRIORITY		
	Alternative 1: Ecosystem- based INRM	No Action	
<p>Soil Management</p> <p>Annually rehabilitate vegetation on military training areas affected by tracked and wheeled vehicles (other than established trails and roads), in part to stabilize soil resources. The BLM and ORARNG would coordinate to identify disturbed areas requiring revegetation. These areas would be seeded annually in the fall or winter or both at a rate of 12 pounds per acre or per site-specific BLM prescription. Seeds would be broadcast or sowed using a rangeland drill with a native seed mixture approved by the BLM. <i>Location:</i> This action would be required in Training Areas A and B where wheeled or tracked vehicles are allowed off established roads and trails.</p> <p>Request funding to obtain a water truck for use on graded roads prior to and during military training exercises involving wheeled or tracked vehicles; the truck can be retrofitted with emergency fire-fighting equipment during fire season. <i>Location:</i> The truck would spray all roads planned for training activities involving wheeled or tracked vehicles.</p> <p>Require military personnel using the BTC for training to adhere strictly to the following military regulations concerning the use, transportation, and disposal of petroleum products, oils, and lubricants in the field:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORARNG Pamphlet 200-1, Chapter 11: Response to Spills and Notification of Reporting Requirements • ORARNG Regulation 210-6: Installation Spill Contingency Plan; • ORARNG Regulation 420-47: Hazardous Waste Management Plan; and • Draft Safety, Fire and Emergency Services Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures (Hazardous Materials Response Procedures). 	High	High	High
<p>Water Resources Management</p> <p>Maintain current water conservation measures to minimize any potential waste of groundwater-produced potable water.</p> <p>Maintain the integrity and functionality of the water guzzlers for wildlife. Consider adding additional water guzzlers for wildlife, as funding and time constraints allow. <i>Location:</i> ORARNG would coordinate with the ODFW and BLM to determine the best location for any new guzzlers.</p>	High Medium	High Low	High Low
<p>Wetlands Management</p> <p>Conduct a wetland survey for any potential new or remnant ephemeral or perennial wetland resources at the BTC. <i>Location:</i> This action would be required on all lands within the BTC that are adjacent to the canal and used for military training.</p> <p>Prohibit any alteration or destruction of any identified wetlands by military training activities, except those activities limited to pedestrian use.</p>	Medium	Medium	Low
	High	High	High

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents a timing preference and does not reflect how well the strategy would be in fulfilling the goals and objectives based on the means of implementation under each alternative.

High priority - Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).

Medium priority - Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).

Low priority - Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

N/A - Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Table 7-1
Summary of Management Strategies and Priority of Implementation by Alternative (continued)

	PRIORITY	
	Alternative 1: Ecosystem- based INRMP	No Action
<p>Management Strategy/Recommendation</p> <p>Encourage the BLM to conduct discussions with the NUID to determine if it is feasible to preserve some of the seepage areas that have produced wetland habitat adjacent to the North Unit Main Canal, provided no adverse impacts to military training result from this action.</p> <p>Location: This action would be required in all wetland areas along the canal (that are used for military training) as identified by the ONHP (Kagan 1993) and discussed in Section 3.8.</p> <p>Support federal mitigation policy of avoidance, minimization, and compensation for any wetland losses.</p>	Medium	High
<p>Terrestrial Habitats Management</p> <p>When conducting maneuvers off road or when not using designated assembly areas, unit commanders would follow the guidelines written in the Standard Operating Procedures. The units will be required to provide necessary information to OMD/ORARNG to facilitate preparation of an environmental checklist when requesting the use of the training site. Guidelines would include such things as the following (and could be changed to address unforeseen issues, concerns, or opportunities):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disperse vehicles and equipment to avoid areas with heavy shrub and tree cover and to avoid excessive concentrations in small areas. • Locate assembly areas near existing roads. Only use existing roads to access all assembly areas. • Prohibit convoys or administrative vehicle movements off road. • Avoid the use of column formations and all sharp turns with tracked vehicles. • Use areas dominated by grasses for intensive maneuvers, column formations, and sharp turns, but only as necessary. <p>Excavate fighting positions only in designated areas and with prior BLM and BTC range control approval.</p> <p>Prohibit trash and refuse associated with military training from being dumped or burned at the BTC and require troops to remove trash and refuse at the end of training.</p> <p>Prohibit live vegetation from being used or cut for use as troop camouflage.</p> <p>Prohibit new roads or trails from being constructed without prior approval of the BLM and the BTC range control.</p> <p>Annually grade all roads that have been used by tracked military vehicles by pulling the excess road material to the center of the roadway (thereby establishing a crowned running surface) with as much soil moisture present as possible.</p> <p>The BTC and ORARNG would repair and rehabilitate damage to rangelands from military training. Rehabilitation measures would follow those outlined under Soils Management.</p> <p>To remove nonnative plant propagules, all military vehicles entering the BTC for training, except those stationed at Brett Hall or COUTES, would be washed before use on training lands to remove all dirt, mud, and vegetative material from tracks, wheel wells, tires, and under carriage. These activities will not occur until funding is available to construct a facility.</p> <p>In cooperation with the BLM, require the BTC to survey dirt roads used by the military and the public for inclusion in a potential road maintenance plan. Location: This action would be required on all lands within the BTC.</p>	High High High High High High High High High High	High High High High High High High High High High Medium

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents a timing preference and does not reflect how well the strategy would be in fulfilling the goals and objectives based on the means of implementation under each alternative.

High priority = Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).

Medium priority = Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).

Low priority = Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

N/A = Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Table 7-1
Summary of Management Strategies and Priority of Implementation by Alternative (continued)

	PRIORITY		
	Alternative 1: Ecosystem- based INRMP	High	No Action
Management Strategy/ Recommendation	High	Medium	Medium
Harden established assembly and vehicle staging areas, as deemed necessary and within funding constraints, with gravel to reduce windblown emissions, rehabilitation costs, and potential for invasion by non-native plants. Other sites may be used for assembly and staging only after approval by the BTC and BLM.	High	Medium	High
Areas of disturbed soil would be surveyed for noxious weeds. Noxious weeds would be eradicated by actively removing plants.			
Wildlife Management			
Conduct a biodiversity survey prior to developing the 2007-2011 INRMP for the BTC in order to analyze and monitor environmental trends derived from the 2002-2006 INRMP. <i>Location:</i> This action would be required on all lands within the BTC.	Medium	Low	Low
Coordinate with the BLM to conduct a survey on antelope use of the BTC. <i>Location:</i> This action will be required on all lands within the BTC.	Medium	Low	Low
Coordinate with the BLM to conduct surveys to determine where bat species are residing and whether sage grouse or pygmy rabbits are present.	Medium	Low	Low
<i>Location:</i> This action will be required on all lands within the BTC.			
Coordinate with the BLM and ODFW to assess the need for developing a pronghorn antelope management plan for the BTC.	Medium	Low	Low
Coordinate with the BLM to identify potential areas for habitat enhancement projects, such as vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects. Conduct vegetation manipulation and revegetation projects would be conducted in an irregular pattern to create a vegetation mosaic. This would allow for a variety of vegetative successional stages and a corresponding variety of habitats for wildlife. Data from the Army's LCTA program would be used to identify enhancement areas. <i>Location:</i> Any areas within the BTC could be identified for enhancement; however, emphasis would likely be placed on areas with important vegetation communities, such as old growth western juniper and bitterbrush shrubland (see Figure 3-6).	Medium	Low	Low
Assess the feasibility and effectiveness of using prescribed fire by consulting with the BLM to determine whether or not a prescribed burn management plan is necessary.	Low	Low	Low
Special Natural Areas Management			
AGI-ENV would instruct BTC range control how to identify bitterbrush and would brief them on where bitterbrush-dominated areas are located. All military assembly areas, bivouacs, mess, and latrine sites would be located more than 30 feet from any bitterbrush and in such a way that no new roads or trails are created.	High	Low	Low
BTC range control would brief military personnel not to remove old growth western juniper.			
Coordinate with the BLM to identify potential areas for enhancement. <i>Location:</i> This action would be required in areas mapped in Figure 3-6 as western juniper alliance and bitterbrush shrubland alliance.	Medium	Low	Low
Special Status Species Management			
Survey the BTC for federally threatened or endangered species identified in Table 3-4. Surveys would be conducted in three-year intervals.	High	High	High
<i>Location:</i> This action would be required on all lands within the BTC with suitable habitat.			

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents a timing preference and does not reflect how well the strategy would be in fulfilling the goals and objectives based on the means of implementation under each alternative.

High priority = Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).

Medium priority = Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).

Low priority = Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

N/A = Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Table 7-1
 Summary of Management Strategies and Priority of Implementation by Alternative (continued)

Management Strategy/Recommendation	PRIORITY	
	Alternative 1: Ecosystem- based INRMP	No Action
Develop specific measures to protect habitats within the BTC that are used by federally threatened or endangered species identified during surveys.	High	High
Livestock Grazing Management Inform military personnel of the presence and potential location of livestock at the BTC before military training exercises begin. Brief military personnel on proper conduct, including maintaining the structural integrity of livestock fences and keeping gates closed during grazing season. Prohibit training troops from damaging or breaching grazing allotment fencing. Continue annual meeting between the BTC and livestock grazing permittees to discuss current and potential rangeland management issues. Maintain powder-river gates installed by the BTC for use by the military and livestock grazing permittees. Coordinate with the BLM and livestock grazing permittees to install additional powder-river gates, as determined necessary and appropriate, and as funding and staffing constraints allow.	High High High Low	Medium Medium Medium Low
Pest Management Maintain compliance with all federal, military, state, and local environmental standards in regard to pesticide/herbicide use and continue to obtain necessary permits for chemical application. Continue requiring that pest management plans, as well as annual weed surveys and pest control reporting, per ORARNG Regulation 210-5. Coordinate with and obtain approval from the USFWS, ODFW, BLM, and other applicable federal or state agencies prior to pest management operations, as deemed appropriate and necessary to comply with applicable law. Prohibit applying pesticides or herbicides directly to wetlands, surface waters, or other identified sensitive areas unless use in such sites is specifically approved by the OMD, BLM, and other applicable federal and state agencies. <i>Location:</i> This action would be required in wetland areas that are located adjacent to the canal as discussed in Section 3.8. Other sensitive areas also include habitat for protected species, which would be established under management measures for threatened, endangered, and special status species. Per ORARNG Regulation 210-5, substitute biological, physical/mechanical, cultural, or ecosystem management controls in lieu of chemicals whenever logistically, environmentally, and financially feasible.	High High High High High	High High High High High
Cultural Resource Management Planning of all ground-disturbing activities will occur in consultation with Native American tribes and Oregon SHPO.	High	High
Outdoor Recreation Management. Environmental Awareness and Enforcement ORARNG would not restrict public access to the federal public lands that compose the BTC.	High	High

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents a timing preference and does not reflect how well the strategy would be in fulfilling the goals and objectives based on the means of implementation under each alternative.

High priority - Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).

Medium priority - Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).

Low priority - Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

N/A - Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Table 7-1
 Summary of Management Strategies and Priority of Implementation by Alternative (continued)

Management Strategy/Recommendation	PRIORITY		
	Alternative 1: Ecosystem- based INRM	No Action	Low
Develop and install interpretative displays at BIC public access points that explain the presence of the military, approximate training schedule, and the importance of the military mission. <i>Location:</i> This action would be required at major public access points, which include the two southern roads off Highway 126 into Training Area B, the northern road off Highway 126 into Training Area F, and the western road off Powell Butte Highway along the boundary of Training Areas D and E (Figure 3-2).	High	Low	Low
Military range patrols would inform public land users of the presence of the military without hindering access to the public lands.	Medium	Medium	Medium
Support the BLM in developing and installing displays that interpret land, water, and wildlife resource values found at the BTC. Signs would explain the destructive potential of invasive species and noxious weeds and how public land users can minimize their potential impacts on natural resources.	Medium	Low	Low
BTC would assist the BLM, Oregon State Police, and other law enforcement officials, as requested, by informing proper authorities about illegal hunting and illegal trash disposal on public lands.	Low	Low	Low
ODFW and the BLM would retain responsibility for any hunting on BTC lands (BTC does not have the authority to administer a hunting program).	Low	Low	Low
In cooperation with the BLM, install educational displays, as funding allows, about wildlife resources at the BTC; emphasize special status or sensitive species and military efforts to conserve such fauna.	Low	Low	Low
Fire Management			
Follow emergency services notification and fire evacuation procedures in the event of fire, as outlined under the BTC's draft <i>Fire, Safety, and Emergency Service Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures</i> and AR 420-90, <i>Fire and Emergency Services</i> .	High	High	High
Request funds to buy and maintain a water truck for fire-fighting purposes. Water truck would be retrofitted with equipment for dust abatement before training maneuvers with tracked and wheeled vehicles begin.	Medium	Low	Low
Consult with the BLM to determine if a prescribed burn program for the BTC would be financially feasible, politically acceptable, and beneficial to wildlife habitat and forage, biodiversity, and military training.	Low	Low	Low
Public Health and Safety Management			
Adhere strictly to the military training safety procedures, as outlined in the BIC's draft <i>Fire, Safety, and Emergency Services Annex to the BTC Standard Operating Procedures</i> .	High	High	High
Inform public of ongoing military training exercises without denying public access to public lands.	High	Medium	Medium
Design and post signs informing the public of military activities at the BTC. Include basic safety information and an approximate schedule of military training exercises. <i>Location:</i> This action would be required at major public access points, which include the two southern roads off Highway 126 into Training Area B, the northern road off Highway 126 into Training Area F, and the western road off Powell Butte Highway along the boundary of Training Areas D and E (Figure 3-2).	High	Low	Low

Notes:

The ranking of management strategies represents a timing preference and does not reflect how well the strategy would be in fulfilling the goals and objectives based on the means of implementation under each alternative.

High priority = Program to be continued or likely to be implemented within the next three years (fiscal years 2002 - 2005).

Medium priority = Likely to be implemented within the next six years (fiscal years 2002 - 2008).

Low priority = Likely to be implemented when staffing and funding is available.

N/A = Not applicable. Generally applies to operating procedures or policies.

Endangered, threatened, and special status species management strategies (such as field surveys to identify the presence of species or sensitive habitats) could have a minor impact on livestock grazing, outdoor recreation, and the military mission at the BTC. Identifying federal or state species of concern could prompt the BLM to curtail such activities in specially designated areas. This effect would likely not be significant because the potential species of concern are typically localized (e.g., bats that reside in lava caves not typically used by the military or in areas that are already considered off-limits to military training).

7.1.2 No Action Alternative

Selection of the No Action Alternative would not result in any change in land use, and no impacts would occur. All management strategies being implemented under the BLM's Resource Management Plan cover compliance-based regulations and management techniques (BLM 1989). As a result, there would be no significant impacts to land use under the No Action Alternative.

7.2 FACILITIES

Facilities include transportation systems (i.e., roads), water supply systems, wastewater treatment and disposal, stormwater collection, solid waste collection and disposal, power services, and natural gas pipelines. Adverse impacts include the loss or reduction of these systems and services. Impact significance is judged on the magnitude of loss or service reduction, which is judged to be significant if it increases the potential for injury or loss of life, damage to the environment, or major economic loss. In addition, an action that would not meet existing regulatory requirements or that is inconsistent with existing plans or policies could result in a significant adverse impact.

7.2.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing the management strategies under Alternative 1 would have no significant adverse effects on facilities. The transportation or facilities changes recommended under this alternative would be inventorying roads in cooperation with the BLM and annually grading all roads that have been used by tracked military vehicles. The military is prohibited from constructing new roads, unless prior consent is obtained, under the BLM's Resource Management Plan.

7.2.2 No Action Alternative

Selection of the No Action Alternative would result in no change to facilities at the BTC, and there would be no impacts.

7.3 CLIMATE

Adverse climate impacts include a change in local or regional climate. Impact significance is judged on the magnitude of such change, which is judged to be significant if it increases the potential for environmental damage.

7.3.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing Alternative 1 would have no foreseeable impacts on local or regional climate.

7.3.2 No Action Alternative

Implementing the No Action Alternative would have no foreseeable impacts on local or regional climate.

7.4 GEOLOGICAL RESOURCES

Geologic resources include soils, mineral deposits, or unique landscape features; soils are addressed separately in the following section. Adverse geologic impacts include exposure to geologic hazards (e.g., seismicity, slope failure, land subsidence) and loss of or reduced access to geologic resources. Impact significance is judged on the hazard's magnitude and resource's value or uniqueness. Exposure to a geologic hazard is judged to be significant if it increases the potential for injury or loss of life, damage to the environment, or major economic loss. Examples of potentially significant impacts to geologic resources include loss of agricultural soils or soils that support valuable habitat; loss of access to mineral or geothermal resources; and erosion or degradation of a unique geologic feature. In addition, an action that would not meet existing regulatory requirements or that is inconsistent with existing plans or policies could result in a significant impact.

7.4.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Selection of Alternative 1 would not affect geologic resources other than soils, which are discussed in the following section. For example, there would be no increase in seismic hazards because of existing or proposed land management practices. Therefore, no impacts to geologic resources would result.

7.4.2 No Action Alternative

Implementing the No Action Alternative would have no foreseeable impacts on geologic resources.

7.5 SOIL RESOURCES

Soil resources are a subset of geological resources. Potential adverse impacts to soil resources include erosion, loss of soil fertility and fecundity, and contamination. In general, the land management strategies of the INRMP are intended to protect soil fertility and fecundity, as well as maintain the maximum long-term benefits from soils. Therefore, land management strategies are expected to result in beneficial impacts on soil resources.

7.5.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Soil management strategies implemented under Alternative 1 would focus on reducing soil erosion by wind and water, maintaining adequate vegetation and native ground cover to prevent soil loss, and implementing a monitoring program to evaluate the success of management strategies and to provide information needed to support the adaptive management program. Since graded roads are typically areas where vegetation has been removed or severely degraded, these areas would be subject to wind erosion. The high priority given to watering graded roads prior to and during military training under Alternative 1 would minimize wind erosion due to disturbing these areas. The impacts of these strategies on soils are expected to be beneficial.

7.5.2 No Action Alternative

Under the No Action Alternative, existing management programs are assumed to continue. The No Action Alternative is similar to Alternative 1, with less emphasis on monitoring vegetative cover to prevent soil erosion by wind and water. Existing damage caused by military training would continue to be corrected, in coordination with the BLM. However, maintaining the management status quo by implementing this alternative could also have minor adverse impacts to soil resources because current management actions to rehabilitate soil resources affected by military training activities lack structure and synergy, which could further damage this resource. Under the No Action Alternative, soils of the BTC would likely be maintained at their present condition, with more limited stewardship-based management strategies being implemented.

7.6 WATER RESOURCES

Water resources include surface water and groundwater. Adverse impacts to water resources include changes in water quality, changes in the quantity of water available for existing or potential beneficial uses, changes in hydraulic conditions (e.g., velocity of flow and channel capacity), and changes in the potential for flooding. Adverse impacts are judged to be significant if they result in noncompliance with regulatory standards, plans, or policies. Otherwise, the significance is based on the degree of harm the impacts could cause to people or the environment. In general, any degradation of water quality that reduces the existing or potential beneficial uses of the water is considered significant. The significance of reducing the quantity of water available for beneficial uses depends on the size, timing, duration, and permanence of the reduction. The significance of changes in hydraulic conditions depends on the context in which the change occurs. For example, increased flooding potential is deemed significant if it increases the 100-year flood zone or if it results in increased potential for injury, loss of life, or damage to structures.

7.6.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Water resources management strategies are of two types—those designed to maintain existing groundwater quality and those designed to improve available water sources for wildlife. The ecosystem approach encourages more diverse water use patterns than under current conditions, with greater ability to adapt to changes in water availability.

As the BTC is hydrologically undeveloped, surface water resources are limited to the North Unit Main Canal and artificial water guzzlers constructed for use by wildlife resources. The BTC maintains no managerial or administrative control over the irrigation canal. Under Alternative 1, the ORARNG could maintain and potentially enhance, depending on available funding and cooperation with BLM and ODFW, water guzzlers used by wildlife resources in areas where this action would not restrict future military training. Maintaining or adding new water guzzlers would be beneficial to wildlife resources, including pronghorn antelope, resident and migratory birds, and myotis (i.e., bat) species that could occur at the BTC. Also under Alternative 1, groundwater resources would benefit from maintaining water conservation practices to protect and conserve these water resources. Implementing Alternative 1 would likely

not have any impact, either adverse or beneficial, on potential flooding, general hydraulic conditions, overland flow patterns, or surface water quality.

7.6.2 No Action Alternative

Under the No Action Alternative, the BTC would continue to implement conservation measures aimed at protecting and conserving groundwater resources. Surface water resources (artificial water guzzlers) would be maintained only as funding and staffing constraints allowed. Cooperation with the BLM to determine the need for additional water guzzlers for wildlife resources would not be pursued. Consequently, implementing the No Action Alternative would likely result in considerably less beneficial impacts to water resources over the long term.

7.7 VEGETATION

Impacts to vegetation communities and habitats could be adverse or beneficial. The significance of impacts is assessed based on the degree to which they affect the functions and values of habitat types and associated vegetation. Adverse impacts to vegetation communities are those that introduce noxious weeds, that degrade or eliminate native or rare habitat, and that reduce habitat types considered important for the military mission and natural resources management at the BTC. Beneficial impacts include those that rehabilitate native habitats and vegetation communities.

7.7.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing the management strategies contained in the INRMP would not result in any adverse impacts, but would instead benefit vegetative communities, including special natural areas, at the BTC. Many of the prescribed strategies (such as hardening select staging areas and bivouac sites) would conserve and rehabilitate vegetative cover at the military training site. Not only is this impact beneficial to the native vegetation of the BTC, but it also provides for soil stabilization, dust abatement, and noxious weed propagation reduction.

Monitoring methods under Alternative 1 require monitoring the baseline ecological condition of existing vegetative communities and assessing the change in this resource over time. Continuing to implement the Army's LCTA program allows the ORARNG to aid the BLM in determining the composition, spatial distribution, quality, and condition of vegetation at the BTC. This knowledge would likely prove invaluable for the future management of the public lands that compose the military training site. Managing and restoring disturbed vegetative communities with native seed also would be beneficial to native wildlife resources that inhabit or migrate through the BTC.

7.7.2 No Action Alternative

Implementing the No Action Alternative would have some beneficial impacts to vegetation. The Army's LCTA program would continue to be implemented under this alternative and would result in the same beneficial effects as described for Alternative 1. All of the compliance-based strategies, such as restoring sites disturbed by military training, would be implemented under the No Action Alternative. Beneficial stewardship strategies would be implemented only when funding and staffing are made

available. Consequently, stewardship strategies proposed in Alternative 1 (such as hardening select staging areas and bivouac sites) would not be implemented, and, as a result, the net benefits to vegetation would be less than those described for Alternative 1.

7.8 WETLANDS

Adverse impacts to wetlands are those that result in the destruction or modification of wetlands. Impacts could include activities that destroy or greatly alter the hydrology, soils, vegetation, or wildlife of wetlands. Some examples of adverse impacts include filling or excavating in wetlands, draining ditches through pumping or excavation, or mowing, plowing, burning, or otherwise removing plants and vegetation. Short-term adverse impacts, such as burning or mowing, could become beneficial in the long term. Adverse impacts are judged to be significant if they result in noncompliance with existing regulatory standards, plans, or policies, such as Section 404 of the CWA or EO 11990. The significance of impacts to wetlands is assessed based on the degree to which they affect the functions and values of wetlands. Beneficial impacts include rehabilitation or enhancement of wetlands or anything that improves the functions and values of a wetland.

7.8.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing the management strategies under Alternative 1 would have no significant adverse effects on wetlands. Stewardship strategies proposed under Alternative 1 could identify perennial or ephemeral wetland resources, however. Implementing Alternative 1 would require the military to survey lands proposed to be used for military training, near the North Unit Main Canal, to determine the spatial and temporal nature of wetland resources created when the concrete lining of the irrigation canal is completed. This aspect would prove to be beneficial to any identified wetlands resources. Additional management measures could be developed to help the BLM protect and conserve such resources, per federal, military, and state guidelines and regulations.

Other management strategies proposed under Alternative 1 would enhance potential wetlands by abating nonpoint sources of pollution and by reducing invasive species when NUID finishes lining the canal. The water quality in wetlands could be improved by reducing nonpoint sources of sediment and pesticides. Sediment loads in wetlands could be reduced by hardening staging areas and bivouac sites. Many strategies emphasize increasing vegetative cover with perennial and annual grasses with native plants, when appropriate, which could protect wetland areas from encroachment by invasive nonnative species.

7.8.2 No Action Alternative

Implementing the No Action Alternative would have no adverse impact on potential wetland resources because compliance-based management strategies are the status quo. However, many of the beneficial strategies proposed in Alternative 1 would not be implemented, and, as a result, the net benefits to potential wetlands resources would be less than for Alternative 1.

7.9 WILDLIFE

Significant adverse impacts to wildlife are those impacts that substantially affect species or habitats (including those that are restricted at a regional scale) that serve as concentrated breeding or foraging areas and that are limited in availability, or habitats that support substantial concentrations of one or more sensitive species. Beneficial impacts are those that protect and conserve wildlife communities.

7.9.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing an ecosystem-based INRMP would result in beneficial impacts to wildlife communities at the BTC. The management strategies proposed are designed to protect and conserve wildlife communities through sound vegetation management and improved available water resources. These strategies would not have any significant adverse impact on wildlife. Alternative 1 could have the following beneficial results:

- Increasing the amount of native shrubs and forbs through the vegetation rehabilitation program;
- Improving the water resources by maintaining existing water guzzlers and adding new ones, per funding and staffing constraints, which would benefit both terrestrial and avian species with no negative impacts to the military mission; and
- Adding inventories and surveys to determine the presence of resident or migratory species of concern at the BTC.

Implementing an ecosystem-based INRMP would likely result in a net beneficial impact to resident and migratory wildlife resources that inhabit, forage on, or breed at the BTC.

7.9.2 No Action Alternative

Implementing the No Action Alternative would have limited beneficial impacts to wildlife. The BTC currently follows wildlife management guidelines outlined in the BLM's *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan* (BLM 1989). These wildlife management methods include compliance-based strategies, such as endangered species habitat protection, use of native plant species in rehabilitation efforts, and management of military training to avoid wildfires. Beneficial stewardship strategies under Alternative 1 would be implemented only under the No Action Alternative as funding and staffing are made available. As a result, the net benefits to wildlife would be less than those described for Alternative 1.

7.10 SPECIAL STATUS SPECIES

Significant adverse impacts are those that substantially affect species (or their habitat) listed as threatened or endangered by federal resource agencies and other species specifically protected by applicable laws. Beneficial impacts could include surveying and inventorying for special status species or protecting or conserving a species or its habitat.

7.10.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing an ecosystem-based INRMP would result in potentially beneficial impacts to special status species. Alternative 1 would have the following beneficial results:

- Surveying for threatened and endangered species would determine the presence or location of such species that could inhabit or migrate through the BTC; and
- Continuing to manage noxious weeds would likely improve the quality of native vegetation for native species.

7.10.2 No Action Alternative

Implementing the No Action Alternative would have no adverse or beneficial impacts on special status species. BTC's current special status species management methods include all of the compliance-based strategies, such as endangered species habitat protection, discussed in the *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan*. However, the beneficial strategies proposed in Alternative 1 would not be implemented. As a result, the net benefits to special status species would be less than those described for Alternative 1.

7.11 CULTURAL RESOURCES

Adverse impacts to cultural resources could result from implementing ground-disturbing activities, modifying and altering historic structures, causing visual intrusion on a historic setting, or collecting artifacts without authorization. The significance of an impact is based on the degree to which actions would alter the depositional or architectural integrity of a given cultural resource. Beneficial impacts include protection of cultural resources.

7.11.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementation of the INRMP would result in the identification of cultural resources on all BTC lands. Additionally, the plan could result in beneficial effects to the protection of cultural resources from erosion control strategies. The plan requires that military personnel be briefed on areas off-limits to training, including those with known cultural and historical value. Therefore, no adverse effects are expected. Coordination with the Oregon SHPO has basically been done through Oregon SHPO's review of and formal comments to the ICRMP.

7.11.2 No Action Alternative

The No Action Alternative would result in no changes to existing conditions.

7.12 AIR QUALITY

Adverse impacts to air quality are those that result in degradation of air quality, such as increased vehicle emissions or generation of airborne pollutants. The significance of impacts to air quality is assessed based on the degree to which they degrade air quality. Beneficial impacts include reducing windblown emissions such as dust.

7.12.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Alternative 1 would have no significant adverse effects on air quality because none of the management strategies would involve generation of airborne pollutants. Alternative 1 would likely have the beneficial impact of reducing windblown emissions (i.e., dust) by restoring vegetative cover, hardening some staging areas and bivouac sites, spraying water on dirt roads prior to training exercises, and conserving soil resources. Implementing Alternative 1 would not require an air conformity determination pursuant to the CAA.

7.12.2 No Action Alternative

The No Action Alternative would not result in any net increase in air emissions over existing conditions, and there would be no direct or indirect impacts to air quality.

7.13 NOISE

Noise impacts include increases in sound levels, exceedances of acceptable land use compatibility guidance, or changes in public acceptance (e.g., complaints about noise). The significance of noise level impacts is assessed based on the degree to which they increase existing noise levels or if impacts result in a substantial increase in noise levels as compared to federal, state, or local regulations.

7.13.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing Alternative 1 would have no foreseeable impacts on noise emanating from the BTC. Potential effects are precluded by the fact that the proposed action does not involve any activities that would impact noise conditions, such as (1) changes in military equipment, (2) increases in the number or location of personnel, or (3) increase in military operations. Therefore, there would be no effects regarding noise levels or sound quality.

7.13.2 No Action Alternative

No direct or indirect noise effects would result from the No Action Alternative because there would be no change to existing conditions.

7.14 PUBLIC HEALTH AND SAFETY

Adverse impacts to public health and safety are those that result in decrease or loss of protection of military personnel and other public land users. The significance of impacts to public health and safety is assessed based on the degree to which impacts threaten public health and safety. Beneficial impacts to public health and safety include dust abatement and wildlife control.

7.14.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing the management strategies under Alternative 1 would have no significant adverse effects on public health and safety and would continue to adequately protect military personnel and other public land users.

Federal, military, and state regulations strictly regulate the use, storage, and transportation of hazardous material. This regulatory aspect would not be altered or

amended under ecosystem management. Likewise, no additional hazardous waste products would be generated. Pesticides would continue to be applied on noxious weeds at a rate and volume similar to current conditions, as conditions warrant; therefore no impacts are expected.

Implementing Alternative 1 would likely beneficially affect dust abatement and wildfire control. Managing natural resources at the BTC conserves the vegetative cover of the BTC, thereby reducing windblown soil and sand. Adhering to the BTC risk management plan reduces the chances for wildfire. This aspect is important for the military, public land users, and the local community. Furthermore, the stewardship-based management strategies proposed for implementation under Alternative 1 would provide for public safety by informing public land users of the presence of the military at the BTC through signs.

7.14.2 No Action Alternative

The No Action Alternative would result in no foreseeable adverse impacts to the public health and safety program at the BTC because the current management strategies would continue to be implemented. All aspects of the public health and safety program would continue to receive the highest consideration by the ORARNG.

7.15 SOCIOECONOMIC RESOURCES

Impacts to socioeconomic resources include changes in employment, local income, population, housing, or schools. The significance of impacts is assessed based on the degree to which impacts change the existing conditions of employment, local income, population, housing, or schools.

7.15.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Implementing the compliance and stewardship management strategies under Alternative 1 would have no significant adverse effects on socioeconomic resources. Under Alternative 1, employment and local income would not likely be affected. Socioeconomic resources in the surrounding communities would remain relatively constant.

7.15.2 No Action Alternative

The No Action Alternative would not result in any change to the socioeconomic resources at the BTC and surrounding communities.

7.16 ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

Adverse impacts to environmental justice include disproportionate impacts to low-income or minority populations.

7.16.1 Alternative 1: Ecosystem-based INRMP

Under environmental justice, water and other biological resource issues are not relevant because impacts related to these resources (e.g., flooding, drought, or wildfire) would not disproportionately affect any one group. Air quality impacts occur over a large area and would not disproportionately affect any one group. Likewise, hazardous materials

issues would not disproportionately affect any one group. No significant impacts to visual or cultural resources were identified; therefore, no disproportionately high or adverse impact would affect any one group.

There would be no adverse impacts with respect to children's environmental health and safety under EO 13045, as the health and safety of all local citizens is already considered under the general health and safety guidelines for the military training site.

Implementing the management strategies under Alternative 1 would have no adverse effects on issues concerning environmental justice. Under Alternative 1, existing demographics and poverty levels would likely remain constant. There is no evidence to suggest that implementing the compliance and stewardship management strategies under Alternative 1 would result in a disproportionate impact to minority or low-income populations.

Viable and healthy natural systems, however, do allow for a greater opportunity for the local population to experience wildlife resources and to recreate in aesthetically pleasing surroundings. Implementing ecosystem management, then, could facilitate an enhanced perception of quality of life.

7.16.2 No Action Alternative

The No Action Alternative would not result in any change to issues concerning environmental justice at the BTC and surrounding communities.

7.17 CONCLUSIONS

No significant adverse environmental impacts would result from implementing either Alternative 1: the Proposed Action or the No Action Alternative. Overall, Alternative 1 would likely benefit the resources discussed in this section since natural resources management efforts would be coordinated with the BLM. The No Action Alternative would result in less benefit than Alternative 1 for some resources. Both alternatives would result in no net loss in the capability of lands to support the military mission of ORARNG. In addition, Alternative 1 would result in the following:

- Conservation and enhancement of natural resources managed by the BLM, where management actions support accomplishment of the military mission;
- Sustainable multiple use of natural resources, per BLM guidelines, which would include open public access to all resources (except those areas designated as off-limits to military use), outdoor recreation, livestock grazing, and nonconsumptive uses;
- Professional natural resources management, including protection, enhancement, and conservation of the natural resources;
- Implementation of land management practices that conserve soil and water resources, reduce reliance on chemical pesticides to control noxious

weeds, abate nonpoint pollution, minimize vegetative loss, and prevent soil erosion; and

- Identification of special status, threatened, or endangered species, emphasizing military mission requirements and interagency cooperation during consultation, species recovery planning, and management activities, in coordination with the BLM.
- Implementation of the INRMP would support military training activities and would not adversely impact the military mission.

7.18 CUMULATIVE EFFECTS

The CEQ regulations implementing the procedural provisions of NEPA define cumulative effects as follows:

The impact on the environment (that) results from the incremental impact of the action when added to other past, present, and reasonably foreseeable future actions regardless of what agency (federal or nonfederal) or person undertakes such other actions (40 CFR § 1508.7 [1997]).

Cumulative effect analysis can be approached in a variety of ways. In this document, it is approached by identifying public and private projects that are expected to be implemented during the same period as would the proposed action. Table 7-2 presents the projects that could be implemented adjacent to or near the BTC that could affect the military training site. No current actions or past projects have been identified that would be interdependent with the proposed action and result in adverse impacts.

The BTC is adjacent to the Redmond Urban Growth Boundary (UGB). Redmond Industrial Park and the Deschutes County Fairgrounds recently were developed within the UGB. The Huntington Ranch Resort is a proposed development that would likely be constructed on private lands within the public lands that compose the BTC. The Juniper Golf Course is on private lands adjacent to the BTC; the proposed action for this project would be to move and expand the golf course onto public lands.

The City of Redmond's proposed plans to extend Southwest 19th Street to a future interchange at Quarry Avenue, and potentially to Deschutes Junction, are anticipated to occur within the next five years. The proposed route is anticipated to parallel the southern UGB through some of the western portion of BTC Area A (Figure 1-1). The City of Redmond, Deschutes County, ORARNG, and the BLM would work cooperatively on such a plan so that various uses are accommodated. The proposed extension and interchange would not conflict with the goals and objectives of the INRMP to manage natural resources of the subject site in concert with military training.

Approximately 320 acres have been identified for the potential expansion of the Deschutes County Fairgrounds in the northwest corner of BTC Area A (Figure 1-1). The identified area is bounded on the east by a historic wagon road alignment. The

Table 7-2
List of Potential Cumulative Projects

Project Name	Location/Schedule	Description
UGB Community Development Plan	City of Redmond/ongoing through 2020.	City of Redmond would implement a consistent vision of development within the UGB, which encompasses a portion of Training Area A within the BTC. The BLM might consider trading a portion of the public lands that compose the BTC to Redmond within the UGB. This loss of training acreage would likely be offset by additional public lands being allotted to the military under a special use permit north of Highway 126.
Juniper Golf Course Development	City of Redmond/proposed	A proposed 18-hole golf course would be located on BLM public land in the North half of Section 32, Township 15 South, Range 13 East, Deschutes County. The course would require the use of one or more right-of-way approvals for roads and utility access across BLM-managed lands.
Deschutes County Fairgrounds Expansion	City of Redmond and Deschutes County/proposed	The existing Deschutes County Fairgrounds complex might seek to expand operations south into existing BLM lands. This project would be roughly adjacent to the proposed Juniper Golf Course.
Huntington Ranch Resort Development	BLM land/proposed	This resort complex would include a golf course and residential development. It would be located roughly three miles southeast of the proposed Juniper Golf Course and would require approval for roads and utility access across BLM lands.
Recreational Vehicle Park Development	BLM land/proposed	A recreational vehicle park is proposed for development immediately south of the Deschutes Fairgrounds.
Roberts Field Runway Expansion	City of Redmond	Elongation of existing airport runways to accommodate aircraft that cannot currently access Roberts Field.
SW 19 th Street Extension	City of Redmond/proposed	Extension of SW 19 th Street to Quarry Avenue (and a future interchange) and potentially to Deschutes Junction. Such an extension would provide a southern connection between US Highway 97 and the County Fairgrounds and the airport, and would also provide a long-term solution to the realignment of US Highway 97.
Smith Rock – Pilot Butte State Parks Pedestrian Trail Development	BLM land/concept stage	Several community and government organizations have proposed to the BLM the development of a pedestrian trail linking Smith Rock and Pilot Butte State Parks. It is anticipated that such a trail would be located primarily on BLM lands and, where possible, along existing canal rights-of-way on BLM land.
Deschutes County Bicycle and Pedestrian Path Development	Along the North Unit Main Canal/proposed	The Deschutes County Bicycle and Pedestrian Advisory Committee has proposed the development of a pedestrian/nonmotorized trail along the irrigation canal.

City of Redmond, Deschutes County, and the BLM are working cooperatively to determine if the identified area is appropriate for expansion of the fairgrounds. If it is determined that the area is appropriate, the proposed use of the area west of the historic wagon road would not conflict with the goals and objectives of the INRMP to manage natural resources of the subject site in concert with military training. The

environmental impact of converting land currently in open space use to fairgrounds use will be addressed by the BLM and the City of Redmond as the proposal proceeds.

The City of Redmond's proposal to extend Southwest 19th Street to the south, and the Deschutes County proposal to expand the fairgrounds, include property that is currently within or adjacent to lands currently subject to the special use permit issued by the BLM for the BTC. The proximity of these lands to the Redmond urban area, other existing or proposed urban-type land uses, and identified cultural resources renders them to be of marginal use for military training. Therefore, although execution of these proposals would reduce the current area of land available for military training, the logical expansion of the urban area in this manner would not unduly affect the operations of the ORARNG or limit lands for military training.

All of these proposed and recently completed construction projects would result or have resulted in the conversion of many acres of big sagebrush steppe and juniper woodlands, typical of the vegetation of the BTC (BLM 2000). Implementing the INRMP with any other proposed management actions at the BTC would not result in any significant adverse impacts to local natural or cultural resources, and there would not be incompatibility between military training activities and the proposed projects. Public access would continue to be provided at the BTC. Implementing other proposed management actions under the No Action Alternative could result in increased use of public lands at the BTC. Implementation of the INRMP would not result in any additional increase to public land use beyond the increases expected under the No Action Alternative. Implementing the INRMP would not affect the amount of training at the BTC, so issues such as transportation would not be affected by the INRMP. The potential for beneficial impacts is substantially increased by implementing the INRMP. No details for substantially increasing the level of the military mission or training schedule at the BTC have been proposed at this time; therefore, the contribution of such an action to cumulative conditions cannot be assessed.

7.19 OTHER CONSIDERATIONS

7.19.1 Irreversible or Irrecoverable Commitment of Resources

NEPA requires an analysis of significant irreversible effects. Resources that are irreversibly or irretrievably committed to a project are those that are long-term or permanent. This includes the use of nonrenewable resources, such as metal, wood, fuel, paper, and other natural or cultural resources. These resources are irretrievable in that they would be used for this project when they could have been used for other purposes. Another impact that falls under the category of the irreversible and irretrievable commitment of resources is the unavoidable destruction of natural resources that could limit the range of potential uses of that particular environment.

No irreversible or irretrievable impacts would be expected from implementing either of the alternatives. Under both alternatives, cultural resources and protected habitats (for example, wetlands and areas inhabited by threatened and endangered species) would

not be adversely affected. Likewise, both alternatives would have a negligible to beneficial effect on net consumption of resources.

7.19.2 Unavoidable Adverse Effects

NEPA requires a discussion of any adverse environmental effects that cannot be avoided. No significant adverse impacts have been identified from implementing either of the alternatives.

7.19.3 Relationship Between Short-term Uses and Long-term Productivity

NEPA requires a discussion of the relationship between short-term uses of the environment and the maintenance and enhancement of long-term productivity. Both of the alternatives would have short-term effects as the management program and management tools are implemented (as discussed in the resource sections above). These effects would be temporary and would serve to obtain the long-term goals of either management alternative. In general, implementing Alternative 1 would likely increase natural resources conservation and rehabilitation activities. Additionally, Alternative 1 would reduce chances of conflict between public land uses, would provide for public health and safety, and would provide for ecological stewardship and natural resources conservation. The No Action Alternative would maintain the status quo of the natural resources located at the BTC and would continue to maintain access to public lands for all users and provide for public health and safety.

SECTION 8

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SECTION 9

LIST OF INRMP PREPARERS AND REVIEWERS

Individuals from the BTC, ORARNG, OMD, BLM, and contractor personnel who were involved in the preparation and review of the INRMP/EA are listed below.

REVIEWERS

National Guard Bureau

Deputy Chief of Staff Operations and Training

MAJ Jack Randall

Biak Training Center

William McCaffrey, Range Control Officer

Oregon Military Department Environmental Branch (AGI-ENV)

Gerald Elliott, Environmental Program Manager

Scott Stuemke, Natural Resources Specialist

Bureau of Land Management

Steve Castillo, Forester

Mollie Chaudet, Project Manager, Upper Deschutes RMP/EIS

Ron Gregory, Archaeologist

Ron Halvorson, Botanist

Michelle McSwain, Hydrologist

Teal Purrington, Range Conservationist

Paul Schmidt, Wildlife Biologist

Ron Wortman, Realty Specialist

PREPARERS

Oregon Military Department Environmental Branch (AGI-ENV)

Greg Mitchell, Natural Resources Specialist

Tetra Tech

180 Howard Street, Suite 250
San Francisco, California 94105

David Batts
MS, Natural Resources Planning and Policy
Years of Experience: 10
(Project Manager)

Constance Callahan
JD, Environmental Law
BA, Anthropology
Years of Experience: 6
(Cultural Resources, QA/QC)

Amy Cordle
BS, Civil Engineering
Years of Experience: 8
(Air Quality)

Robert Edgerton
MS, Watershed Sciences
Years of Experience: 5
(Principal Author)

Karen Frye
BS, Political Economy of Natural Resources
Years of Experience: 12
(NEPA Compliance)

Genevieve Kaiser
MS, Energy Management and Policy
Years of Experience: 8
(Socioeconomic Resources and Environmental Justice)

Angela Nelson
BA, Biology and English
Years of Experience: 6
(Document Revision)

George Redpath
MS, Ecology
Years of Experience: 27
(Biological Resources)

Jeff Skahill
BS, Environmental Health
Years of Experience: 3
(GIS Specialist)

Randolph B. Varney
BA, Technical and Professional Writing
Years of Experience: 15
(Technical Editor)

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APPENDIX A

LEGAL LAND DESCRIPTION OF BIAK TRAINING CENTER

Section	Portion of Section	Township	Range	County (Oregon)
23	E½ SE¼			
24 and 25	All			
26	S½ S½ NE¼ NE¼ NE¼ SE¼ NW¼ NE¼ S½ SW¼ NW¼ NE¼ E½ NE¼ NW¼ NE¼	15 South	13 East	Deschutes
33 through 35	All			
36	E½ E½			
19	All (only that portion of the section south and west of Highway 126)			
20	NW¼ (only that portion of the section confined to the Clay Pit's excavation area)	15 South	14 East	Crook
30	All			
31	All (except the portion of the SW¼ located east of McCaffery Road)			
32	S½			
1 through 5	All			
7	E½ E½			
8 through 15	All			
17	All			
18	E½ E½			
19	E½			
20 through 23	All			
24	All (only that portion of the section north and west of Powell Butte Highway)	16 South	13 East	Deschutes
25	W½ NW¼ NE¼ (Only those portions of the sections north and west of Powell Butte Highway)			
26 through 29	All			
30	E½			
31	E½			
	E½ W½			
32 through 35	All			

Legal Land Description of Biak Training Center *(continued)*

Section	Portion of Section	Township	Range	County (Oregon)
5	W $\frac{1}{2}$ W $\frac{1}{2}$ E $\frac{1}{2}$			
6 and 7	All			
18	All	16 South	14 East	Crook
19	N $\frac{1}{2}$ NW $\frac{1}{4}$ SW $\frac{1}{4}$ (Only those portions of the sections north and west of Powell Butte Highway)			
1 through 3	All			
10	NE $\frac{1}{4}$	17 South	13 East	Deschutes
11	N $\frac{1}{2}$			
12	All			
6 and 7	All	17 South	14 East	Deschutes

APPENDIX B

PUBLIC OUTREACH AND DISTRIBUTION LIST

B.1 INTRODUCTION

Included in this section is a summary of the initial public scoping effort undertaken for the project and the public and agency scoping conducted during the review period of the draft INRMP/EA.

B.2 INITIAL PUBLIC OUTREACH

B.2.1 Public Notice

The ORARNG announced its intention to develop an INRMP for the BTC by publishing a public notice in local newspapers and requesting public comments. The public notice was published in the *Bend Bulletin* on Tuesday, September 26, 2000 and Sunday, October 1, 2000; the Prineville *Central Oregonian* on Tuesday, September 26, 2000; and the *Redmond Spokesman* on Thursday, September 28, 2000 and Sunday, October 1, 2000. A copy of the public notice is provided on the following page. Submittal of comments was requested by October 16, 2000.

More than 150 public notices were also directly mailed to public officials, organizations, individuals, and federal, state, and local agencies by letters dated September 25, 2000. Copies of these letters follow the public notice. The mailing list was compiled from sources that included the ORARNG and BLM. All persons and organizations thought to have a potential interest, including minority, disadvantaged, and federally recognized Native American tribes, were included. The public notice attached to the September 25, 2000 letters announced the OMD as the agency to which comments should be sent.

B.2.2 Summary of Comments Received

A total of five comments were received, which included four letters and one telephone message. One comment was from a private individual, one was from the Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project, one was provided by the Deschutes County Bicycle and Pedestrian Advisory Committee, and two comments were from public agencies (the Oregon Department of Water Resources and the city of Redmond). These letters and

telephone record are included following the public notice below. Issues concerning the INRMP and BTC that were raised in the comments are:

- Use of herbicides to control noxious weeds;
- Eradication of noxious weeds;
- Conservation of sensitive species' habitat;
- Identification of specific activities where water use would occur;
- Identification of incompatibility between military training activities and public users associated with the Juniper Golf Course, the Deschutes County Fairgrounds, land zoned for industrial uses, and proposed expansion of the runway on Roberts Field;
- Relocation of increased training activities to training areas other than Training Area A; and
- Consideration and incorporation of a pedestrian/nonmotorized recreational trail along the North Unit Main Canal.

B.2.3 Conclusions

All of the issues raised concerning the management of natural resources located at the BTC are addressed in this document. Specifically, issues related to noxious weeds are covered in Sections 3.7.4, 5.5.2, 5.11, 7.7.1, 7.14.1, and 7.17; issues related to sensitive species are covered in Sections 3.10, 5.6, 5.9, and 7.10. Water resources management is addressed in Sections 3.6, 5.4, and 7.6. Land use is addressed in Sections 3.1 and 7.1. Public use of BTC natural resources are addressed primarily in the outdoor recreation discussion (Section 5.13). Cumulative effects, which include the potential nonmotorized trail along the irrigation canal, are discussed in Section 7.18 and address regional issues that could have an effect on the management of natural resources located at the BTC.

Public Notice

The Oregon Military Department (OMD) announces their intent to prepare a joint Environmental Assessment and Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) to guide the natural resources program at the Biak Training Center (BTC) from 2002 to 2006. The BTC is used by the Oregon Army National Guard as a training center under a special use permit of the Bureau of Land Management, but is also open and accessible to the public and is used as livestock grazing. The BTC is located in central Oregon approximately 4 miles southeast of the City of Redmond.

The INRMP will address the interrelationship between military training and natural resources conservation at the BTC, as well as other current land uses, such as outdoor recreation, livestock grazing, wildlife conservation, invasive species control, and soils management. The Oregon Army National Guard uses the BTC to train military personnel for national security interests and to mobilize for civilian emergency response situations within the State of Oregon. The BTC consists of maneuver areas for the movement of both tracked and wheeled vehicles on- and off-road, digging and excavation areas, and infantry training areas. Live fire exercises are not conducted at the BTC, and most areas remain easily accessible and open to the public.

Agencies and the public are invited and encouraged to provide written comments concerning the development of the management plan for the BTC. Public comments should clearly describe specific issues or topics that the commenter believes the INRMP should address. The draft INRMP will be published in spring 2001. A 30-day public review period will follow the publication and distribution of the draft INRMP. Written comments must be received at the address below no later than 16 October 2000 to be considered:

OREGON MILITARY DEPARTMENT
ATTN: MR. GREGORY MITCHELL (AGI-ENV)
1776 MILITIA WAY SE
P.O. BOX 14350
SALEM, OR 97309-5047
PHONE (503) 945-3851; FAX (503) 945-3584

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OREGON MILITARY DEPARTMENT
HEADQUARTERS OREGON NATIONAL GUARD
1776 MILITIA WAY
P.O. BOX 14350
SALEM, OREGON 97309-5047

25 September 2000

Dear Sir or Madam:

The Oregon Military Department (OMD), the administrative head of the Oregon Army National Guard, is in the early stages of preparing an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the Biak Training Center (BTC), located approximately four miles southeast of Redmond, Oregon (Deschutes and Crook Counties). The purpose of the INRMP is to provide direction for the management of the estimated 31,400 acres of land administered by the Bureau of Land Management (BLM) and allocated for special use to the Oregon Army National Guard. The BTC is used as a training site for the men and women of the U.S. military, but remains open and accessible to the public as well. The INRMP is being prepared in cooperation with the BLM and will have tenure for federal fiscal years 2002 to 2006.

The INRMP is being prepared in accordance with the Sikes Act (16 U.S.C. 670), as amended, the Federal Land Policy and Management Act, and other associated environmental laws, guidelines, and regulations. Implementation of the plan will constitute a federal action, thereby requiring compliance with the National Environmental Policy Act of 1969. Accordingly, the plan will include an environmental assessment to analyze potential impacts to the local environment and economy.

The INRMP will address the interrelationship between military training and natural resources conservation at the BTC, as well as other current land uses, such as outdoor recreation, livestock grazing, wildlife conservation, invasive species control, and soils management. The OMD and BLM are committed to maintaining this concept of multiple-use on public lands.

The Oregon Army National Guard uses the BTC to train military personnel for national security interests and to mobilize for civilian emergency response situations within the State of Oregon. The BTC consists of maneuver areas for the movement of both wheeled and tracked vehicles on- or off-road, digging and excavation areas, and infantry training areas (Figure 1). Live fire exercises are not conducted at the BTC, and most of the areas remain easily accessible and open to the public.

The general goals of the INRMP will focus on the preservation of military training, maintaining adequate public access to the site, livestock grazing, and outdoor recreation. The INRMP will emphasize the continuing action of existing conditions, with recommendations on how to conserve the natural and cultural resources located on the public lands. Specific objectives that will likely be addressed in the INRMP include:

- Preservation of the military mission;
- Control of noxious weeds and invasive species;
- Identification of current and compatible land uses;
- Vegetation restoration and soils management; and
- Habitat conservation for sensitive species.

The Oregon Military Department invites you to express your comments and concerns regarding this action. Please submit your comments to Mr. Greg Mitchell, Oregon Military Department (ATTN: AGI-ENV), 1776 Militia Way SE, Salem, OR; phone 503-945-3851, or fax 503-945-3584, by 16 October 2000. Your assistance in this early phase of the project is appreciated.

JAMES R. LYMAN
Lieutenant Colonel
Director of Installations

Enclosure

OREGON MILITARY DEPARTMENT
HEADQUARTERS OREGON NATIONAL GUARD
1776 MILITIA WAY
P.O. BOX 14350
SALEM, OREGON 97309-5047

25 September 2000

Tribal Chairman Name
Tribal Affiliation
Address
City, State, ZIP

Dear _____,

The Oregon Military Department (OMD), the administrative head of the Oregon Army National Guard, is in the early stages of preparing an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the Biak Training Center (BTC), located approximately four miles southeast of Redmond, Oregon (Deschutes and Crook Counties). The purpose of the INRMP is to provide direction for the management of the estimated 31,400 acres of land administered by the Bureau of Land Management (BLM) and allocated for special use to the Oregon Army National Guard. The BTC is used as a training site for the men and women of the U.S. military, but remains open and accessible to the public as well. The INRMP is being prepared in cooperation with the BLM and will have tenure for federal fiscal years 2002 to 2006.

The INRMP is being prepared in accordance with the Sikes Act (16 U.S.C. 670), as amended, the Federal Land Policy and Management Act, and other associated environmental laws, guidelines, and regulations. Implementation of the plan will constitute a federal action, thereby requiring compliance with the National Environmental Policy Act of 1969. Accordingly, the plan will include an environmental assessment to analyze potential impacts to the local environment, including cultural resources.

The INRMP will address the interrelationship between military training, cultural resources, and natural resources conservation at the BTC, as well as other current land uses, such as outdoor recreation, livestock grazing, wildlife conservation, invasive species control, and soils management. The OMD and BLM are committed to maintaining this concept of multiple-use on public lands.

The Oregon Army National Guard uses the BTC to train military personnel for national security interests and to mobilize for civilian emergency response situations within the State of Oregon. The BTC consists of maneuver areas for the movement of both wheeled and tracked vehicles on- or off-road, digging and excavation areas, and infantry training areas (Figure 1). Live fire exercises are not conducted at the BTC, and most of the areas remain easily accessible and open to the public.

The general goals of the INRMP will focus on the preservation of military training, maintaining adequate public access to the site, livestock grazing, and outdoor recreation. The INRMP will emphasize the continuing action of existing conditions, with recommendations on how to conserve the natural and cultural resources located on the public lands. Specific objectives that will likely be addressed in the INRMP include:

- Preservation of the military mission;
- Cultural resources identification and conservation;
- Control of noxious weeds and invasive species;
- Identification of current and compatible land uses;
- Vegetation restoration and soils management; and
- Habitat conservation for sensitive species.

I will be contacting you by telephone within the next few weeks to determine whether you require more information regarding the development of the INRMP, to request referrals of knowledgeable individuals in your tribe who may be willing to assist in the identification of areas of cultural significance, and to offer the tribe an opportunity to voice concerns over the INRMP. Additionally, should you like a tour of the planning area or a meeting arranged to answer any questions and discuss the INRMP, please let us know so that we may set a date.

Once again, the Oregon Military Department welcomes your participation and comments on the INRMP for the Biak Training Center. Unfortunately, as with most federal projects of this caliber, time constraints are ever present. Consequently, in order that the INRMP be completed in a timely manner we request that you submit your comments by 16 October 2000. Please submit your comments to Mr. Greg Mitchell, Oregon Military Department (ATTN: AGI-ENV), 1776 Militia Way SE, Salem, OR; phone 503-945-3851, or fax 503-945-3584, by 16 October 2000. We appreciate your assistance in this early phase of the planning process and look forward to working with you.

Enclosure

Karen Coulter
Blue Mtns. Biodiversity Project

Fossil, OR
97830

No herbicides on noxious weeds
Habitat conservation for sensitive species - priority
Wants copy of INRMPs

(Voice mail message of 10/16/00)

Oct. 12, 00

Dear sir

Received your letter about
military exercises east of
Bend + Redmond.

We will be aware of this.
Hope you get rid of the
noxious weeds!

Myrtice Morrison
Hiker

Ms. Myrtice M. Morrison

Oregon

John A. Kitzhaber, M.D., Governor

Department of Water Resources

South Central Region

Watermaster District 11

1340 NW Wall St., Suite 100

Bend, OR 97701-1939

(541) 388-6669

FAX (541) 388-5101

<http://www.wrd.state.or.us>

16 October 2000

Mr. Greg Mitchell
Oregon Military Department (Attn: AGI-ENV)
1776 Militia Way SE
Salem, OR 97310

Dear Mr. Mitchell,

I received the notice of the Biak Training Center in Deschutes and Crook Counties. I have only one comment. Oregon water law allows the exempt use of groundwater for up to 15,000 gallons per day for domestic uses and the irrigation of up to 1/2 acre of non-commercial lawn and garden. The law also allows 5,000 gallons per day for commercial use. In the notice, there were no specific activities identified where water use was going to occur, but I felt it would be good for the record to advise you of the laws.

If you are in need of water use above the limits listed above, please don't hesitate to contact me about the potential for obtaining water rights for the uses you require. Please call me at (541) 388-6669.

Sincerely,

Kyle Gorman
Watermaster - District 11

RECEIVED AGI
2001 Oct 19 A 10:28
DEPARTMENT
FOR

CITY OF REDMOND

716 SW Evergreen
PO Box 726
Redmond, OR 97756-0100

RECEIVED AGI

(541) 923-7710

Fax: (541) 548-0706

NOV 01 10 A 9 45 E-mail: info@redmond.or.us
Web site: www.redmond.or.us

DEPARTMENT
OF
MILITARY
OPERATIONS

October 16, 2000

Via Fax (503) 945-3584 and Regular Mail

Mr. Greg Mitchell
Oregon Military Department
Attn: AGI-ENV
1776 Militia Way SE
PO Box 14350
Salem, OR 97309-5047

RE: Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan for the Biak Training Center

Dear Mr. Mitchell:

The City of Redmond appreciates the opportunity to comment on the proposed Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the Biak Training Center (BTC) located approximately four miles south and east of the City of Redmond. The City of Redmond wishes to express its support for the activities and efforts of the Oregon Military Department in its attempt to provide state-of-the-art training for the Oregon Army National Guard, and would like to be considered a Stakeholder in future discussions on how to allocate and prioritize the uses of the 31,400 acres of land allocated for special use by the Oregon Army National Guard.

In 1980, in the Urban Growth Boundary Management Agreement both the City of Redmond and Deschutes County identified an Area of Mutual Interest which encompasses approximately 900 acres of land located south of Roberts Field. This Area of Mutual Interest is located within the area identified as Training Area Classification A. The City of Redmond's draft 2020 Comprehensive Plan contains a policy which specifically calls for cooperation with the Bureau of Land Management (BLM) in identification of urbanizable lands south of the Redmond Municipal Airport - Roberts Field and the Deschutes County Fairgrounds. The City of Redmond has adopted the Roberts Field Airport Master Plan as part of its Comprehensive Plan; and this Master Plan calls for a future runway to be constructed near the southern boundary of the Airport.

It appears that the BLM's Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan identifies an area included within the military training area as public lands which have been identified for possible transfer or exchange to local governments as needed to accommodate community expansion and other public purposes.

There are anticipated transportation improvements proposed for the area involved with the BTC training activities.

The City of Redmond and Deschutes County are in the planning stages for the extension of SW 19th Street to Quarry Avenue to provide a southern connection between US Hwy 97 and the County Fairgrounds and the Airport. SW 19th Street would provide an important alternative access into the southern area of the city which avoids the Yew Avenue interchange. The City is also in the planning stages of identifying a proposed by-pass route that would provide a long-term solution to the re-

page 2
Mr. Greg Mitchell
October 16, 2000

alignment of US Hwy 97 currently going through downtown Redmond. This proposed by-pass route, in conjunction with the 19th Street to Quarry interchange, is anticipated to parallel the southern urban growth boundary through a portion of the BCT training area.

Anticipated uses which will occur in this area include the relocation of the Juniper Golf Course, a publicly-held municipal golf course; the possible expansion of the Deschutes County Fairgrounds; possible addition of more land zoned for industrial uses; and the expansion of Roberts Field to add another runway. In light of the anticipation for future urban uses in this area south of the existing Redmond Urban Growth Boundary, the City of Redmond wishes to express several concerns related to the proposed INRMP for the BTC.

Both the City of Redmond and Deschutes County have concerns regarding the incompatibility between training activities, including but not limited to both wheeled and tracked vehicles, and the public uses associated with the Juniper Golf Course, the Deschutes County Fairgrounds, land zoned for industrial uses and the expansion of the runway for Roberts Field. Impacts associated with the training activities would include, but not necessarily limited to, substantial amounts of noise and dust.

Given the economic importance to the area of the Deschutes County Fairgrounds, the Airport and surrounding industrial lands, increased training activities would be better located in areas other than in Training Area A.

Sincerely,

Jo Anne Sutherland
Interim City Manager

December 7, 2000

Mr. Greg Mitchell,
Oregon Military Department
ATTN: AGI-ENV
12776 Militia Way SE
Salem OR

Re: Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
Smith Rock - Pilot Butte Recreational Trail

Dear Mr. Mitchell:

We understand that the Oregon Military Department is in the process of developing an Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP) for Deschutes and Crook Counties. The Deschutes County Bike Pedestrian Committee request that you consider and incorporate pedestrian and recreational access in your development of the INRMP.

Specifically, several community and governmental organizations have proposed to the BLM development of a pedestrian trail linking Smith Rock and Pilot Butte State Parks. It is anticipated that such a trail will be located primarily on BLM land and, where possible, along existing canal right of ways located on BLM land.

Your incorporation of recreational trails accommodating and linking to the proposed Smith Rock - Pilot Butte Recreational Trail is consistent with maintaining multiple-use of the public lands, as well as your commitment to maintaining easy accessibility, public access, and outdoor recreation. We also suggest that such trails will ultimately serve your mission by providing alternative means of access to your facilities by your personnel.

We look forward to participating and contributing to your planning process as an interested party.

Very truly yours,

Bicycle/Pedestrian Committee

cc: Robert Towne
Area Manager
Bureau of Land Management, Prineville District
P.O. Box 550
Prineville OR 97754

Steve Jorgensen
Deschutes County, Senior Transportation Planner
Community Development Department
Planning Division,
117 NW Lafayette Ave
Bend OR 97701-1925

James R. Lyman,
Lieutenant Colonel
Director of Installations
Headquarters Oregon National Guard
1776 Militia Way
Salem, Oregon 97309-5047

Curtis Smith
OPRD, High Desert Management Unit
62976 OB Riley Road
Bend OR 97701

Sean Loughran,
OPRD, Trails Coordinator
1115 Commercial Street NW
Suite 1
Salem OR 97301-1002

B.3 DRAFT INRMP/EA PUBLIC OUTREACH AND DISTRIBUTION LIST**B.3.1 Notice of Availability**

The ORARNG provided the public with an opportunity to review and comment on the draft INRMP/EA between August 3 and September 4, 2001. The ORARNG announced the availability of the draft INRMP/EA by publishing notices of availability in local newspapers and requesting comments. The notices were published in the *Bend Bulletin*, *Prineville Central Oregonian*, and *Redmond Spokesman*. Submittal of comments was requested by September 4, 2001. A copy of the notice is provided on the following page.

Copies of the draft INRMP/EA were available at local libraries in Bend, Redmond, and Prineville, Oregon, and by request. More than 220 letters announcing the availability of the draft INRMP/EA were mailed to public officials, organizations, individuals, and tribal governments, federal, state, and local agencies by letters dated August 3, 2001. The recipients of these letters, which are listed in Table B-1, were either provided a copy of the draft INRMP/EA or were notified of its availability. Both letters note the closing date for the comment period as September 4, 2001.

Notice of Availability

**Draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
and Environmental Assessment
for the Biak Training Center**

The Oregon Military Department, in cooperation with the National Guard Bureau, has completed an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) and a Draft Environmental Assessment (EA) that evaluates the potential environmental effects of implementing the INRMP for the Biak Training Center, an Oregon Army National Guard training area on U.S. Bureau of Land Management administered property southeast of Redmond, Oregon. Printed copies of these documents are available for public review through September 4, 2001 at the reference desks of the following public libraries:

Crook County Public Library: 175 NW Meadow Lakes Drive, Prineville
Deschutes County Public Library: 601 NW Wall St., Bend
Deschutes County Public Library: 827 SW Deschutes Ave., Redmond

**COMMENTS OR REQUESTS FOR ADDITIONAL INFORMATION
SHOULD BE SENT TO:**

Mr. Gregory A. Mitchell
Oregon Military Department
1776 Militia Way, P.O. Box 14350
Salem, OR 97309-5047
Telephone (503) 584-3851

Table B-1
Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
or Notified of its Availability

NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
<i><u>Government Officials</u></i>		
	Governor's Office	254 State Capitol Salem, OR 97310
Denny Jones	State Representative, State Capitol	Room H-360 Salem, OR 97310
Lynn Lundquist	State Representative	12503 S. Shumway Rd Powell Butte, OR 97753
Neil Bryant	State Senator, State Capitol	Room S-218 Salem, OR 97310
Congressman Greg Walden	US Congress	843 E Main, Suite 400 Medford, OR 97504
<i><u>Native American Tribes</u></i>		
Dave Evans	Burns Paiute Tribe	HC 71 100 Pasigo St Burns, OR 97720
Albert Teeman, Chairperson	Burns Paiute Tribe	HC 71 100 Pasigo St Burns, OR 97720
Linda Reed-Jerofke, Cultural Resource Mgr	Burns Paiute Tribe	HC 71 100 Pasigo St Burns, OR 97720
Mike Farrow, Natural Resource Manager	Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation	P.O. Box 638 Pendleton, OR 97801
Rick George	Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation	P.O. Box 638 Pendleton, OR 97801
Antone Mimhorne, Chairman	Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation	P.O. Box 638 Pendleton, OR 97801
Jeff VanPelt, Cultural Resource Manager	Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation	P.O. Box 638 Pendleton, OR 97801
Robert Brunoe	Confederated Tribes of Warm Springs	PO Box C Warm Springs, OR 97761
Brad Nye	Confederated Tribes of Warm Springs	PO Box C Warm Springs, OR 97761
Olney Patt Jr., Chairman	Confederated Tribes of Warm Springs	PO Box C Warm Springs, OR 97761
Clay Penhollow, Natural Resource Manager	Confederated Tribes of Warm Springs	PO Box C Warm Springs, OR 97761
Allen Foreman, Chairman	The Klamath Tribes	PO Box 436 Chiloquin, OR 97624

Table B-1
Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
or Notified of its Availability (continued)

NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
Elwood Miller, Jr., Natural Resource Mgr	The Klamath Tribes	PO Box 436 Chiloquin, OR 97624
<i><u>Federal Agencies</u></i>		
Steve Castillo	Bureau Of Land Management	PO Box 550, 3050 NE Third St Prineville, OR 97754
Teal Purrington	Bureau Of Land Management	PO Box 550, 3050 NE Third St Prineville, OR 97754
Paul Schmidt	Bureau Of Land Management	PO Box 550, 3050 NE Third St Prineville, OR 97754
Ron Wortman	Bureau Of Land Management	PO Box 550, 3050 NE Third St Prineville, OR 97754
Recreation Staff	USDA Deschutes National Forest	1645 NE Hwy 20 Bend, OR 97701
Jerry Cordova	US Fish and Wildlife Service	20310 Empire Avenue, Suite A-100 Bend, OR 97701
Ron Davis	US Natural Resources Conservation Service	625 SE Salmon Rd., Suite 4 Redmond, OR 97756
<i><u>State Agencies</u></i>		
Bonnie Lamb	Oregon Department of Environmental Quality	2146 NE 4 th , Suite 104 Bend, OR 97701
Brian Ferry	Oregon Department of Fish & Wildlife	2042 SE Paulina Hwy Prineville, OR 97754
Steven George	Oregon Department of Fish & Wildlife	61374 Parrell Rd Bend, OR 97702
Doug White	Oregon State Dept. of LC&D	1175 Court Street NE Salem, OR 97310
Patrick F Creedican, District Manager	Oregon Department of Transportation	PO Box 5309 Bend, OR 97701
Ken Doud	Oregon Department of Transportation, Region 4 Right Of Way,	63020 Ob Riley Road Bend, OR 97701
Russ Frost	Oregon Department of Transportation	63034 O B Riley Rd Bend, OR 97701
E. David Blum, Project Coordinator	Oregon State Division of State Lands	775 Summer Street Salem, OR 9310-1337
Nancy Niedernhofer	Oregon State Historic Preservation Office % Oregon Parks and Recreation Department	1115 Commercial Street NE Salem, OR 97310
Kyle Gorman	Oregon Water Resources Department	1340 NW Wall St., Ste 100 Bend, OR 97701

Table B-1
 Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
 or Notified of its Availability (*continued*)

NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
<u>Local Agencies & Organizations</u>		
	82nd Cavalry	875 SW Simpson Bend, OR 97702-3113
Sandra Sands	Alliance for Responsible Land Use	3450 SW 81st St Redmond, OR 97756
Rick Artig	Bend Bulletin	1526 NW Hill Street Bend, OR 97701
Scott Maben	Bend Bulletin	1526 NW Hill Street Bend, OR 97701
	Bend Chamber Of Commerce	63085 N Highway 97 Bend, OR 97701
Carrie Whitaker	Bend Metro Park & Recreation District	200 NW Pacific Park Lane Bend, OR 97701
Myrtice Morrison	Bend Senior Hikers	61563 SE Orion Dr Bend, OR 97702
Bill McCaffrey	Biak Training Center	875 SW Simpson Avenue Bend, OR 97702
Karen Coulter	Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project	HCR 82 Fossil, OR 97830
Rick Hinman	Central Electric Coop, Inc	PO Box 846 Redmond, OR 97756
Craig Miller	Central Oregon Audubon Society	PO Box 6376 Bend, OR 97708
Glen Vancise	Central Oregon Audubon Society	2110 NW 2nd Bend, OR 97701
	Central Oregon Economic Development Council	63085 N Highway 97, Suite 105 Bend, OR 97701
Ron Nelson	Central Oregon Irrigation District	2598 N Hwy 97 Redmond, OR 97756-1219
Dave Cheney	Central Oregon Motorcycle & All-Terrain Vehicle Club	3227 SW Pumice Place Redmond, OR 97756
Katie Hammer	Central Oregon Parks & Recreation District	465 SW Rimrock Way Redmond, OR 97756
Don Pickens	Central Oregon Parks & Recreation District	6414 NW Atkinson PO Box 843 Redmond, OR 97756
	Central Oregon Recreation Association	63085 N Hwy 97, Suite 104 Bend, OR 97701
	Central Oregon Trails Alliance	87 NW Shasta St Bend, OR 97701

Table B-1
Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
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NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
	Central Oregonian	558 N Main St Prineville, OR 97754
Joe Hannan, City Manager	City of Redmond	PO Box 154 Redmond, OR 97756
Jo Anne Sutherland	City of Redmond	716 SW Evergreen PO Box 726 Redmond, OR 97756
Alan Unger	City of Redmond Planning Department	1544 NW 4th Redmond, OR 97756
Dave Ledder	C.O. Chapter, National Audubon Society	21110 Sholes Rd Bend, OR 97702
Fred Rodgers Judge	Crook County Commissioners	Courthouse 300 E 3rd St Prineville, OR 97754
	Crook County Library	200 East Second Street Prineville, OR 97754
Alan Rappleyea	Crook County Planning Department	County Courthouse Prineville, OR 97754
J.B. Cox	Crook County Soil and Water Conservation District	2215 NE McKay Rd Prineville, OR 97754
Dottie Morrisette	Crook County Soil and Water Conservation District	498 SW Lynn Blvd. Prineville, OR 97754
Brad Chalfant	Deschutes County	1340 NW Wall Bend, OR 97701
Watermaster	Deschutes County	1340 NW Wall Bend, OR 97701
Wolf Reusse	Deschutes County 4-Wheelers	76 SE Pipr Dr Bend, OR 97702
	Deschutes County Bicycle and Pedestrian Advisory Committee % Deschutes County Community Development Department	117 NW Lafayette Avenue Bend, OR 97701
	Deschutes County Board of Commissioners	1130 NW Harriman Bend, OR 97701
	Deschutes County Library	507 NW Wall Street Bend, OR 97701
	Deschutes County Library	446 SW 7th Redmond, OR 97756
	Deschutes County Library	164 East Main Sisters, OR 97759

Table B-1
Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
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NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
Heidi Kennedy, Assistant Planner	Deschutes County Planning Department	Courthouse Annex 1130 NW Harriman Bend, OR 97701
George Read	Deschutes County Planning Department	Courthouse Annex 1130 NW Harriman Bend, OR 97701
Tom Blust	Deschutes County Public Works	61150 SE 27th Bend, OR 97701
Jeff Rola	Deschutes County Soil and Water Conservation District	625 SE Salmon Rd., Suite 4 Redmond, OR 97756
	High Desert Saddle Club	PO Box 242 Prineville, OR 97754
Ball Janik, LLP	Huntington Ranch Resort, LLC	15 SW Colorado Avenue # K Bend, OR 97702
Klaus Hohman	Lobos Motorcycle Club	62643 Cephus Court Bend, OR 97701
Stuart Garrett, MD	Native Plant Society Of Oregon	1501 NE Medical Center Dr Bend, OR 97701
Chuck Schonneker	North Unit Irrigation District	2024 NW Beech Street Madras, OR 97741
Kelly Smith	Oregon Hunters Association	63570 Johnson Rd Bend, OR 97701
	Oregon Hunters Association	60812 Brighton Circle Bend, OR 97702
	Oregon Hunters Association	PO Box 1545 Prineville, OR 97754
	Oregon Hunters Association	PO Box 267 Redmond, OR 97756
Joy Belsky	Oregon Natural Desert Association	732 SW 3rd Ave, Suite 407 Portland, OR 97204
Bill Marlett	Oregon Natural Desert Association	16 NW Kansas Bend, OR 97701
	Oregon Natural Resources Council Southwest Office	PO Box 11648 Eugene, OR 97440
Tim Lillebo	Oregon Natural Resources Council	16 NW Kansas Ave Bend, OR 97701-3202
	Oregon State Fish & Wildlife Commission	64770 Melinda Ct Bend, OR 97701
Bend Branch	The Oregonian	PO Box 5847 Bend, OR 97701

Table B-1
Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
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NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
Robert Latimer	PG&E Gas Transmission Company	1440 SE Lake Road Redmond, OR 97702
	Pacific Power & Light, Inc.	63140 Britta St. # D-105 Bend, OR 97701
Carrie Novak	Redmond Airport	2522 SE Jesse Butler Circle Redmond, OR 97756
	Redmond Chamber of Commerce	446 SW 7th St Redmond, OR 97756-2207
	Redmond Rod & Gun Club	PO Box 14 Redmond, OR 97756
Jan Volz and Ted Kramer	Redmond Spokesman	PO Box 788 Redmond, OR 97756
Kent Gill	Sierra Club	PO Box 115 Camp Sherman, OR 97730
Sandy Lonsdale	Sierra Club	PO Box 5506 Bend, OR 97708
Bruce Miller	Sierra Club	20515 Klahani Dr Bend, OR 97701
Charles Engel	Sierra Club Juniper Group	22470 Rickard Road Bend, OR 97702
Frank Spieker	SW Alfalfa Land Watch	25261 Alfalfa Market Road Bend, OR 97701
	Sylvan Knolls-Boones Borough Property Association	PO Box 5132 Bend, OR 97708
Barbara Lee	Upper Deschutes Watershed Council	PO Box 1812 Bend, OR 97709
<i>Individuals</i>		
Jim Abbott		Redmond, OR 97756
Constance Albretch		Redmond, OR 97756
Carl F & Linda Anderson		Redmond, OR 97756
Art Balbini		Redmond, OR 97756
Jeremy Band		Redmond, OR 97756
Art Barnes		Redmond, OR 97756
Dan Barnes		Redmond, OR 97756
Chuck Benesch		Redmond, OR 97756
Kent Benesch		Powell Butte, OR 97753
Bill & Roberta Bennett		Redmond, OR 97756
Joanna Booser		Bend, OR 97701
Linda Boougeons		Bend, OR 97701
Vic Borghesi		Redmond, OR 97756

Table B-1
Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
or Notified of its Availability (continued)

NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
Mark Boyce		Bend, OR 97701
Bill Boyer	Artu De Co	Sisters, OR 97759
Marsha Brant		Bend, OR 97701
Ben Burreight		Redmond, OR 97756
David & Missy Butler	Butler Ranch Inc.	Terrebonne, OR 97760
Mike Carnahan		Redmond, OR 97756
Bill Chace		Bend, OR 97701
Robert Childers	Central Cascade Corporation	Redmond, OR 97756
R. Keith Clark		Redmond, OR 97756
Thomas Cocanovver		Bend, OR 97701
Eva Conover		Bend, OR 97701
Peggy Cordiner		Redmond, OR 97756-9433
Peter Coughlin		Redmond, OR 97756
Hank Court		Bend, OR 97701
Bill Cowan		Bend, OR 97701
Norma Crocker		Redmond, OR 97756
Linda Leigh Daniels		Redmond, OR 97756
Ralph & Cathey Davidson	Crenshaw Allotment	Eagle Creek, OR 97022
Howard M. (Matt) Day		Bend, OR 97701-5254
Tim Day		Redmond, OR 97756
Ernest & Marilyn Decorte		Redmond, OR 97756
Ron & Sherri Dewey		Redmond, OR 97756
Marie Hudson-Donovan		Bend, OR 97701
Virginia Dougherty		Bend, OR 97701
Ron & Jeannie Eddings		Bend, OR 97701
Mary Elbeir		Redmond, OR 97756
Shirlee Evans		Redmond, OR 97756
Pamela Falcioni	Comac	Bend, OR 97702
Lee & Teri Fast		Redmond, OR 97756
Tim Geoffreys		Bend, OR 97702
Carol Gilbert	Overland Ranch	Redmond, OR 97756
Dale Gilbert		Redmond, OR 97756
Leslie & John Gill	Rock Springs Guest Ranch	Bend, OR 97701
John J & Selma Goodman		Redmond, OR 97756
Pete & Sharon Goodmanson		Bend, OR 97701
Harrell Graham		Redmond, OR 97756
Charlie Grant		Bend, OR 97701

Table B-1
Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
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NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
Glenn & Claudia Green	Alfalfa Store	Bend, OR 97701
Elton Gregory		Redmond, OR 97756
Gary Gump		Redmond, OR 97756
Jack & Kim Hagel		Bend, OR 97701
Kelly & Alan Hanslovan		Redmond, OR 97756
Albert Haskell	Hacker-Hassing Allotment	Powell Butte, OR 97753
Linda & Bob Heckman		Bend, OR 97701
Perry Herford		Bend, OR 97701
Mike & Connie Hoffstetter		Redmond, OR 97756
Vint Holtman	Cascade Motorsports	Vancouver, WA 98662-1718
Andrew Hood		Bend, OR 97701
J Dell Howard		Bend, OR 97701
Carol Jacquet		Redmond, OR 97760
Ted Johnson		Redmond, OR 97756
Bill & Jeanie Kloepper	Comac	Prineville, OR 97754
Jim & Gail Knotek		Bend, OR 97701
Stan Lachowski		Bend, OR 97701
Louise Lamb		Redmond, OR 97756
Brian & Laura Lee Lash		Redmond, OR 97756
Ron Leep		Redmond, OR 97756
Jeff & Wendy Lovaas		Bend, OR 97701
Jim & Margie Lussier		Bend, OR 97701
D. Malarkey		Eugene, OR 97401
Ralph & Harriet Marchildon		Redmond, OR 97756
Boyd Martin		Redmond, OR 97756
Diane May		Redmond, OR 97756
Shannon & Pat McCreary		Redmond, OR 97756
Cliff McDonald	McDonald/Hacker-Hassing Allotments	Powell Butte, OR 97753
Ken & Nancy McGilvray		Redmond, OR 97756
D. W. McMenemy		Redmond, OR 97756
Nancy Merrick		Bend, OR 97701
Gary Millen	Pipeline Allotment	Powell Butte, OR 97753
Pat & Naida Miller	Pipeline Allotment	Powell Butte, OR 97753
Terry Moore		Redmond, OR 97756
Lonay Nelson		Redmond, OR 97756
Patrick & Amy O'Toole		Bend, OR 97701
Fred W & Freda Opp		Redmond, OR 97756

Table B-1
Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
or Notified of its Availability (*continued*)

NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
Andy Osborne		Redmond, OR 97756
Lynn Owen		Redmond, OR 97756
Al Pagel		Redmond, OR 97756
Rick Peterson		Redmond, OR 97756
Ken Pimentel		Bend, OR 97701
Christian Radabaugh	Lnk Ranches - Powell Butte/Mayfield Pond Allotments	Bend, OR 97701
Mary Roscamp	Rock Springs Guest Ranch	Bend, OR 97701
Ted Schassberger		Bend, OR 97701-8814
Juanice Schram		Bend, OR 97701
David M. Schroeder	Spectrum Hardwoods	Bend, OR 97701
Lynn & Robert Scobee		Bend, OR 97701
Bill & Heidi Searle		Redmond, OR 97756
Hayden & Sandy Sears		Bend, OR 97701
Greg Shoffner		Bend, OR 97701
Ray Shumway	Hutton/Oertle Allotments	Powell Butte, OR 97753
Dave & Brian Skidgel	Bar 7a Trucking	Redmond, OR 97756
Lila & Harvey Smith		Redmond, OR 97756
Ken Sporalsky		Bend, OR 97701
Jenelle Standiford		Bend, OR 97701
Woody Starr	Cog-Wild Bicycle Tours	Bend, OR 97701
Ambers Thornburgh		Redmond, OR 97756
Eva & Everett Thornburgh		Terrebonne, OR 97760
Steve Tognoli	River Run Ranch	Redmond, OR 97756
Rex Tompsett		Redmond, OR 97756
Steve & Jo Trenhaile		Redmond, OR 97756
Vern & Hallie Tulare		Bend, OR 97701
Tom & Teri Turquand		Bend, OR 97701
Chris Unger		Redmond, OR 97756
Bob & Laurie Vander Beek		Bend, OR 97701
Roberta Vandehey		Fossil, OR 97830
Eldrit Vanwert		Redmond, OR 97756
Gary Ward	Allen Allotment	Powell Butte, OR 97753
Gil Ward		Bend, OR 97701
Phil Weigand	Weigand Allotment	Powell Butte, OR 97753
Pat Weirlein		Terrebonne, OR 97760-9035
R. J. & Mae Weiss		Redmond, OR 97756
Jeri Welbourn		Bend, OR 97701

Table B-1
Individuals and Agencies Provided a Copy of the Draft INRMP/EA
or Notified of its Availability (continued)

NAME	AGENCY OR AFFILIATION	ADDRESS
Elbert Whitaker		Redmond, OR 97756
Charlie Winchell		Bend, OR 97701
Larry & Kathryn Wogman	Lnk Ranches - Powell Butte/Mayfield Pond Allotments	Chehalis, WA 98532
Jo Wolf		Redmond, OR 97756
Marian Woodall		Bend, OR 97701
Bob Woodward		Bend, OR 97701
Jan Wroncy	Canaries Who Sing	Eugene, OR 97440
Don Zalunardo		Redmond, OR 97756
Tom Zowney		Redmond, OR 97756

B.3.2 Summary of Comments Received

In total, two government agencies, one individual, and one organization commented in writing on the draft INRMP/EA during the 30-day comment period that extended from August 3 to September 4, 2001. The letters were from the Oregon Department of Transportation, District 10, the City of Redmond, Mr. Perry Herford, and the Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project. Two additional government agencies, the Oregon SHPO and the USFWS, commented in writing on the draft INRMP/EA after the comment period ended, but the letters were still considered in this evaluation. Copies of letters received are included on the following pages. Comments made and issues raised are addressed in Table B-2.

B.3.3 Conclusions

This document has been revised, as necessary, to address all of the issues raised. Table B-2 identifies which section of the INRMP/EA has been revised to address each comment or, if not specifically addressed elsewhere in the document, the table provides a response to the comment.

Table B-2
Comments Made on Draft INRMP/EA

CMT. No.*	COMMENTOR	COMMENT OR ISSUE RAISED	RESPONSE TO COMMENT / ISSUE
1	Oregon Department of Transportation	Support of the proposed use of the BTC.	Your support is noted and appreciated.
2	Oregon Department of Transportation	<p data-bbox="444 927 526 1582">Listing of comments regarding how use of the BTC would affect the three state highways bordering or passing through the training site:</p> <ul data-bbox="537 927 1182 1582" style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="537 927 597 1582">• ODOT has not experienced problems with the present facility. <li data-bbox="602 927 781 1582">• Any access to a state highway requires a permit from ODOT. The present access points used by the BTC and the public are acceptable. If they are planned to be moved or new ones are constructed, ODOT would have to approve and give written permission before any action could be taken. <li data-bbox="786 927 846 1582">• No use of highway rights-of-way are allowed unless by written permission. <li data-bbox="850 927 1057 1582">• Crossing of highways must be done at permitted access points and under existing traffic laws, giving preference to highway traffic. If a special need arises to cross a convoy or at a location where there is no permitted access, a written permit must be obtained from ODOT prior to the event. No stopping, delaying, or interfering with highway traffic would be allowed without written permit. <li data-bbox="1062 927 1154 1582">• Hauling of heavy vehicles across highway pavements must be done under the statutes and regulations governing highway traffic. <li data-bbox="1159 927 1182 1582">• No access for the BTC will be taken from Highway 97. 	The proposed INRMP would not alter from current conditions how ORARNG uses or accesses BTC. Likewise, no new access points to BTC are proposed.
3	City of Redmond	Statement that the draft INRMP/EA does not adequately address the proposed extension of Southwest 19th Street to a future interchange at Quarry Avenue and potentially to Deschutes Junction.	Changes and additions presented in the comment have been made to Section 7.18, Cumulative Effects. However, the determination of effect on the military mission and its operations can only be done by ORARNG at a later date after they have had an opportunity to review all of the City of Redmond's proposed plans.

Table B-2
Comments Made on Draft INRMP/EA (continued)

CMT. No.*	COMMENTOR	COMMENT OR ISSUE RAISED	RESPONSE TO COMMENT / ISSUE
4	City of Redmond	Statement that the draft INRMP/EA does not adequately address the proposed expansion of the Deschutes County Fairgrounds.	Changes and additions presented in the comment have been made to Section 7.18, Cumulative Effects. However, the determination of effect on the military mission and its operations can only be done by ORARNG at a later date after they have had an opportunity to review all of the City of Redmond's proposed plans.
5	Mr. Perry Hereford	Although your letter makes no mention of the proposed destination resort, called Huntington Ranch Resort, to be located in Section 16, T16, R13, based on maps supplied to me by the Hi Desert Development Partnership LLC, it appears that BTC lands completely surround Section 16.	The cover letter to the draft INRMP/EA does not specifically mention the Huntington Ranch Resort. However, Section 7.18, Cumulative Effects, of the draft INRMP/EA does discuss this other project.
6	Mr. Perry Hereford	The Huntington Ranch Resort's necessary sewer, water, electric, gas, and phone lines will need to cross BTC. This would seem extremely dangerous. Also, their entrance and exit roads will need to cross BTC. This adds more danger and complications.	It is likely that infrastructure easements would require special use permits from the BLM, as such infrastructure would cross BLM lands. Compliance with NEPA would also be required. ORARNG would likely be involved in the permit application and NEPA review process and would address any concerns at that time.
7	Mr. Perry Hereford	There are many historic and archaeological sites that are located within the boundaries of BTC. Your training activities have been curtailed to an extent on your training areas so they do not deface or destroy these important historic and archaeological features.	ORARNG values historic and archaeological resources and, as your comment mentions and as stated in the INRMP/EA, ORARNG takes steps to protect such resources.
8	Mr. Perry Hereford	My analysis is that the proposed Huntington Ranch Resort and your training area activities are not compatible. In as much as your training area has been established for some long time, and your activities have proven to be good caretakers of this public BLM-managed land, the destination resort is not in the best interest of the public or the OMD.	The scope of this document is limited to evaluating the environmental effects of implementing the proposed INRMP. In addition, a cumulative effects analysis that considers the Huntington Ranch Resort is provided in Section 7.18. Determining what is or is not in the best interest of the public from a land use perspective is not within the scope of this analysis.

Table B-2
Comments Made on Draft INRMP/EA (continued)

CMT. No. #	COMMENTOR	COMMENT OR ISSUE RAISED	RESPONSE TO COMMENT / ISSUE
9	Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project	<p>Support of the goals to enhance ecosystem integrity and sustain biological diversity. Some aspects of the plan that I and the Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project encourage and support are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protect soil resources of BTC from erosion, compaction, and contamination resulting from military use. • Assist BLM in identifying wetland resources at BTC. • Maintain and enhance upland resources for desired plant communities (e.g., native vegetation), plant species composition, and species diversity. • Protect and enhance wildlife that reside on and migrate through BTC. • Enhance and rehabilitate western juniper and bitterbrush habitat. • Protect the potential habitat and populations of threatened, endangered, and special status species that could reside on or migrate through BTC now or in the future. • Maintain livestock fences and keep gates closed during the grazing season to prevent livestock from impacting the ecosystem any more than they already are as an alien species that should not be on this continent in the first place. • Controlling nonnative noxious and undesirable weeds through means other than pesticide/herbicide application. • Eliminate disturbances of cultural resources, especially Native American sites. • Implement a prescribed burn management program or fuel hazard reduction strategy if beneficial to wildlife habitat, forage, and biodiversity. • Protection of forests and the juniper trees therein, not allowing commercial logging, removal, or damage of said trees. 	Your support is noted and appreciated.

Table B-2
Comments Made on Draft INRMP/EA (continued)

CMT. NO.*	COMMENTOR	COMMENT OR ISSUE RAISED	RESPONSE TO COMMENT / ISSUE
10	Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project	Support of controlling nonnative noxious and undesirable weeds through means other than pesticide or herbicide application (e.g., hand-pulling, mowing, grazing, prescribed burning) (from previous comment). Concern about the effects of pesticides and herbicides and strong disagreement with their use to combat noxious weeds.	The INRMP proposes an integrated approach that is consistent with Army, BLM, and ORARNG guidance. As shown in Section 3.7.4, this approach includes hand-pulling, mowing, and grazing. Chemicals, however, can be cost-effective means of treatment. Any use of chemicals would conform with Army guidelines, BLM policies, and ORARNG Regulation 210-5. ORARNG is also proposing to evaluate other methods, including prescribed burning.
11	Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project	Concern about the potential removal of or harm to wild horses.	Section 3.9.1 has been revised to clarify information about the few (less than 10) feral horses on BLM lands that are sometimes found on BTC. Per discussions with BLM, these feral horses escaped from private land and are of unknown ownership. They are not in the wild horse herd management area that BLM manages and, since they are not wild horses per the definition and guidelines of the Wild Free-Roaming Horse and Burro Act of 1971, they are not protected under that Act. As stated in Section 3.9.1, it is BLM's intention to remove the feral horses from public lands, and, as a BLM action, the decision to remove them and the methods by which that would occur are not within the scope of this INRMP/EA. If you would like more information on feral horses from the BLM, please contact Mr. Bill Pieratt of the BLM Prineville District Office at (541)416-6720.

Table B-2
Comments Made on Draft INRMP/EA (continued)

CMT. No.*	COMMENTOR	COMMENT OR ISSUE RAISED	RESPONSE TO COMMENT / ISSUE
12	Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project	Concern about effects of military training on wildlife, especially all-terrain combat vehicles, and the soil compaction and erosion that results.	The INRMP proposes measures to minimize effects to these wildlife and soil resources. The INRMP places a high priority on protecting soil resources from erosion, compaction, and contamination resulting from military use. The majority of the BTC is restricted to infantry (i.e., pedestrian) troops or restricts vehicles to established roads and trails. The proposed INRMP would include annual rehabilitation of vegetation in locations where wheeled or tracked vehicles are allowed off established roads and trails, in part to stabilize soil resources. The INRMP also places a high priority on watering graded roads prior to and during military training, which would minimize wind erosion. Impacts of these activities to soils are expected to be beneficial.
13	Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project	Statement that the BTC and proposed action is part of a series of connected actions sharing the same geographic area and time frame and should require an Environmental Impact Statement to address region-wide and cumulative effects.	This document is mandated under the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997. Implementing guidance for this Act requires that an INRMP be completed by November 2001. OMD evaluated combining this proposal with environmental documentation for other projects, but other projects were not ready for analysis and documentation in the time frame necessary for OMD to meet the November 2001 deadline. Additionally, Section 7.18 defines and addresses cumulative effects. Under NEPA, an Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) is required if a proposal is expected to result in significant effects. This EA was prepared to evaluate the proposal (the INRMP) for the possibility of significant effects. This EA has concluded that no significant adverse impacts would occur - from implementation of the proposed action (implementation of the INRMP) or from the incremental effects of all the various projects analyzed in the cumulative effects analysis. Since no significant impacts are expected to occur, an Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) is not required.
14	Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project	Disagreement with the goals and mission of the military and the activities in which it engages. Advocacy that the military stop using the BTC, or public lands, for its training.	ORARNG is mandated to provide these military services.

Table B-2
Comments Made on Draft INRMP/EA (continued)

CMT. No.*	COMMENTOR	COMMENT OR ISSUE RAISED	RESPONSE TO COMMENT / ISSUE
15	Oregon SHPO	Our comments related to the <i>Summary of Known Resources</i> section within Section 3.11, "Cultural Resources." The document states that five out of six historic wagon roads identified within the BTC were found to be ineligible. The SHPO does not concur with that statement. None of those wagon roads, including Horner Road, which has been recommended for eligibility in the past, have been surveyed in their entirety. In the opinion of this office, the eligibility of the wagon roads has not been adequately assessed. The SHPO recommends the INRMP be changed to reflect that SHPO concurrence on the eligibility of the wagon roads has not been received.	The comment that "five out of the six historic wagon roads identified within the BTC were found to be ineligible" does not reflect the text of the INRMP/EA. Page 3-39 states: "Of the six identified historic wagon roads, portions of five have been recommended as not eligible and one (Horner Road) is recommended as eligible." The key word here is <i>portions</i> . As such, no changes to the INRMP/EA have been made. A concurrence letter from the SHPO is needed regarding the eligibility determination for resources identified in the following reference: "Oetting, Albert C. 1997. Archaeological Investigations at the Central Oregon Training Site near Redmond, Deschutes and Crook Counties, Oregon. Heritage Research Associates Report Number 196."
16	Oregon SHPO	The North Unit Main Canal is noted in the document as being ineligible for the National Register of Historic Places because it was not fifty years of age at the time of the finding. The SHPO recommends that the North Unit Main Canal be reevaluated for eligibility and the INRMP be revised to reflect that intention.	This statement regarding the canal is correct in that the 1991 evaluation did not recommend the canal or its features as eligible based on the 50-year threshold for a determination of historic. Likewise, the determination of eligibility is the responsibility of the Bureau of Reclamation, and not that of the ORARNG or the BLM. Language regarding reevaluation of the canal was dropped from the ICRMP because of the Bureau of Reclamation's Section 106 responsibility. In summary, no changes to the INRMP/EA have been made.
17	Oregon SHPO	The INRMP states that, "recent correspondence from the SHPO regarding the ICRMP did not identify any issues of "exceptional contribution" under criteria G for ORARNG facilities, which include the BTC." The SHPO was asked by ORARNG to comment on the material presented in the draft ICRMP. We were not asked to "identify issues of exceptional contribution," and the lack of specific mention of such issues in our comments should not be interpreted to mean that there are no such issues to consider.	The last sentence of Section 3.11 has been changed to: "The ICRMP did not identify any properties or issues of "exceptional contribution" under criteria G, "Properties That Have Achieved Significance within the Last Fifty Years," for ORARNG facilities, which include the BTC."

Table B-2
Comments Made on Draft INRM/EA (continued)

CMT. No. #	COMMENTOR	COMMENT OR ISSUE RAISED	RESPONSE TO COMMENT / ISSUE
18	USFWS	An issue we strongly recommend be addressed is the role of environmental contaminants in natural resource or ecosystem management. Contaminants adversely affect the quality of habitats and the viability of plant and animal populations. Examples of contaminant-related issues include hazardous substance disposal, pesticide use, oil and chemical spills, contamination of surface waters and associated groundwater, wildlife and fish die-off or reduced reproduction, and ordnance disposal. The INRM/EA should include a section summarizing known or suspected contaminant-related issues and management actions taken, or identify if additional information is needed. The Service has extensive expertise in the environmental contaminants area and we would look forward to working with you in the future, on a reimbursable basis, to more fully address this issue in your on-going INRM/EA updates.	Sections 4-9 and 5.3 of the INRM/EA outline existing hazardous waste programs at BTC and management measures to prevent contamination. No specific changes to the INRM/EA have been made. However, OMD will coordinate with USFWS on any contaminant issues that arise at the BTC that may affect sensitive flora and fauna.
19	USFWS	Page 3-35, 3.10, first paragraph. The document should state that no proposed or designated critical habitat exists on Biak.	The following has been added before the last sentence of the paragraph: "No proposed or designated critical habitat exists at BTC (USFWS 2001)."
20	USFWS	Page 3-35, 3.10, second, third, and fourth paragraphs. The Endangered Species Act categorizes species as listed, proposed, or candidates. There is no category of "federal species of concern."	The following has been added after the first sentence in Section 3.10: "The ESA is the primary federal law that protects special status species. The federal government categorizes species as listed (endangered or threatened), proposed, or candidate. USFWS previously maintained a list of federal species of concern. This category is no longer formally recognized; however, to evaluate potential future encumbrances, species of concern are included in this analysis."
21	USFWS	D-3, first paragraph. The first sentence should read "... or adversely modify or destroy critical habitat."	The suggested change has been made.
22	USFWS	D-3, last paragraph. The first sentence should read "... affects the species and/or its critical habitat."	The suggested change has been made.
23	USFWS	D-3, last paragraph. The second sentence should read "... biological opinion may provide nondiscretionary..."	The suggested change has been made.

* Refers to the comment number circled on each comment letter, copies of which are reproduced on the following pages.

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Oregon

John A. Kitzhaber, M.D., Governor

Department of Transportation

District 10

63055 N Hwy 97

Bend, OR 97701

(541) 388-6192

FAX (541) 388-6022

August 10, 2001

FILE CODE:

Oregon Military Department
Attn: Gerald E. Elliot
1776 Militia Way
P O Box 14350
Salem, OR. 97309-5047

RE: Biak Training Center INRMP – Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan

①

Thank you for the opportunity to review the document. The Oregon Department of Transportation recognizes the need for the military training facility and supports the proposed use.

ODOT's comments are in regard to how the use of the facility would affect the three state highways bordering or passing through the training site:

②

- ODOT has not experienced problems with the present facility.
- Any access to a state highway requires a permit from ODOT. The present access points used by the BTC and the public are acceptable. If they are planned to be moved or new ones are constructed, ODOT would have to approve and give written permission before any action could be taken.
- No use of highway rights-of-way are allowed unless by written permission.
- Crossing of highways must be done at permitted access points and under existing traffic laws, giving preference to highway traffic. If a special need arises to cross in a convoy or at a location where there is no permitted access, a written permit must be obtained from ODOT prior to the event. No stopping, delaying or interfering with highway traffic would be allowed without written permit.

MILITARY DEPARTMENT
STATE OF OREGON

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②

- Hauling of heavy vehicles across highway pavements must be done under the statutes and regulations governing highway traffic.
- No access for the BTC will be taken from Highway 97.

Please contact the ODOT District 10 Office for questions and for obtaining permits. The address is P O Box 5309, Bend, OR 97708; phone 541-388-6192.

Sincerely,

Pat Creedican

Pat Creedican
District 10 Manager

CC: John Scott
Peter Russell
Jim Bryant

Jerry Baggett
Dave Neys
Bob Heckman

CITY OF REDMOND

716 SW Evergreen
PO Box 726
Redmond, OR 97756-0100

(541) 923-7710
Fax: (541) 548-0706
info@redmond.or.us
www.redmond.or.us

August 21, 2001

National Guard
Oregon Military Department
1776 Militia Way SE
PO Box 14350
Salem, OR 97309-3584

RECEIVED AGI
2001 AUG 24 A 10:15
MILITARY DEPARTMENT
OF OREGON

Attn: Greg Mitchell

The City of Redmond has now had an opportunity to review the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP). We have significant concerns because the plans of the City of Redmond for the extension of SW 19th Street to a future Quarry interchange and potentially to Deschutes Junction have not been adequately addressed in the draft plan. We anticipate that the extension of SW 19th Street to Quarry interchange will occur within the time period covered by this plan. We hope to have the Quarry Avenue interchange and southwest expansion in place within the next five years.

③ In looking at Figure 1-1 within the draft plan, it would appear that the extension of SW 19th Street to both the Quarry interchange and Deschutes Junction could affect the westerly portion of Area A. The plan needs to address that this could occur and that the National Guard, City, Deschutes County, and Bureau of Land Management will work cooperatively to accommodate these respective uses.

We do not believe that the extension of 19th Street to the Quarry Avenue interchange or Deschutes Junction will in any way compromise the ability of the National Guard to perform their necessary training exercises.

We believe that the plan needs to address this issue in a pro-active manner and note that this development may occur and if so will be consistent with the goals and objectives of the INRMP.

④ We also note that in the NW corner of Area A, the 320 acres that have been identified for potential expansion of the fairgrounds and other related uses has not been adequately addressed in the plan. As you know there is also a cultural resource area (the old wagon trail) on the easterly edge of this 320 acre parcel. We believe that the use of the parcel west of that old wagon trail will not unduly affect the operations of the National Guard. If the collaborative planning

Page 2
Greg Mitchell
August 21, 2001

④ which is now occurring between the Bureau of Land Management, the City of Redmond, Deschutes County, and others results in a finding that the identification of those 320 acres for urban expansion is appropriate we believe that this plan needs to identify that and to ensure that there will not be a conflict with that proposal. Please consider this letter our request that you revise the draft INRMP Environmental Assessment for the Biak Training Center accordingly. If you need additional information, we would be happy to provide it. Thank you.

Very Truly Yours,

Ed Fitch

cc: Ben Westlund
Bev Clarno
Deschutes County Commissioners
Redmond City Council
Robert Towne, Bureau of Land Management

Perry Herford:

Mr. Gerald E. Elliott
Sergeant Major (Retired)
Environmental Program Manager.

Re: Your Letter of Aug. 3, 01.
(EA,) Biak Training Center
on BLM Land near Redmond

⑤ Although your letter makes no mention of the Proposed Destination Resort, called HUNTINGTON RANCH RESORT, to be located on Section # 16, T.# 16 R# 13, a study of the maps that I have at hand that have been supplied to me by the "Hi Desert Development Partnership LLC", it appears that the BIAK Training Center Lands, completely surround this Section # 16, the proposed location of this Destination Resort. It does not seem reasonable, that your activities and the activities of a Destination Resort can be compatible. In addition, this Resorts Necessary, Sewer, Water, Electric, Gas and
⑥ Phone lines will need to cross your Training Center Lands. This would seem extremely dangerous. Also of course, their Entrance and Exit Roads likewise will need to cross your area. This adds more danger and complications.

⑦ In this letter to you, I make no mention of the many Historic and Archaeological sites that are located within the boundaries of your Training Area. I will say however that your Training Activities, have been curtailed to an extent on your training areas, so they do not deface or destroy these important Historical and Archaeological features..

⑧ In Summery, my analysis is that the proposed Destination Resort and your training area activities are not compatible. In as much as your Training Area has been established for some long time , and your activities have proven to be good caretakers of this Public BLM managed Land. That the Destination Resort is not in the best interest of the public, nor the Oregon Military Department.

Respectfully Yours,

Perry Herford.

MILITARY DEPARTMENT
OF OREGON

2001 AUG 27 A 10:24

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Tyler Knapp

Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project
HCR-82 Fossil, OR 97830

September 3, 2001

To: Oregon Military Dept.
Headquarters, Oregon National Guard
1776 Militia Way
P.O. Box 14350
Salem, OR 97309-5047

Attn: Mr. Greg Mitchell

RECEIVED AGI
2001 SEP 10 A 10:52
DEPARTMENT

Comments re: Bialk Training Center Draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan and EA,

I have read the Draft INRMP and EA, and am supportive of the goals to enhance ecosystem integrity and to sustain biological diversity. Some aspects of the plan that I, and the Blue Mountains Biodiversity Project (BMBP) encourage and support are:

- Protect the soil resources of the BTC from erosion, compaction, and contamination resulting from military use.
- Assist the BLM in identifying wetland resources at the BTC.
- Maintain and enhance upland resources for desired plant communities (e.g., native vegetation), plant species composition, and species diversity.
- Protect and enhance the wildlife that reside on and migrate through the BTC.
- Enhance and rehabilitate Western Juniper and Bitterbrush habitat.
- Protect the potential habitat and populations of threatened, endangered, and special status species that could reside

(9)

- on or migrate through the BIC now or in the future.
- Maintain livestock fences and keep gates closed during grazing season to prevent livestock from impacting the ecosystem any more than they already are as an alien species that shouldn't be on this continent in the first place.
 - Controlling non-native noxious and undesirable weeds through means other than pesticide/herbicide applications.
 - Eliminate disturbances of cultural resources, especially Native American sites.
 - Implement a prescribed burn management program or fuel hazard reduction strategy if beneficial to wildlife habitat, forage, and biodiversity.
 - Protection of forests and the Juniper trees therein, not allowing commercial logging, removal, or damage of said trees.

⑨

Although we agree with the above management activities or non-activities, we are still concerned about some of the things you describe. We are concerned about the effects of pesticides/herbicides, which have been proven to adversely harm the environment, people, and wildlife, and strongly disagree with you using them to combat noxious weeds. Alternatives to these toxic chemicals include hand-pulling, mowing, grazing, and prescribed burning.

⑩

We are also concerned about the potential removal of wild horses. These horses should be left alone, or

⑪

removed in a humane manner to an area that is more wild, with less fencing, and not slaughtered. We are concerned in general with the effects that military training has on wildlife, especially all-terrain combat vehicles, and the soil compaction and erosion that ensues.

The Brak Training Center, and this proposed action is part of a series of connected actions sharing the same geographic area and timeframe, and should require a full Environmental Impact Statement to fully address region-wide and cumulative effects of this and similar connected actions. These actions include, but are not limited to those listed in the EA: Juniper Golf course, Deschutes County fairgrounds expansion, Huntington Ranch Resort, an RV park, and more. We do support, however, the Smith Rock-Pilot Butte Pedestrian trail, and Deschutes County Bicycle and Pedestrian Path developments.

We disagree with the goals and mission of the military, and the activities that it engages in (such as recent wars to promote imperialist and capitalist domination, wars over oil, killing of Iraqi children, and the genocidal assault on Colombian peasants and forests in the false "war on drugs.") We also advocate that the military stop using the BTC, on public lands, for its training, thus allowing the land to rest and restore itself, along with the wildlife.

Sincerely,

 Tyler Knapp, Intern BMBP

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⑬

⑭

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Oregon

John A. Kitzhaber, M.D., Governor

Parks and Recreation Department

State Historic Preservation Office

1115 Commercial St. NE

Salem, OR 97301-1012

(503) 378-4168

FAX (503) 378-6447

September 20, 2001

File Code: Deschutes
Crook

Gerald Elliott:
Oregon Military Department
P. O. Box 14350
Salem, OR 97309-5047

RE: Review Request
Draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
and Environmental Assessment for Biak Training Center
Deschutes and Crook counties

Dear Mr. Elliott:

Thank you for the opportunity to review the Oregon Army National Guard's (ORARNG) draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan and Environmental Assessment for Biak Training Center (BTC).

Our comments relate to the *Summary of Known Resources* section within Chapter 3.11 "Cultural Resources." The document states that five out of six historic wagon roads identified within the BTC were found to be ineligible. The SHPO does not concur with that statement. None of those wagon roads, including Homer Road, which has been recommended for eligibility in the past, have been surveyed in their entirety. In the opinion of this office, the eligibility of the wagon roads has not been adequately assessed. The SHPO recommends the INRMP be changed to reflect that SHPO concurrence on the eligibility of the wagon roads has not been received. In addition, the North Unit Main Canal is noted in the document as being ineligible for the National Register because it was not fifty years of age at the time of the finding. The SHPO recommends that the North Unit Main Canal be re-evaluated for eligibility and the INRMP be revised to reflect that intention.

Finally, the INRMP states that "recent correspondence from the SHPO regarding the ICRMP did not identify any issues of "exceptional contribution" under criteria G for ORARNG facilities, which include the BTC." The SHPO was asked by ORARNG to comment on the material presented in the draft Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan. We were not asked to "identify issues of exceptional contribution" and the lack of specific mention of such issues in our comments should not be interpreted to mean that there are no such issues to consider.

If you have further questions or need additional assistance, please feel free to contact me at the SHPO, extension 229.

Sincerely,

Christine Curran
Preservation Specialist

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2001 SEP 24 A 10: 23
MILITARY DEPARTMENT
STATE OF OREGON

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United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE

911 NR. 11th Avenue
Portland, Oregon 97232-4181

IN REPLY REFER TO:

AFK

OCT 25 2001

Gerald E. Elliot, Sargent Major (Retired)
Environmental Program Manager
Oregon Military Department
Headquarters, Oregon National Guard
1776 Militia Way
PO Box 14350
Salem, Oregon 97309-5047

Dear Sargent Major Elliot:

The Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) has reviewed the August 2001 Final Draft Biak Training Center Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan and Environmental Assessment (Biak INRMP). The Service concurs that the programmatic objectives and recommendations as presented in the Biak INRMP are compatible with the objectives of the Sikes Act Improvement Act (SAIA) of 1997 (PL 105-85). Furthermore, the Service concurs that implementation of these recommendations should protect and enhance those living resources and habitats for which the Service has partial or complete jurisdiction.

In compliance with SAIA, military installations must prepare INRMPs that provide for conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources; sustainable multipurpose uses of the resources; and public access for use of natural resources, subject to safety requirements and military security. INRMPs are to be prepared in cooperation with the Service and relevant state resource agencies so that each approved INRMP reflects the mutual agreement of the parties concerning conservation, protection, and management of fish and wildlife resources.

To facilitate implementation of the precepts of the SAIA, the Department of Defense (DoD) and the Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) entered into a Memorandum of Understanding, signed May 17, 1999, "to establish a policy of cooperation and coordination between the DoD and the Service for the efficient management of fish, wildlife, and plant resources on military lands." The Service has worked with the Oregon Military Department over the last year to develop programmatic recommendations for the protection and enhancement of natural resources within the Biak Training Center INRMP project area.

Under Section 670a(b)(2) of the SAIA, the INRMP "must be reviewed as to operation and effect by the parties thereto on a regular basis, but not less than every 5 years." This review and updating schedule allows the partnering agencies regular opportunities to contribute to the planning process. The Service expects to have the opportunity to work with the Oregon Military Department to implement and refine the programmatic recommendations contained in this plan.

18 | An issue we strongly recommend be addressed is the role of environmental contaminants in natural resource or ecosystem management. Contaminants adversely affect the quality of habitats and the viability of plant and animal populations. Examples of contaminant-related issues include hazardous substance disposal, pesticide use, oil and chemical spills, contamination of surface waters and associated groundwater, wildlife and fish die-off or reduced reproduction, and ordnance disposal. The INRMP should include a section summarizing known or suspected contaminant-related issues and management actions taken, or identify if additional information is needed. The Service has extensive expertise in the environmental contaminants area and we would look forward to working with you in the future, on a reimbursable basis to more fully address this issue in your on-going INRMP updates.

Specific Comments

19 | Page 3-35, 3.10, first paragraph. The document should state that no proposed or designated critical habitat exists on BIAK.

20 | Page 3-35, 3.10, second, third, and fourth paragraphs. The Endangered Species Act categorizes species as listed, proposed, or candidates. There is no category of "federal species of concern."

21 | D-3, first paragraph. The first sentence should read "...or adversely modify or destroy critical habitat."

22 | D-3, last paragraph. The first sentence should read "...affects the species and/or its critical habitat."

23 | D-3, last paragraph. The second sentence should read "...biological opinion may provide nondiscretionary ..."

We look forward to assisting the Oregon Military Department in their effort to protect and enhance these valuable natural resources. If you have questions, please contact Rich Johnson, Regional Sikes Act Coordinator at (503) 872-2763.

Sincerely,

Regional Director

cc:
Lindsey Ball, Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife
Kemper McMaster, Oregon Fish and Wildlife Office
Jerry Cordova, Bend Field Office

APPENDIX C

LETTERS OF CONCURRENCE

The BLM's role for this INRMP is as a public agency reviewer for NEPA content and process. The USFWS and ODFW are cooperating agencies in the development of the INRMP. The USFWS has cooperated with the BTC and ORARNG in providing technical assistance on potentially occurring sensitive species and wildlife habitat management issues. The ODFW is the primary state agency responsible for managing fish and wildlife. All three agencies have reviewed the draft INRMP/EA at various stages of its development. The following three letters of concurrence from these agencies are included in this appendix:

- BLM's letter of approval as a reviewing agency.
- USFWS's letter of concurrence as a cooperating agency.
- ODFW's letter of concurrence as a cooperating agency.

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United States Department of the Interior

BUREAU OF LAND MANAGEMENT

Prineville District Office
P.O. Box 550 (3050 N.E. 3rd Street)
Prineville, Oregon 97754

IN REPLY REFER TO:

1780
1792

Gerald E. Elliott
Sergeant Major (Retired)
Environmental Program Manager
Oregon Military Department
1776 Militia Way
P.O. Box 14350
Salem, Oregon 97309-5047

SEP 20 2001

Dear Mr. Elliott:

Thank you for the forwarding the Biak Training Center Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) and Environmental Assessment (Draft) for our review.

BLM has had an opportunity to review this and previous drafts of the Biak INRMP. Overall, the plan appears to support the training needs of the Oregon Army National Guard while providing a higher level of awareness and integration of natural resource management on BLM-administered public lands. This INRMP, along with BLM's Upper Deschutes Resource Management Plan (pending) will provide the framework for guiding ORARNG/BLM cooperative management of the 31,400 acre Biak Training Center from fiscal year 2002 to 2006.

BLM concurs with the goals and guidelines of the INRMP and we look forward to a productive and mutually beneficial working relationship with Oregon Army National Guard.

Sincerely,

Robert Towne
Field Manager
Deschutes Resource Area

MILITARY DEPARTMENT
OF OREGON

2001 SEP 24 A 10:26

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United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE

911 NE. 11th Avenue
Portland, Oregon 97232-4181

IN REPLY REFER TO:

A/R

OCT 25 2001

Gerald E. Elliot, Sargent Major (Retired)
Environmental Program Manager
Oregon Military Department
Headquarters, Oregon National Guard
1776 Militia Way
PO Box 14350
Salem, Oregon 97309-5047

Dear Sargent Major Elliot:

The Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) has reviewed the August 2001 Final Draft Biak Training Center Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan and Environmental Assessment (Biak INRMP). The Service concurs that the programmatic objectives and recommendations as presented in the Biak INRMP are compatible with the objectives of the Sikes Act Improvement Act (SAIA) of 1997 (PL 105-85). Furthermore, the Service concurs that implementation of these recommendations should protect and enhance those living resources and habitats for which the Service has partial or complete jurisdiction.

In compliance with SAIA, military installations must prepare INRMPs that provide for conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources; sustainable multipurpose uses of the resources; and public access for use of natural resources, subject to safety requirements and military security. INRMPs are to be prepared in cooperation with the Service and relevant state resource agencies so that each approved INRMP reflects the mutual agreement of the parties concerning conservation, protection, and management of fish and wildlife resources.

To facilitate implementation of the precepts of the SAIA, the Department of Defense (DoD) and the Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) entered into a Memorandum of Understanding, signed May 17, 1999, "to establish a policy of cooperation and coordination between the DoD and the Service for the efficient management of fish, wildlife, and plant resources on military lands." The Service has worked with the Oregon Military Department over the last year to develop programmatic recommendations for the protection and enhancement of natural resources within the Biak Training Center INRMP project area.

Under Section 670a(b)(2) of the SAIA, the INRMP "must be reviewed as to operation and effect by the parties thereto on a regular basis, but not less than every 5 years." This review and updating schedule allows the partnering agencies regular opportunities to contribute to the planning process. The Service expects to have the opportunity to work with the Oregon Military Department to implement and refine the programmatic recommendations contained in this plan.

Gerald E. Elliot, Sargent Major (Retired)

2

An issue we strongly recommend be addressed is the role of environmental contaminants in natural resource or ecosystem management. Contaminants adversely affect the quality of habitats and the viability of plant and animal populations. Examples of contaminant-related issues include hazardous substance disposal, pesticide use, oil and chemical spills, contamination of surface waters and associated groundwater, wildlife and fish die-off or reduced reproduction, and ordnance disposal. The INRMP should include a section summarizing known or suspected contaminant-related issues and management actions taken, or identify if additional information is needed. The Service has extensive expertise in the environmental contaminants area and we would look forward to working with you in the future, on a reimbursable basis to more fully address this issue in your on-going INRMP updates.

Specific Comments

Page 3-35, 3.10, first paragraph. The document should state that no proposed or designated critical habitat exists on BIAK.

Page 3-35, 3.10, second, third, and fourth paragraphs. The Endangered Species Act categorizes species as listed, proposed, or candidates. There is no category of "federal species of concern."

D-3, first paragraph. The first sentence should read "...or adversely modify or destroy critical habitat."

D-3, last paragraph. The first sentence should read "...affects the species and/or its critical habitat."

D-3, last paragraph. The second sentence should read "...biological opinion may provide nondiscretionary ..."

We look forward to assisting the Oregon Military Department in their effort to protect and enhance these valuable natural resources. If you have questions, please contact Rich Johnson, Regional Sikes Act Coordinator at (503) 872-2763.

Sincerely,

Regional Director

cc:

Lindsey Ball, Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife
Kemper McMaster, Oregon Fish and Wildlife Office
Jerry Cordova, Bend Field Office

Oregon

John A. Kitzhaber, M.D., Governor

Department of Fish and Wildlife

Deschutes Watershed District

61374 Parrell Road

Bend, OR 97702

(541) 388-6363

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September 4, 2001

Gerald E. Elliott
Sergeant Major (Retired)
Environmental Program Manager
Oregon Military Department
PO Box 14350
Salem, Oregon 97309

RE: Draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan and Environmental Assessment for
Biak Training Center.

Thank you for the opportunity to comment on this draft INRMP and EA. We also wish to thank
you for allowing us the opportunity to work with you and your staff in preparation of these plans.

After reviewing the INRMP and EA we have no further comments than what have been provided
in early meetings. We feel that that those comments have been addressed adequately in these
plans.

If you have any further questions please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

Steven George
Deschutes District Wildlife Biologist
steven.w.george@state.or.us

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DEPARTMENT

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APPENDIX D

FEDERAL REQUIREMENTS AND OTHER GUIDELINES

Army facilities, including Army National Guard installations, are subject to numerous regulations affecting use and management of natural resources, including federal laws, EOs, and Army regulations. Table 2-1 lists of applicable laws, regulations, and policies, and this section discusses the most important of these. Military regulations, directives, and guidelines are enforced by the ORARNG and NGB. All other federal regulations, except for those related to wildlife resources, are enforced by the BLM as the primary land management agency for the BTG. The USFWS and ODFW are responsible for enforcing laws and regulations pertaining to wildlife resources, especially the management of threatened and endangered species.

D.1 MILITARY INSTRUCTIONS ON INRMPS

This section provides an overview of NGB, DOD, and Army policies and instructions, as well as the Sikes Act, which establish requirements and guidance for the preparation of INRMPS and are part of the need for this document. NGB's All-States Memorandum P00-0039 of June 15, 2000 is the main guidance for preparation and implementation of INRMPS and is discussed below.

D.1.1 National Guard Bureau Regulations

It is NGB policy to prepare an INRMP and EA for all federally supported military training sites used by the Army National Guard. NGB's All-States Memorandum P00-0039 of June 15, 2000 provides policy and guidance for preparation and implementation of INRMPS at Army National Guard training sites (NGB 2000a). The directives presented in this memorandum incorporate a variety of other guidance documents and regulations including but not limited to the Sikes Act, the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, DOD instruction, multiple Army regulations, and various other guidance memorandums, procedure manuals, and policies. The most important of these are discussed in the following sections.

D.1.2 Department of Defense Instruction 4715.3

DOD Instruction 4715.3 implements policy, assigns responsibilities, and prescribes procedures for the integrated management of natural and cultural resources on property under military control. The instruction states that "all DOD conservation programs shall work to guarantee continued access to [DOD] land, air, and water resources for realistic military training and testing while ensuring that the natural and cultural resources entrusted to DOD care are sustained in a healthy condition for scientific research, education, and other compatible uses by future generations" (DOD 1996).

DOD Instruction 4715.3 also designates DOD executive agents to lead the military services in implementing key conservation issues, including preparing, maintaining, and monitoring of INRMPs on all military installations. Instruction 4715.3 notes that conservation management is a dynamic process, yet prescribes that a consistent conservation management approach include those systematic procedures that should be used by each DOD installation, as follows:

- Assess military mission;
- Prepare detailed inventory of resources;
- Analyze and assess risk to the resources;
- Prepare and implement management plans;
- Monitor and assess results;
- Conduct needs assessment survey;
- Reassess inventories;
- Reanalyze and reassess risk to resources; and
- Adjust program as necessary.

D.1.3 Army Regulations

The *US Army Environmental Strategy into the 21st Century* (US Army 1992) provides the framework to ensure that environmental considerations are integral to the Army mission and that an environmental stewardship ethic governs all Army activities. The Army's environmental strategy is illustrated as a building with a foundation and four pillars supporting the overall vision of environmental stewardship. The strategy's goals focus on the four pillars, which represent environmental compliance, restoration, pollution prevention, and natural resources conservation.

The general goal of the conservation pillar is to conserve, protect, and enhance environmental, natural, and cultural resources using all practical means consistent with Army missions, so that present and future generations can use and enjoy them. Natural resources management in the conservation pillar is focused on conservation. Conservation involves the responsible stewardship of Army-managed lands to ensure long-term natural resources productivity so the Army can fulfill its military mission. Conservation balances the need for long-term resource use and resource protection.

Conservation is also essential for ensuring the future integrity of valuable national resources, such as wetlands, soils, endangered species habitat, and historic and cultural sites. The Army Regulation (AR) 200-series describes in detail the natural resources and environmental protection programs to be employed on lands used by the Army. These regulations are as follows:

AR 200-1: *Environmental Protection and Enhancement* (US Army 1997), requires conducting an integrated, multiple-use natural resources and land management program on lands under Army jurisdiction. Although the BTC is on lands managed by the BLM, and the military maintains no oversight of the natural resources management program there, the spirit and intent of this regulation is met in the INRMP for the BTC.

AR 200-2: *Environmental Effect of Army Actions* (US Army 1988), “sets forth policy, responsibilities, and procedures for integrating environmental considerations into Army planning and decision making” (US Army 1988). Specifically, AR 200-2 states that environmental analyses and other documentation required by this regulation will be integrated as much as practicable with other environmental reviews, laws, and EOs.

The Army’s commitment to the conservation of natural resources is further reflected in AR 200-3, *Natural Resources—Land, Forest, and Wildlife Management*. AR 200-3 “sets forth the policy, procedures, and responsibilities for the conservation, management, and restoration of land and the natural resources thereon consistent with the military mission and in consonance with national policies” (US Army 1995).

AR 200-4: *Cultural Resources Management* (US Army 1998), promotes the Army’s policy for managing cultural resources to meet legal compliance requirements and to support the military mission.

D.1.4 Oregon Army National Guard Regulations

The ORARNG also has separate regulations pertaining to natural resources management. Those regulations that could be pertinent to the management of military activities at the BTC include the following:

- ORARNG Circular 350 (Draft): *Biak Training Center Users Guide*. The circular contains administrative, personnel, training, and environmental guidance for military personnel using the BTC for training (ORARNG 2000a).
- ORARNG Regulation 200-1: *Environmental Compliance*. This regulation defines the responsibilities of commands, directorates, and individuals of the ORARNG in meeting the requirements of AR 200-1, 200-2, 200-3, and 200-4, NGB regulations and policies, and applicable federal, state, and local environmental regulations. Directorates, commands, and personnel must execute defined responsibilities in order to ensure that ORARNG activities and operations comply with applicable requirements (ORARNG 1999a).

- ORARNG Regulation 210-5: *Integrated Pest Management Plan*. This regulation identifies pest management requirements and defines resources, administrative, safety, and environmental requirements to control pests at ORARNG facilities and installations (ORARNG 1999c).
- ORARNG Regulation 210-6: *Installation Spill Contingency Plan*. This regulation describes responsibilities of units, supervisors, and individuals of the ORARNG in planning for and responding to spills of regulated substances to the environment. In order to comply with the law and to meet DOD and DA directives on environmental stewardship, the provisions of Regulation 210-6 are followed to the maximum extent practicable on ORARNG installations (ORARNG 1998).
- ORARNG Regulation 420-47: *Hazardous Waste Management Plan*. This regulation provides responsibilities and guidance for managing hazardous materials and for disposing of hazardous waste generated at ORARNG facilities and installations in accordance with federal and state regulations (ORARNG 1999b).
- ORARNG Regulation 350-25: *Integrated Training Area Management*. Integrated Training Area Management (ITAM) is a management approach that seeks to match military mission requirements with the long-term ecological integrity of military training sites. The Army and Army National Guard have embraced this approach and are implementing it on their installations and training areas. The goal of ITAM is to achieve and sustain the optimum use of training lands to support training and mission requirements indefinitely, while ensuring protection of natural resources. ITAM consists of four components that should be implemented as a whole in order to meet its overall goal (ORARNG 2000d). Section 4.4 provides a synopsis of the four components: LCTA, Training Requirements Integration (TRI), Land Rehabilitation and Maintenance (LRAM), and Environmental Awareness.

D.2 FEDERAL LAND POLICY AND MANAGEMENT ACT OF 1976, PL 94-579, AS AMENDED (43 USC §§ 1701 - 1785)

BLM-administered lands are managed under Congressional policies established by FLPMA. FLPMA mandates that the BLM manage the public lands and natural resources using "multiple use."

Multiple use refers to the management of the public lands and their various resource values so that they are utilized in the combination that will best meet the present and future needs of the American people. This concept requires the BLM to make the most judicious use of the land for some or all of these resources or related services over areas large enough to provide sufficient latitude for periodic adjustments in use to conform to changing needs and conditions. Multiple use requires a combination of balanced and diverse resource uses that takes into account the long-term needs of future generations for renewable and nonrenewable resources, including, but not

limited to, outdoor recreation, range, timber, minerals, watershed, wildlife and fish, and natural scenic, scientific, and historical values. Finally, the concept of multiple use is based on the harmonious and coordinated management of the various resources without permanent impairment of the productivity of the land and the quality of the environment, with consideration given to the relative values of the resources and not necessarily to the combination of uses that will give the greatest economic return or the greatest unit output (BLM 2000).

Following the requirements of FLPMA, the BLM Prineville District prepared the *Brothers/La Pine Resource Management Plan*, detailing management goals and objectives for the lands and natural resources managed by the BLM in central Oregon (BLM 1989). The BTC adheres to the regulations, policies, and guidelines outlined in this document in regard to its military mission.

The analysis presented in this INRMP has not taken into consideration impacts to natural resources from public lands users other than the military at the BTC. The federal public lands that compose the BTC are used for outdoor recreation and livestock grazing year-round. Impacts from differing public land users are difficult, if not impossible, to differentiate, and it is beyond the scope of this document to determine the impact or environmental effects of users other than the military.

D.3 ENDANGERED SPECIES ACT, PL 93-205 (16 USC §§ 1531 - 1534)

Under the ESA, all federal agencies, in consultation with the Secretary of the Interior, must take all necessary precautions to ensure that agency actions do not jeopardize federally threatened or endangered species or adversely modify or destroy critical habitat. Any agency whose action could affect (positively or negatively) the continued existence of a federally listed threatened or endangered species must consult with USFWS (see 50 CFR § 17 and 50 CFR § 402). Section 7(A)(1) of the ESA states that "All other Federal agencies shall, in consultation with and with the assistance of the Secretary, utilize their authorities in furtherance of the purposes of this Act by carrying out programs for the conservation of endangered species and threatened species listed pursuant to Section 4 of the ESA."

Consultations under the ESA are divided into two categories: formal and informal. In general, no formal consultation is required if the action agency finds, with the USFWS's written concurrence, that the proposed action "may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect" listed species or critical habitat. This finding can be made only if all of the reasonably expected effects of the proposed action will be beneficial, insignificant, or discountable. The action agency must request concurrence in writing from the USFWS for this finding.

Preparation of a biological assessment is required before formal consultation begins and also is required for informal consultation in cases involving major construction activity where listed species or critical habitat are present. Anywhere from a few weeks to more than a year could be required to finalize a biological assessment before it can be submitted to the USFWS as part of the request to initiate formal consultations. Formal

consultations involve up to 90 days and an additional 45 days for the USFWS to prepare a biological opinion (135 days total).

A biological opinion is a written statement from the USFWS regarding its opinion and a summary of the information on which the opinion is based, detailing how the agency action affects the species and/or its critical habitat. The biological opinion may provide nondiscretionary "reasonable and prudent" measures that should be implemented in conjunction with a proposed action to avoid or minimize impacts. The USFWS also provides nonbinding conservation recommendations as part of the biological opinion.

D.4 CLEAN WATER ACT, PL 92-500 (33 USC §§ 1251 - 1387)

The Clean Water Act (CWA) is the law under which most US Army Corps of Engineers (COE) permits are issued for discharging fill into wetlands. Most of the act deals with water pollution, which is the purview of the EPA. Responsibility for disposing of dredged material was delegated to the COE because of its historic role in that arena, but the EPA still maintains ultimate responsibility for overseeing the program. The COE regulations are published in the Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) at 33 CFR §§ 320 - 384; those of the EPA are published at 40 CFR §§ 230 - 233 and are often referred to as Section 404(b)(1) guidelines.

Section 404 defines dredge and fill responsibilities under the CWA. Exemptions for Section 404 permits are granted for normal agricultural, livestock grazing, and silvicultural activities, as well as for maintaining existing drains, culverts, farm ponds, and roads. The COE manages the wetland permitting program, but the EPA has veto power over COE permit decisions, and the USFWS and National Marine Fisheries Service have consultative rights. The COE and the EPA share enforcement authority. States can adopt administration of parts of the program from the COE, with EPA oversight. The point of contact for Section 404 permit issues is the COE.

Section 319 under the CWA addresses nonpoint source pollution by requiring all states to report to EPA all major sources of nonpoint source pollution. States must develop management programs with identified best management practices suitable for reducing nonpoint source pollution. Section 319(h) grants are awarded to states with approved nonpoint source pollution programs. Such grant money supports a wide variety of activities including technical assistance, financial assistance, education, training, technology transfer, demonstration projects, and monitoring to assess the success of specific nonpoint source implementation projects.

D.5 RELEVANT EXECUTIVE ORDERS

EO 11990—Protection of Wetlands. This order states that federal agencies will avoid adverse impacts associated with the destruction or modification of wetlands wherever there is a practicable alternative. Projects in wetlands should include all feasible measures to minimize harm to wetlands.

EO 11644—Use of Off-road Vehicles on Public Lands. This order requires federal agencies to establish policies and provide for procedures to ensure that the use of off-

road vehicles on public lands will be controlled and directed so as to protect the resources of those lands, to promote the safety of all users of those lands, and to minimize conflicts among the various uses of those lands. The order clarifies agency authority to define zones of use by off-road vehicles on public lands by exempting fire, military, emergency, law enforcement, or combat/combat support vehicles.

EO 13112—Invasive Species. To the extent permitted by law, federal agencies will restrict the introduction of exotic species into the natural ecosystems on lands and waters that they own, lease, or hold for purposes of administration, and they will encourage the states, local governments, and private citizens to prevent the introduction of exotic species into natural ecosystems of the United States. Executive agencies shall, to the extent permitted by law, restrict the use of federal funds, programs, or authorities to export native species for the purpose of introducing such species into ecosystems outside the United States where they do not naturally occur.

EO 13175—Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments. This order states that federal agencies will have an accountable process to ensure meaningful and timely input by tribal officials in the development of regulatory policies that have tribal implications.

D.6 OTHER FEDERAL ACTS

In addition to the laws discussed above, there are a number of other laws that must be considered in natural resource management. Table 2-1 lists the major federal natural resource laws and regulations, along with a qualitative assessment on the likely influence they have on management activities at the BTC. The laws and regulations listed in the table could drive BLM natural resources management decisions in managing the federal public lands that compose the BTC. The Legal Information Institute, at <http://www.law.cornell.edu/topics/environmental.html>, conveniently provides the complete text of codified laws.

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APPENDIX E

VEGETATION MONITORING GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

E.1 INTRODUCTION

The following excerpt from the *Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site* (Jones 2000) provides an overview of the vegetation monitoring goals and objectives for the BTC:

- Management Goal 1: Maintain healthy and diverse ecosystems and wildlife habitats. (In the future, desired plant communities characteristics may be used to specify criteria for “healthy and diverse.”)
- Management Goal 2: Minimize the establishment and spread of undesirable non-native plants.
- Management Goal 3: Maintain upland watershed function: maintain soil stability, soil compaction, and susceptibility to erosion at current level, especially in areas of good condition versus significantly degraded/disturbed areas.
- Management Goal 4: Revegetate disturbed areas, where feasible, to provide habitat, stabilize soil, and minimize susceptibility to weed invasion.
- Management Goal 5: Minimize soil disturbance and vegetation loss.

For each Management Goal, specific monitoring objectives and general approaches to sampling are presented below. Detailed protocol for monitoring methods are provided in the *Vegetation Monitoring Protocols for the Central Oregon Training Site* (Jones 2000).

E.2 MAINTENANCE MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING

Maintenance monitoring applies to the overall condition of the BTC. By attempting to address Management Goal 1, soil stability, disturbance, and vegetation loss also are

addressed to some degree. Management Goals 1-3 will help to improve understanding of the relationship between land uses, habitat loss, soil stability, and weed invasion.

Management Goal 1 is to maintain healthy and diverse ecosystems and wildlife habitats. (In the future, desired plant communities characteristics may be used to specify criteria for "healthy and diverse.")

- **Management Objective 1a:** Maintain the mean native grass, forb, shrub, and tree cover within 20% of baseline levels (1999-2001) within each ecological stratum in each training area.
 - **Monitoring Objective:** We want to be 90% confident that mean cover estimates are within 10% of the estimated percent cover.
 - **Approach:** Permanent transects, point intercept along 100m line transect presence/absence by groundcover categories (basal intercept) and each unique species (aerial intercepts). Mean cover by functional group also provides information about vertical structure.
- **Management Objective 1b:** Maintain native grass and forb species diversity at 1999-2001 levels.
 - **Monitoring Objective:** We want to be 90% confident that richness and diversity estimates are within 10% of the estimated richness and diversity.
 - **Approach:** Nested frequency frames placed along permanent transects.

Management Goal 2 is to minimize the establishment and spread of undesirable non-native plants.

- **Management Objective 2:** Maintain the frequency of undesirable plant species (e.g., *Bromus tectorum*) within 10% of 1999-2001 mean levels between 2001 and 2005.
 - **Monitoring Objective:** We want to be 90% confident that the frequency of undesirable species is within 10% of estimated true mean.
 - **Approach:** Nested frequency frames placed along permanent transects.

Management Goal 3 is to maintain upland watershed function: maintain soil stability, soil compaction, and susceptibility to erosion at current level, especially in areas of good condition versus significantly degraded/disturbed areas.

- **Management Objective 3:** Maintain estimated sheet/rill soil loss and groundcover components at 1999-2001 levels.
 - **Monitoring Objective:** We want to be 90% confident that mean Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation estimates are within 20% of the estimated soil loss.

- Approach: Permanent transects, point intercept along transect; presence/absence by groundcover category and aerial cover by species.
- Additional General Monitoring Objective: Document and improve understanding of the effects of disturbance on plant community status and dynamics at the BTC.

E.3 REHABILITATION MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING

Rehabilitation management and monitoring applies to areas that are disturbed by off-road military activities including maneuvers, excavation, bivouac, and other activities and are subsequently revegetated using natural or artificial means. Monitoring plays an important role in evaluating the success of revegetation projects.

Management Goal 4 is to revegetate disturbed areas, where feasible, to provide habitat, stabilize soil, and minimize susceptibility to weed invasion.

- Management Objective 4: For revegetation sites, increase plant cover to within 50% of undisturbed plant cover after three years of recovery. Frequency of weed species should not exceed that found in undisturbed areas after three years (need to look at data from adjacent undisturbed areas or reference areas).
 - Monitoring Objective: We want to be 80% confident that the mean cover of desirable and undesirable plant species (aggregated by group) is within 20% of the estimated mean cover.
 - Approach: Cover frames placed randomly within individual revegetation areas – ten cover class system for “desirable” and “undesirable.”

E.4 DISTURBED AREA MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING

Soil surface disturbance has been identified as an indicator of site degradation. The focus of disturbance surveys is to identify disturbed sites spatially, broadly define the level of disturbance, and track these and additional areas over time to assess whether the proportion of the terrain in each disturbance category is decreasing, staying the same, or increasing.

Management Goal 5 is to minimize soil disturbance and vegetation loss.

- Management Objective 5: Allow no more than a 25% increase in new surface disturbance compared to 1999 levels.
 - Monitoring Objective: Locate and document that areas qualifying as “disturbed surface lands” using global positioning systems. Future maps are compared to the 1999 map to determine if a change $\geq 25\%$ has occurred. Estimate the extent (i.e., number of square meters) of disturbed lands in each category in moderate and high-use areas. Surveys are done on a site-by-site basis.
 - Monitoring Objective: Estimate the area of vegetation loss and the area of weed change for each site.

- Approach: Point mapping of disturbed sites (Objective 1). Visual estimates using ground surveys of disturbed areas (Objective 2), photographs of damaged areas, and permanent photo points.